

**An exploration of open innovation practices in food SMEs: A case
of UK-based Asian food wholesalers**

MD HABIBUR RAHMAN

February 2022

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of
the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Business Administration

DECLARATIONS

I declare that this doctoral research entitled “An exploration of open innovation practices in food SMEs: A case of UK-based Asian food wholesalers” was carried out in accordance with the regulations of the University of the West of Scotland. This thesis has not been submitted previously which has led to the award of an academic degree.

I also declare that all other works cited in the thesis have been appropriately referenced.

Name: MD HABIBUR RAHMAN

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to show my deepest gratitude to my lead supervisor Professor Wilson Ozuem who guided me towards completing my doctoral thesis. I would also like to thank the University professors and other members of staff for their academic support along the way. I am incredibly grateful to the examiners of my thesis Dr Gordon Bowen and Dr Imani Silver Kyaruzi, for providing their valuable insights to enhance the quality of the thesis significantly.

I would also like to extend my gratitude to the participants who shared their professional knowledge and experiences with me along this journey.

Finally, I would like to express my enormous gratitude towards my family for their continuous support and motivation, which helped me complete my doctoral thesis.

ABSTRACT

With increased globalisation worldwide, the number of ethnic communities globally is rising, and so are their demands for ethnic foods. The UK is home to diverse ethnic communities and has a rapidly growing ethnic food consumer market. A review of the existing literature indicated that, although the gross domestic product contribution of the ethnic food consumer market is growing, there is limited understanding in the literature regarding the kind of challenges wholesalers in the ethnic food business face and how Open Innovation can be used to mitigate those challenges. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs in an attempt to understand how they use Open Innovation practices to address their business problems and become competitive in the marketplace.

This research followed the interpretivist research philosophy and used the inductive research approach for theory creation. This research is based on qualitative inquiry and utilised a single case study research strategy to investigate SMEs in the UK-based South Asian Food wholesale sector. A total of 19 UK-based South Asian food wholesaler SMEs were investigated by interviewing directors and managers working at the decision-making levels. Besides, three industry experts were also interviewed to understand better how the UK food distribution industry works. Semi-structured interviews were conducted for data collection. The interviews lasted from 30 minutes to 1 hour and 15 minutes. The collected data was analysed using thematic analysis.

This research identified that UK-based South Asian food wholesaler SMEs face numerous challenges, such as lack of economies of scale, lack of market knowledge, lack of supplier–buyer coordination, and uncertainties following Brexit. This research also revealed that the outside-in (inbound) Open Innovation strategy is commonly used by UK-based South Asian food wholesaler SMEs to improve their products, processes, and services. This open innovation strategy is beneficial for SMEs as they can reduce their research and development expenditure through collaborations with external parties, such as customers, suppliers, and technological firms. The findings contribute to the literature by filling the existing knowledge gap. The study results also contribute to professional practice by providing practitioners in the UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs with recommendation on how to effectively utilise open innovation practices to enhance organisational competitiveness and performance.

Key Words: *Innovation, SMEs, Food Industry, Suppliers, Open Innovation, South Asian food, Customers, Collaboration.*

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Publications Associated with This Thesis

1. Open innovation practices and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).
Conference Paper: Global Business and Technology Association, (Bangkok, 2018).
2. Open innovation practice in the UK-based food sector SMEs: Ethnic minority.
Conference Paper: 24th UK Academy for Information Systems (UKAIS), (St. Catherine's College, Oxford, 2019).

ABBREVIATIONS

EPOS: Electronic Point of Sale

EU: European Union

F&B: Food and Beverage

FWD: Federation of Wholesale Distributors

KBV: Knowledge-Based View

MNEs: Multi-National Enterprises

OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

OI: Open Innovation

RBV: Resource-Based View

R&D: Research and Development

SMEs: Small and Medium Sized Enterprises

UK: United Kingdom

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Research Background

The term ‘innovation’ is increasingly used in many scientific fields, including geography, marketing, public policy, and regional science. It has also become a trendy word in discussions of business development. The phenomenon of business innovation emerged in early human settlements and has influenced civilisations and cultures ever since. The invention of new methods for production and supply has been invariably crucial to the survival of businesses in competitive markets. A small number of innovation strategies have led to agricultural and industrial revolutions creating continuous positive impacts on human life (Bruland and Mowery, 2006).

Significant technological advancements revolutionised businesses in the twentieth century through industrial research departments working on product development. The vertical integration of firms was the most common way to develop new technologies, and such efforts endowed firms with a competitive advantage over SMEs and start-up rivals (Chandler, 1990; West et al., 2006). Furthermore, economies of scale and economies of scope have set more prominent organisations apart from their rivals. In this traditional setting, innovations are produced and commercialised only within the limits of the company’s capabilities.

Innovation is known as an essential business strategy for organisational success. Innovation is often driven by external factors such as competition, deregulation, scarce resources, and customer demands (Damanpour, 2009; Baregheh et al., 2012). It is considered one of the most significant factors that enable firms to challenge significant competitors in both local and foreign markets. Such firms increasingly encounter new regulations and make structural changes to remain competitive in the industry (Rama, 2008; Sarkar and Costa, 2008; Capitano et al., 2009; Saguy and Sirotinskaya, 2016). Open innovation has been adopted by both Multi-national Enterprises (MNEs) as well as Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in manufacturing firms to discover, explore and exploit innovation within and outside of the organisation (Idrissia et al., 2012; Laursen and Salter, 2006; Lazzarotti et al., 2011).

Innovation in the food and drink industry is one of the most interesting topics in business management research (Huizingh, 2011). The food industry is the largest manufacturing sector within the European Union (EU). It is regarded as one of the most significant drivers of the EU

economy, contributing to financial and employment sectors (Avermaete, 2002; Menrad, 2004; Traill, 1998). SMEs are the backbone of most economies. Although food sector SMEs are considered low-tech, this sector is regarded as the most significant industry, with a total turnover of €528 billion in 2016. Some 99.1% of Europe's 285,000 food and drink companies are SMEs that collectively create 2.9 million jobs all over Europe (Food & Drink Report, 2017). The industry is viewed as a significant manufacturing sector in terms of its total turnover in France, Spain, and the UK (Food and Drink Federation, 2017).

Over the last decade, this industry has encountered many societal, economic, and technological changes that have had a significant impact on the entire food processing chain, starting from agricultural production to food production and distribution to end-users. Therefore, innovation is imperative for food sector firms. Many researchers believe that innovation plays an essential role in competitiveness and sustainability (Capitanio et al., 2010; Grunert, 2005; Rama and Filippaios, 2008). However, innovation has become increasingly dependent on developing appropriate external relationships - not just building internal capabilities, which has led to open innovation.

Chesbrough first conceived open innovation as a strategy in 2003. As the focus shifted from purely internal R&D activities, the academic community started recognising that organisations should be open to outside innovation (Rigby and Zook, 2002; Christensen et al., 2005). Open innovation (OI) is now regarded as one of the most critical topics in the innovation and management research literature (Chesbrough, 2003; Christensen et al., 2005; Gassmann, 2006; Giannopoulou et al., 2010; Huizingh, 2011; Lichtenhaler, 2011; Saidi et al., 2020). Although this area has been widely researched, there is no clear consensus as to what constitutes open innovation in practice.

OI strategies have been extensively implemented successfully across many industrial sectors such as the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) sector, pharmaceuticals, and the high-tech computing industry. Large organisations need to access new ideas and technologies to feed their innovation processes and, to do so, they must source these in a range of ways. This is particularly true for food firms where thousands of new food and household products have been introduced and launched into niche markets all around the world.

As the food sector is defined by its low Research and Development (R&D) intensity, most innovative processes are based on the external acquisition of technology without much regard for science (Costa, 2013; Garcia Martínez and Briz, 2000; Samadi, 2014). Firms ought to

collaborate with a variety of players and actors in the market and business environment rather than merely depending on internal R&D activities as in the closed innovation paradigm (Clausen and Pohjola, 2009; Piperopoulos, 2012; Wynarczyk and Piperopoulos, 2013). Chesbrough (2003) argues that firms should collaborate with external partners in order to face potential challenges. The mutual attraction between two firms can lead to the development of new products and services.

All companies endeavour to maximise profits. In addition, customer satisfaction is a vital aspect of food processing. Many food firms have now incorporated innovative strategies using open innovative technologies for profit maximisation. This is achieved whilst satisfying consumers and enhancing overall growth through cooperation. Prior to this, companies were reluctant to implement innovative strategies. However, this trend has changed in recent times, and firms are more dedicated to innovation in terms of their products and services. Many companies work together to share the common knowledge that has been attained in creative areas in the food sector (Melissa, 2007). Indeed, firms have realised over time that it is effectively cheaper to share the kinds of knowledge and skills applied in production lines. Many organisations have successfully implemented OI, such as Proctor and Gamble, Coca-Cola, Samsung, GE, Xerox, and other global brands. In addition, OI strategies have also been implemented in food sector SMEs.

Moreover, recent significant changes, both in the nature of food demand and supply chain organisations, and competitiveness in the market have made innovation a specific corporate activity that is fundamental to the overall profitability of the industry (Costa and Jongen, 2006). Notably, the demand for food has rapidly evolved into a mass customisation market (Boland, 2008; Costa et al., 2001). This new trend in food consumer demand has encouraged firms to use more sophisticated marketing techniques to better understand differentiated consumer needs (De Jong et al., 2006). This forces food firms to develop new products by adopting innovative technological solutions and new business models. This illustrates the significance of OI implementation in the food industry to enhance competitiveness and sustainability in the market.

1.2. Research Problem

Several research studies have been conducted in the context of the food and drink industry to investigate how open innovation can be used to enhance a firm's performance. For example, Huizingh (2011) revealed that OI practices can maximise a firm's return on innovation. It has been argued that OI can result in increased knowledge, lowered operational costs, reduced lead times to markets, and increased sales performance (Huizingh, 2011; Laursen and Salter, 2006; Tomlinson, 2010; Wang et al., 2015). Food sector firms, especially SMEs, commonly implement various OI strategies in attempts to address the competitive challenges faced in the market (Barney and Clark, 2007). OI helps SMEs mitigate resource constraints, scale limitations and their lack of technological resources (Dahlander and Gann, 2010; Spithoven et al., 2013; Bigliardi and Galati, 2016).

An investigation by Enzing et al. (2011) on the Dutch food and beverage industry highlighted the important roles OI strategies play in the long-term and short-term market performance of new products, such as for technology-related actors (companies providing training and supplying machinery and equipment) and market-related actors (customers, competitors, and marketing companies). Further, some researchers applied the concept of OI to addressing the competitive challenges faced by SMEs' competitors; for instance, Sadat and Nasrat's (2020) study in the Flanders region of Belgium investigated how open innovation strategies are practised by food SMEs. Similarly, a study of Lefebvre et al. (2015) showed how different external sources of knowledge play significant roles in product and process, market, and organisational innovations in food SMEs. Their study findings indicated that effective customer collaboration helps develop new or existing products and collaboration with competitors improves organisational innovation. Likewise, Bigliardi and Galati's (2016) study investigated factors such as knowledge, collaboration, and organisational, financial and strategic barriers that impede various Italian SMEs along with food and beverage SMEs in adopting open innovation. The results of Bigliardi and Galati's (2016) study were gathered only from survey data in various SMEs in Italy. In a similar vein, Saidi et al. (2020) identified factors that facilitated SMEs in open innovation activities, such as collaborating with external partners, by focusing on small enterprises.

Although numerous studies have been conducted to investigate how open innovation has been used by both big and small enterprises, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, no study has specifically focused on the food wholesale sector to understand how open innovation can be

used to enhance the competitiveness of ethnic food wholesaler SMEs. Hence, this study seeks to fill this existing knowledge gap in the literature by investigating a case of UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. This research seeks to investigate how UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs use open innovation and what kind of challenges they face whilst engaging in opening innovation practices.

The food industry is considered to be the biggest manufacturing sector in the EU (Menrad, 2004; Kuhne, 2011). According to Federation of Wholesale Distributors (2020), the food and drink wholesale distribution industry plays a significant role and makes a vital contribution of £31.1 billion per annum to the UK economy whilst employing 60,000 people across the country. The UK food and drink wholesale distribution industry has multiple sectors of which the South Asian food sector alone contributes £4 billion per annum to the UK economy. However, in recent years, South Asian food wholesale distribution SMEs have been exposed to tremendous challenges and their market share is plummeting due to the intense competition they face from their competitors, such as local supermarkets. Therefore, the current study seeks to investigate whether open innovation strategies can be implemented not only for addressing the demand of the consumer market but also to tackle the challenges they faced from competitors in the industry. The findings of this study will make significant contributions to professional practise by highlighting how the concept of open innovation can be effectively used in everyday business processes to mitigate the risks posed by competitors as well as to increase the business sustainability of UK Asian food and drink wholesale distribution SMEs. The next section of this chapter specifies the aim and objectives of this research.

1.3. Research Aim, Objectives, and Questions

1.3.1. Research Aim and Objectives

This research aims to make recommendations to the practitioners in UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs for enhancing their organisational competitiveness and performance through the implementation of open innovation strategies.

In order to achieve the above research aim, the following research objectives were formulated:

Objective 1: To critically review the existing literature related to Open Innovation to explore various OI strategies, OI models, the importance of OI to SMEs and challenges involving implementation of OI in SMEs.

Objective 2: To explore the strategic challenges faced by UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs.

Objective 3: To reveal the OI strategies used by UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs and evaluate their effectiveness in mitigating competitive barriers.

Objective 4: To understand how effective networking with external partners can facilitate OI in UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs.

Objective 5: To provide recommendations to the practitioners in UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs for enhancing their organisational competitiveness and performance based on the research findings.

1.3.2. Research Questions

The following main research question is established to achieve the aim:

How can the use of Open Innovation by UK-based South Asian Food wholesale SMEs enhance their competitiveness in the market?

In order to answer the main research question, the following research sub-questions have been constructed:

RQ 1: What are the key OI strategies and models available in the literature and how can OI be used to overcome the challenges faced by SMEs?

RQ 2: What are the strategic challenges faced by UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs?

RQ 3: What OI strategies are used by UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs and how do they help to effectively mitigate competitive barriers?

RQ 4: How can effective networking with external partners facilitate OI in UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs?

RQ 5: What kind of recommendations can be made to UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs for enhancing their organisational competitiveness and performance through the implementation of OI?

1.4. Rationale

Open innovation has become a widespread phenomenon as it provides firms with a new way to engage with consumers (Chesbrough, 2003, 2006; von Hippel, 2005; Dahlander and Gann, 2010; West and Bogers, 2011; Radziwon and Bogers, 2019). Many SMEs depend on their ability to be innovative to gain a competitive advantage (Parida et al., 2012). However, the usual success rate of innovative efforts tends to be lower than expectations. This is mainly due to the inherent complexity of innovation as well as to the high levels of risk alignment and uncertainty to the innovation process (Griffiths-Hemans and Grover, 2006; Koufteros, 2005). In addition, innovative development is usually challenging for SMEs due to the ‘liability of smallness’. This is because SMEs have limited financial resources (Grando and Belvedere, 2006). Furthermore, a lack of multidisciplinary competence and less structured approaches to innovation often restrict the ability of SMEs to innovate and attain competitiveness (Bianchi et al., 2011; De Tony and Nassimbeni, 2003).

Recent studies regarding innovation technology management have proposed several potential benefits of open innovation processes. Some have described a shift from traditional or closed innovation models with a primary focus on internal R&D to an OI approach (Chesbrough, 2003; Parida et al., 2012). With open innovation, businesses can develop new products and services quickly at lower costs. Moreover, it is believed that products developed in collaboration with stakeholders and suppliers are often seen to be more adherent to consumers’ choices (Soto-Acosta and Cegarra-Navarro, 2016; Cillo et al., 2019). Thus, consumers’ demands for more personalised products and the implementation of OI strategy are vital in enhancing competitiveness in the food sector. The food industry is usually deemed slow in

business growth, low R&D investment, and a tendency to be cautious in implementing innovation strategies. This is due to high consumer sensitivity to products and consumption patterns (Wicaksono et al., 2021).

Moreover, Wicaksono et al. (2021) revealed that implementing innovation in the food industry is a complex issue and requires time and effort. However, the ever-changing dynamics of customer needs and intense competition in the market force companies to innovate, which is an important element for the survival of businesses. Ismanu and Kusmintarti (2019) stated that innovation in SMEs is crucial in delivering quality products and services and thus improving competitiveness in the market. Furthermore, Gaynor (2002) outlined innovation as a driving force for businesses' sustainability as it helps organisational growth. Similarly, Ortiz-Villajos (2014) emphasised the importance of innovation for the continuity of any enterprise. Therefore, innovation is a significant component of a business strategy that leads to a competitive advantage.

Many scholars agree that open innovation could be useful for both SMEs and large firms (Chesbrough, 2003; Chesbrough et al., 2006; Lichtenthaler, 2008). However, the initial research on open innovation mainly focused on multinational organisations. SMEs are different from large firms in terms of how they exploit OI activities for specific outcomes. SMEs face some inherent limitations, such as a lack of financial resources for R&D, unstructured innovative processes, and underdeveloped internal capabilities (Chesbrough and Crowther, 2006; Lichtenthaler, 2008; Madrid-Guijarro et al., 2009). On the other hand, SMEs are usually less bureaucratic, more willing to take risks and in possession of specialised knowledge. They tend to react quickly to change management activities which enables them to be better than larger organisations at adopting OI activities (Christensen et al., 2005; Stam and Elfring, 2008). Although OI plays a substantial role in the success of food SMEs, most recent studies of OI in food and beverage merely focused on observations of the effects of OI on innovation. They disregarded the drivers that could potentially encourage food and beverage firms to engage in OI activities. Therefore, the current study focuses on OI in the context of UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. The findings of this research will provide interesting insights not only because they will reveal how UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs utilise OI and what types of challenges they face in terms of implementing OI, but also inferences may be drawn from the findings on how ethnic food wholesalers utilise OI to enhance their competitiveness. Therefore, it is anticipated that the findings will add substantial value to the literature.

The food industry is considered one of the most significant industrial sectors of the global economy, and it ranks high in terms of employment, turnover, and value-added investment. The food processing industry was traditionally characterised as the most reluctant industry to embrace new technologies (Brasili and Fanfani, 2006). The food processing industry has long been associated with low technology from a historical perspective. In fact, R&D activities in the food industry are considered of secondary importance compared to other industrial sectors, for instance, the chemical industry and the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) industry (Samadi, 2014).

Even though multinational food companies invest heavily in R&D, most large and multinational companies do not have the means to invest in modern laboratories and intensive research. However, it is noticeable that the food industry has dramatically changed over the last decade. For instance, competition has been amplified in both national and international markets, and the industry has encountered a string of threats to food processing. Furthermore, a range of cultural and environmental issues have arisen in the food debate (Avermaete and Viaene, 2002).

Avermaete and Viaene (2002) suggest that the food industry should undertake innovative processes to improve product quality, expand consumer confidence and encourage modernisation. Innovation is considered one of the primary determinants of success and long-term survival for companies in the food industry. Mansfield (1995) stated that academic research has contributed to business innovation activities in various sectors. Innovation is achieved through R&D, which is carried out by universities and research centres that apply efficient methods to production and supply in the food industry (Samadi, 2014). Universities have much pressure to raise research funding to actively contribute to industrial innovation (Muscio et al., 2010).

Industrial policy depends a great deal on technology transfer as a tool for developing knowledge incentive economies and increased competitiveness (Bozeman, 2000). Despite having excellent innovation potential, the food industry is generally based on 'redundant technologies' (Muscio et al., 2010). SMEs are actively involved in the food industry. Studies have indicated that SMEs adopt OI in practice due to the need for external resources that could help develop and commercialise new products (Samadi, 2014). However, the industrial structure is generally composed of SMEs with low R&D capacity. The introduction of

innovation in the food industry is strongly influenced by demand conditions (Muscio et al., 2010).

Schumpeterian (1934) postulates that prominent firms are more innovative because of economies of scale in research and development and better technological knowledge and capabilities. Therefore, it can be said that the bigger the firm, the higher the probability of success. On the other hand, Stock et al. (2002) argued that SMEs are more innovative in comparison to large firms because of their entrepreneurial attitude, flexibility, dynamism, and less bureaucratic management. Furthermore, Spithoven et al. (2012) suggested that SMEs, compared to large firms, are more effective in using different OI simultaneously when introducing a new product or service in the market.

In summary, it can be said that large firms are more likely to engage in product and process innovation, but the extent to which they radically implement innovation in their products is not as great as compared to the situation with SMEs. In contrast, SMEs innovate less, but innovation amongst these businesses is more radical than innovation in bigger companies (Beyona-Saez et al., 2017). OI is prevalent in the food industry principally to be competitive and sustainable in the market. The researcher has some practical knowledge of SMEs in terms of how they seek to compete with large firms in the UK market. This was behind the motivation to conduct research to identify solutions to issues of competitiveness and sustainability in the competitive UK market.

1.5. Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is divided into six chapters.

Chapter One presents an introduction and background to the study, and it identifies the problem statement associated with this research. It identifies several gaps in knowledge and sets out the aim and objectives of the study. The study's rationale is to extend knowledge and contribute to the chosen area of study.

Chapter Two analyses extant literature concerning open innovation and food SMEs. The chapter introduces open innovation and its core processes. The chapter expands by critically discussing OI strategies and the role of SMEs in innovation. Next, it discusses open innovation in the food industry SMEs. Furthermore, it critically reviews open innovation concerning products and processes. The applicability of open innovation for overcoming challenges in food sector SMEs are illustrated. This chapter also examines the importance and benefits of OI

practices and the associated challenges of adopting OI in food and beverage distributing firms. Finally, the chapter ended by developing a conceptual framework illustrating how networking and collaboration lead to open innovation in SMEs.

Chapter Three discusses the research methodology and sets out the research design for this study. It identifies the research paradigm and defends the chosen paradigm in detail. It also explains why the study followed a qualitative inquiry route and how the data were collected to achieve study objectives. This chapter also briefly describes respondents' profiles and the company background.

Chapter Four presents the data analysis of participant responses from interviews. This chapter presents the rationale for thematic analysis for analysing interview data. This follows by the findings and discussion of interviews with the directors and managers of South Asian food wholesale SMEs as well as the industry experts. The six major themes extracted from the interview data are critically discussed in order to achieve the research objectives.

The following chapter (In Chapter Five) develops a Conceptual Model and synthesises significant findings from the literature, and the factual data gathered via fieldwork.

The last chapter (Chapter Six) concludes the thesis by revisiting the research objectives. A recommendation has been made in this chapter for the practitioners of UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs to effectively utilise open innovation practices for enhancing competitiveness in the market. In addition, this chapter outlines the contribution to knowledge. The study limitations and opportunities for future research are also outlined.

1.6. Summary

This chapter presented an overview of the research. It provided a brief background to open innovation. It also outlined the rationale for conducting the research. It identified literature gaps in the context of South Asian food wholesale SMEs and set out the problem statement for the study. The aim and objectives of the study, along with the main research question and sub-questions, were identified in this chapter. The next chapter critically reviews the extant literature in relation to open innovation in food SMEs.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to critically review the existing literature related to Open Innovation, its processes, and its usefulness for addressing the challenges faced by SMEs in the wholesale food industry. In this chapter, various OI processes and strategies have been reviewed, along with the existing models on OI. For the construction of this chapter, various peer-reviewed journal articles, books and reliable government websites have been visited. This chapter initially deals with the concept of Open Innovation, which is then followed by how OI can be used by SMEs to address the challenges they face. In the latter section of the chapter, a conceptual framework is conceptualised based on the findings of the literature.

2.2. Applicability of Open Innovation to Food SMEs

Companies face many challenges nowadays and thus are forced to discover better ways to stay competitive. Innovation is considered a decisive factor for economic growth and the creation of competitiveness for any organisation (Almeida, 2021; Maier et al., 2020). In the traditional innovation process, companies entirely rely on internal ideas, knowledge, and skills for the development of new innovations (Felin and Zenger, 2014). However, OI enables firms to engage with external parties and generate ideas that eventually lead to innovation. OI is an innovation management model developed by Chesbrough (2003a, 2003b, 2004). According to Chesbrough (2003a), the urgency of innovation occurs based on firms' needs. Firms should utilise both internal and external technological developments to produce a successful innovation strategy that brings added value for the organisation. Open innovation is now considered the driving force that stimulates technology management and innovation management in organisations (Lichtenthaler, 2011; Zanjirichi et al., 2019).

Open innovation is important because the core of OI is based on sharing organisational knowledge with customers, suppliers, and competitors in the market (Hagedoorn and Zobel, 2015; Zanjirichi et al., 2019). Open innovation has the potential to guide companies to value creation. Through OI strategies, firms engage in an inter-organisational network to spread the risks as well as the uncertainty which may occur in markets, shorten innovation time, and reduce the costs in the innovation process (Cantner et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2010; Lefebvre et al., 2015; Hoffmann and Schlosser, 2001).

Initially, the academic literature on OI was mostly concentrated on large firms (Chesbrough, 2006; Gassman et al., 2010). However, more recently, a number of OI studies have emerged in the context of SMEs (Berends et al., 2014; Tobiassen et al., 2018). SMEs have the advantage of being flexible and less bureaucratic, which allows them to respond quickly to any business changes (Berends et al., 2014; Lasagni, 2012; Nieto and Santamaria, 2010; Tobiassen et al., 2018). Thus, OI could be highly relevant to SMEs for addressing the business challenges they face. Besides, OI is also relevant for SMEs to mitigate resource constraints, scale limitations and have fewer technological assets (Narula, 2004; Dahlander and Gann, 2010; Chesbrough, 2011).

Whilst being relevant to many other industries, OI is also relevant to the food industry. Studies on the food industry highlighted that open innovation and collaborative networks guide organisations to increase competitiveness, customer satisfaction, and, hence, sustainability (Annosi et al., 2020; Kiessling et al., 2019; Bogers et al., 2020; Kafetzopoulos et al., 2020; Enzing et al., 2011; Garcia Martinez et al., 2014). Food and drinks firms that have successfully implemented open innovation appear to have a more robust long-term position on the market and better profitability (Bayona-Saez et al., 2017; Enzing et al., 2011; Miglietta et al., 2017).

Food sector SMEs face structural confines in their access to external information with implications for their competencies (Muscio et al., 2010). Two significant factors potentially restrict SME's innovation. Firstly, even if SMEs are aware of their business disorientations, they may find it difficult to resolve such issues. In other words, their cognitive limits hinder the immersion of clearly understood business requirements and intelligible demand for innovation. Consequently, the public sectors find it difficult to offer support for, and to promote the development of the industry.

Secondly, SMEs' possible and real innovation requirements must be interpreted and translated into innovation projects and collaboration programmes with external organisations. While the previous points to cognition and learning, the latter affords scope for intermediaries in the innovation system (Zollo and Winter, 2002; Volberda et al., 2009; Zahra et al., 2005; West, 2007; Howells, 2006; Yousuf, 2008). Furthermore, there is likely to be a different bundling of resources and capabilities (Peteraf and Barney, 2003; Teece, 2007).

There are many significant reasons why food SMEs should implement OI strategies in their businesses. According to Chesbrough (2003), many firms have applied open innovation as a necessary organisational adaptation to changes in the environment. As a result of globalisation

and mobile workers as well as venture capital, widely distributed knowledge and reduced product life cycles, most firms can no longer afford to innovate on their own. An interview-based study conducted by Chesbrough and Crowther (2006) found that the most common reason for external technology acquisition was a common belief that it is critical to maintaining growth for sustainability. Fundamental entrepreneurial values such as growth and revenues will be the essential motives of firms to implement and practise open innovation.

Prior studies into the conditions for OI only concentrate on Multinational Enterprises (MNEs) and only, therefore, cover a handful of open innovation practices (Van de Vrande et al., 2009). An example is the R&D managers of MNEs involved in venturing for market-related motives such as meeting customer demands and gaining new knowledge (EIRMA, 2003). Similarly, Jacobs and Waalkens (2001) study found that innovation processes are used to reduce ‘time-to-market’ and utilise inner creativity. However, Van de Vrande et al. (2009) criticised these studies and suggested market considerations and knowledge creation are key motives for OI.

Other potential motives can result from innovative collaboration studies. Van de Vrande et al. (2009) suggest that firms can collaborate with other firms to attain missing knowledge, complementary resources, or financial intelligence and to share risks. Such activity leads to social networking opportunities within the marketplace and reduces costs (Hoffman and Schlosser, 2001). These motives mainly reflect outside-in considerations, while motives to conduct outbound activities are often absent. However, Karuna (2004) acknowledges several objectives firms follow to externally exploit their knowledge, and these include raising revenues, setting industry standards to gain profit from infringements, realising learning effects and guaranteeing freedom to operate by establishing cross-licensing agreements with other firms.

2.3. Open Innovation

2.3.1. An Introduction to Open Innovation

Understanding how to manage innovation successfully is significant at a time when change has become a prerequisite survival strategy (Drucker, 1999). At the same time, innovation is a risk-taking strategy because it can lead to the demise of the organisation (Olleros, 1986; Tellis and Golder, 1996). Many innovation management studies are normative in nature and focus on how to innovate successfully. Given that innovation management has changed over the last few decades, notions of what counts as success or best practice have also altered over time

(Rothwell, 1994). However, historical divisions may have been accurate in recent years, and modern innovation practices advocate that organisations do not automatically decide to adopt best practices as prescribed by the dominant model of their time. (Ortt and Van der Duin, 2008). In fact, innovation managers often decide upon various innovation processes based on a context.

The term ‘innovation’ is increasingly used across various scientific fields. Innovation is recognised as making a significant contribution to organisational success, performance, and survival. Innovations vary significantly in their nature. Damanpour (2009) advocates that pressure from the external environment often determine the urgency of organisational innovation management processes. These factors include competition, deregulation, isomorphism, scarce resources, and customer demand (Baregheh et al., 2012). Damanpour (1996) defines innovation as a multifaceted construct that encompasses the generation, development, and implementation of a new idea or behaviour to the adopting organisation.

Through the innovation process, these new ideas transform into new products and services, new process technologies, new organisational structures, or new managerial approaches (Damanpour and Aravind, 2011). Some innovation typologies have been proposed in past studies (Damanpour et al., 2009). The technological-organisational typology is popular among management researchers and refers to a general distinction between the firm’s technologies and administrative systems along with “organisational innovation” and “management innovation” processes (Azar and Ciabuschi, 2017).

Damanpour and Evan (1984) describe technological innovation as the enactment of a concept for developing a new product or service or introducing new elements in an organisation's production process or service operation. On the other hand, organisational innovation means the generation and application of management practices, methods, structures, or techniques that are the most recent, state of the art examples intended to further corporate goals (Birkinshaw et al., 2008).

Another significant distinction of innovation typology is the degree of innovation radicalness (Azar and Ciabuschi, 2017). Innovation radicalness refers to the degree to which innovations are ground-breaking and disruptive and trigger significant amendments to the organisation's internal activities (Damanpour and Aravind, 2011: 436).

Companies seldom innovate on their own, and instead do so in cooperation with agents (Bayona-Saez et al., 2017). Innovation processes are systematic and interactive. Research into

the interactive process has increased following Chesbrough's (2003) publication. This led to an increased understanding of the categorisation of innovation. Open innovation is one type of innovation management in the business world. Open innovation is amongst the more recent innovation strategies in business management research. Chesbrough (2003) coined the term 'open innovation' to describe a shift in innovation paradigms from closed or in-house R&D to an OI model which is associated with internal and external ideas, knowledge, and technologies to create and commercialise new products and services.

OI encompasses some important changes in corporate innovation activities which can be characterised as more distributed, multidisciplinary, trans-border forms of cross-institutional and inter-temporal innovation which vary from the types of innovation typical of the 20th century which were confined to one conceptual framework (Bianchi et al., 2011; Chiaroni et al., 2011; Dalhandera and Gann, 2010; Huizingh, 2011). This framework postulates that innovation reaches beyond R&D activities and is regarded as the result of the smart and targeted combined use and application of knowledge and competencies with special emphasis on the willingness to integrate third party 'knowledge and abilities into organisational activities (Vanhaverbeke and Cloudt, 2014).

In a broad sense, OI implies that innovation results from sharing competencies between different players along and beyond the value chain, with profound implications for external relationships (Chesbrough, 2003; Chesbrough et al., 2006). It is assumed that OI is the preserve of more prominent organisations.

Therefore, initial research into OI mainly focused on the adoption of OI approaches and practices in sizeable high-tech industries, such as IBM, Xerox, Adidas, and Proctor & Gamble who managed innovation and new product development as internal processes (Chesbrough, 2003; Walcher, 2006; Dodgson et al., 2006). Success profoundly depended on the tacit knowledge, R&D capacity, and technology in these businesses to develop new products which represented significant strategic assets (Wynarczyk, 2013). The 'closed innovation paradigm' labelled by Chesbrough (2003) provided a considerable entry barrier for potential competitors, particularly small and medium-sized firms for whom retaining competitive advantage and lead time in the market was considered more difficult (Teece, 1986). Subsequently, research advocates that OI is also being practised in SMEs (Bianchi et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2010; Van de Vrande et al., 2009; Wynarczyk, 2013). However, empirical studies on OI practices in SMEs remain relatively rare (Wynarczyk et al., 2013).

There are various definitions of OI. An early definition defined it as “the use of purposive inflows and outflows of knowledge to accelerate internal innovation and to increase the markets for external use of innovation respectively” (Chesbrough et al., 2006:1). Thus, it comprises both the outside in and inside out movement of ideas and technologies. This can also be referred to as ‘technology acquisition’ and ‘technology exploitation’ (Lichtenthaler, 2008).

Table 2-1: Definitions of OI

Source	Definitions of Open Innovation
Chesbrough (2006)	Open Innovation is the use of purposive inflows and outflows of knowledge to accelerate internal innovation, and expand the markets for external use of innovation, respectively.
Laursen & Salter (2006)	An Open Innovation model is using a wide range of external actors and sources to help them achieve and sustain innovation.
West & Gallagher (2006)	Open innovation as systematically encouraging and exploring a wide range of internal and external sources for innovation opportunities, consciously integrating that exploration with firm capabilities and resources, and broadly exploiting those opportunities through multiple channels.
Dittrich & Duysters (2007)	The system is referred to as open because the boundaries of the product development funnel are permeable. Some ideas from innovation projects are initiated by other parties before entering the internal funnel; other projects leave the funnel and are further developed by other parties.
Chesbrough & Bogers (2014)	As a distributed innovation process based on purposively managed knowledge flows across organizational boundaries, using pecuniary and non-pecuniary mechanisms in line with the organization’s business model.
Banu et al. (2016)	Government, research organisations, clients and consumers, suppliers, business actors, aiming at linking human, financial, material resources, information, and knowledge for the purpose of obtaining shared-value innovation.
Greco et al. (2016)	Innovating capability of a firm deriving from the interaction with other firms.
Zobel et al. (2017)	Firms make greater use of external knowledge and increasingly collaborate with a variety of external partners.

Firms can no longer rely on the traditional model of closed innovation. Indeed, firms progressively depend on external sources of knowledge and collaborate with individuals, companies and other organisations that hold similar knowledge that may be deployed in the context of tacit innovation process (Chesbrough, 2003; Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; von Hippel, 2005). “Innovation can result from distributed inter-organisational networks, rather than from single-firms (West and Gallagher, 2006:320).”

Similarly, “The open innovation system is referred to as open because the boundaries of the product development funnel are permeable. Other parties initiate some ideas from innovation projects before entering the internal funnel; other projects leave the funnel and are further developed by other parties” (Dittrich and Duysters, 2007:512).

Open innovation is a paradigm which assumes that firms should use both external as well as internal ideas, and internal paths to market, as firms look to develop new technology (Chesbrough et al., 2006). Open innovation highlights the significance of applying a wide range of knowledge sources to a range of invention processes relative to customers, competitors, academics, and companies in different sectors (West and Gallagher, 2006).

Chesbrough (2003a) presents six principles of innovation, so-called closed innovation, countering these principles with so-called open innovation.

Table 2-2: Contrasting Principles of Closed and Open Innovation

Closed Innovation	Open Innovation
1. All the smart people work in our organisation.	1. Not all the smart people work in our organisation.
2. To profit from R&D we should discover, develop, and supply everything ourselves.	2. External R&D can create value for organisation.
3. Only if we discover we manage to get it to the market.	3. Internal R&D is needed to grasp that value.
4. If our organisation is the first to commercialise an innovation, we will beat our competitors.	4. We must be involved with basic research to benefit from it, but the discovery does not have to be ours.
5. If we create the most and best ideas in our industry, we will win the market.	5. If we make better use of external and internal ideas and unify the knowledge created, we will win.
6. If we have the full control over the innovation process our rivals will not be able to profit from our innovation ideas.	6. We should optimise the results of our organisation, combine sale or licensing of our innovation with the purchase of external innovation processes wherever they are more efficient and economic.

Source: Chesbrough (2003a; 2003b).

2.3.2. Chesbrough's Conceptualization of Open Innovation

In the early 21st century, many organisations conquered new markets with their innovative products and services (Ettabaa et al., 2019). The term open innovation refers to organisations that rely not just on their internal knowledge and capabilities for innovations but also use other external sources to drive innovation. Businesses and organisations have always welcomed feedback from external bodies for the improvement of products and services. Henry Chesbrough first coined the term open innovation; his conceptualisation of OI has been explained below.

Figure 2-1: Open Innovation Funnel Model

Source: Chesbrough (2004)

(Figure 2-1 reproduced with permission of the right holder)

Chesbrough (2003a) perceives that, useful ideas are generated both inside and outside of the company and can reach the market inside and outside of the company as well. OI places external ideas and external paths to market on the same level of importance that is typically reserved for internal thoughts and trails in a closed innovation model. From a variety of disciplinary perspectives, OI can seem ‘old hat’ (Freel and Robson, 2017). Interactive and network models of innovation have attained something of a normative status over the last few decades. Some continue to defend the more traditional linear model of innovation (Balconi et al., 2010). Chesbrough’s closed innovation model has the appearance of a Strawman (Freel and Robson, 2017).

It has been contended that the practice of OI obliges firms to combine internal and external ideas, with technology and R&D, and use inbound and outbound paths to distribute their products as they attempt to commercialise and advance their technologies (Chesbrough, 2003:23) in the market. An OI strategy allows external ideas to be taken to market through external channels, outside the firm’s internal mechanisms, to engender additional value (Wynarczyk, 2013).

Moreover, Vanhaverbeke et al. (2008) recognised four extensive benefits associated with OI practices. Firstly, innovative companies benefit from early involvement in new technologies and business opportunities. OI practice allows innovative companies to sense developments in a wide range of externally developed inventions by acquiring minority stakes (high tech) in start-ups and by participating in venture capital funds. They can also keep up to speed with

developments through educational investments in promising projects at universities or research labs. The main advantage of OI strategy adaptation is that firms learn early about new technologies in the market.

Moreover, tapping into externally developed technologies also increases the upward potential real option (this allows companies to scrutinise a broad range of technologies and new market developments instead of waiting for opportunities from internal projects alone). This is the case since firms can scan through a wide range of interesting ideas and projects. Secondly, innovative companies benefited from late entry and delayed financial commitment. The staged process in which new technologies are developed and commercialised into new business opportunities can be analysed as a compound option. Unlike closed innovation, OI practice is based on more flexibility as regards when to begin the internal portion of the innovation process.

Moreover, delayed investment allows firms to consider a broader portfolio of entry options at the outset. This also encourages more ways to develop growth opportunities from technology. Third, OI underscores for the firm the advantage of an early exit. OI is characterised by the possibility that innovative companies can license or sell technologies or spin-off ventures that are not promising enough in the market.

Moreover, OI activities improve access to other organisations' technological capabilities or higher R&D productivity through the combination of internal and external channels to market (Vanhaverbeke et al., 2008). OI has been associated with a wide spectrum of activities that fall into two distinct categories, such as inbound and outbound innovation. However, Gassmann and Enkel (2005) suggested that coupled innovation processes were also relevant to open innovation management.

2.3.3. Product Development through Open Innovation

Although OI is a widely researched topic, there is no unified definition of OI practice. Gassmann and Enkel (2005) recognised three 'core processes' in OI that may have constructive effects on corporate innovativeness. These include the 'Outside-In Process', which consists of all activities associated with external technology sourcing. 'The inside out' process creates profit by bringing ideas to the market, selling 'intellectual property' (IP), and using burgeoning technology to transfer ideas to the outside environment. Moreover, 'the coupled innovation' process combines both inbound and outbound innovation processes by working in alliance with

complementary partners. Reciprocal relationships play a significant role in success. All three methods signify an open innovation strategy.

Figure 2-2: The core processes of open innovation

Source: Chesbrough (2003a)

(Figure 2-2 reproduced with permission of the rights holder)

2.3.3.1. The Outside-in Process of Open Innovation

In the era of open innovation, the importance of access to public knowledge has gained significant attention (Lichtenthaler, 2008a). In this context, firms are part of an environment that is characterised by distributed knowledge, and the innovation process is distributed through a number of actors in the innovation system (Tether, 2002; Acha and Cusmano, 2005). The 'Inbound (outside-in) process of open innovation' sees the firm determine to invest in co-operation with suppliers and customers and to integrate internal ideas with external knowledge. Enterprises can gain external knowledge from different market-based partners, such as customers, suppliers, rival groups, and science-based partners, including universities and research centres (Santoro et al., 2017). In 'inbound' open innovation, firms search for new ideas and technologies beyond organisational boundaries, drawing on networks and knowledge sources (Ya-Huan Wu et al., 2016). As seen in the IBM industry solution lab case, IBM invests

heavily in contact with customers, suppliers, and other external knowledge sources. Cisco invests in young start-up companies with the aim of monitoring their attractiveness and innovations. Opening the internal innovation process by integrating suppliers and customers is not new. Many scholars who have looked at inter-firm and supplier relationship management postulate that organisations can benefit from inbound open innovation if they can set up differentiated relationships with suppliers (Dyer et al., 1998). Inbound open innovation, which requires search processes, tends to exist within many companies. These search processes are generally known as "Absorptive Capacity."

The concept of Absorptive Capacity is defined by Cohen and Levinthal (1990:128) as "the ability of a firm to identify the value of new, external Information, adapt it and then apply it to commercial ends". The success of a company's absorptive capacity will depend on individuals who stand at the crossroads of the firm and the external environment. Spithoven et al. (2011) postulate that it is relevant to study absorptive capacity about understanding inbound open innovation in population firms, often lacking formal R&D departments, in traditional sectors. Previous literature clearly illustrates that SMEs in conventional sectors do not abstain from engaging in inbound open innovation (Muscio, 2007; Therin, 2007). Despite the low levels of absorptive capacity which they discard, firms in traditional industries are still quite able to apply OI and engage in inbound oriented open innovation activities (Gann, 2001; Chesbrough and Crowther, 2006).

However, the performance of these activities in SMEs may be different from the performance of their large counterparts, or companies in high-tech sectors. Cohen and Levinthal (1990:128) argue that the ability of a company to identify the value of new, external information and to assimilate and eventually apply it in practice to commercial ends is critical to its innovation capacity. Therefore, it is imperative to understand the concept of absorptive capacity for successful inbound OI activities, which are characterised by a reliance on external knowledge. In other words, absorptive capacity is important to support organisational innovativeness (Gebauer et al., 2012; Lane et al., 2006; Muller et al., 2020). According to Escribano et al. (2009), absorptive capacity is a fundamental aspect for firms to gain a competitive advantage. It is particularly important for successful inbound open innovation processes for any organisation.

Inbound open innovation is a strategic choice for organisations. The fundamental concept of open innovation is that firms are always scouting for innovative ideas and information to

dominate the market or to enter new market segments (Spithoven et al., 2012). These innovative ideas can be attained from external sources of information of the type discussed in the above paragraphs.

However, SMEs have limited human resources to screen the outward environment for valuable information in comparison to large firms (Van de Vrande et al., 2009; Dahlander and Gann 2010; Chesbrough 2011). The process of developing and introducing innovation is a complicated matter which drives the need to source expertise from outside partners. Consequently, the use of external sources to innovate can be significant to improve or speed up innovation (Laursen and Salter 2006; Van de Vrande et al., 2009).

As the complexity of innovation processes is influenced by technical and scientific progress, the knowledge base of many firms is inadequate to control all aspects of the innovation process. Open innovation practices are relevant for SMEs since many struggles with the liability of smallness, scarce resources, financial constraints, and fewer technological assets to bargain with their rivals (Narula 2004; Dahlander and Gann 2010; Chesbrough, 2011).

Small firms have the advantage of more open up than large firms to access into external knowledge and technology for innovative purposes (Mesquita and Lazzarini, 2008). Though previous studies have emphasised the benefits of OI for firms, there are some potential risks inherent to opening up to innovation processes. Vanhaverbeke et al. (2002) criticised the fact that companies engage in inbound open innovation without developing strong technological competencies internally. This can result in some over dependence on external parties. In addition, firms depend significantly on external firms involved in inbound OI and thus run the risk of encountering high competition in the market as externalising competitively relevant know-how may add to the strength of competitors (Fosfuri, 2006). Thus, SMEs find these risks more challenging than large firms.

Inbound open innovation includes networking and collaboration with other firms or universities to develop products involving customers or end users in product development activities and licensing- in off intellectual property from other firms.

2.3.3.2. The Inside-out Process of Open Innovation

The outbound (Inside-out) dimension of OI processes refers to ‘the practice of exploiting technology capacities by utilising not only internal ideas but also external ways of

commercialisation' (Chesbrough, 2003; Chesbrough and Crowther, 2006). Outbound practices are the processes by which companies disclose information or sell their technology in the market (Chesbrough 2006; Faems et al., 2010; West and Bogers 2014; Lichtenthaler 2015). Enkel et al. (2009) also define outbound open innovation as earning profits by bringing ideas to the marketplace as well as selling intellectual property and multiplying technology by transferring ideas to the outside environment. Firms focus on external paths to commercialise innovations that have been developed rather than becoming dependent entirely on internal paths to be more productive in the marketplace. In addition, companies always search for external organisations with a business model that is more suitable to commercialise a given technology (Chiaroni et al., 2011).

However, Chesbrough (2012) argues that the difference between open innovation and previous models on collaborative innovation is an outbound feature that deals with how firms utilise and commercialise their internally produced unused innovation, such as licensing out their intellectual property/or spin-offs. Van de Vrande et al. (2009) postulate three practices: venturing, outward licensing of IP and the involvement of non-R&D workers in the innovation process for effective implementation of outbound innovation strategies. Venturing implies starting up companies through spin-off and spin-out strategies. Support can come from the existing competencies and resources such as finance, human power, legal advice, and administrative services.

Intellectual property plays a vital role as a result of inflows and outflows of knowledge for successful open innovation strategies (Arora, 2002; Chesbrough, 2003, 2006; Lichtenthaler, 2007). Organisations can attain more value by out licensing their intellectual property in the market. The out-licensing of intellectual property allows the firm to make more profit when other organisations from diverse business models find profitable external paths to the end market (Van de Vrande et al., 2009). The degree to which firms out-license their intellectual property decisions depends on anticipated revenues and profit-dissipation effects (Arora et al., 2001). Organisations gain profits from licensees as a form of licensing payments.

However, current profit might decline if the licensee uses licensing technology to compete in the same market as the licensor. Early research on outbound open innovation has illustrated the significance of establishing a reputation as a knowledge provider to proliferate the monetary and strategic benefits of technology out-licensing (Lichtenthaler and Ernst, 2007).

The third way to benefit from internal knowledge is to exploit the initiatives and knowledge of current employees including personnel that are not directly deployed in the research and development department. Several case studies show that informal interactions between employees from different organisations are crucial to understanding how products are developed and commercialised in the end market (Chesbrough et al., 2006).

Many management practitioners and scientists endorse the view that innovation by individual employees is a means to foster organisational success (Van de Ven, 1986). Nowadays, work has become more knowledge-based and less rigidly defined. In this context, employees can provide suggestions and be more interactive towards the benefits of organisations (Van Dijk and Van den Ende, 2002).

Although outbound OI carries the risk that core knowledge can be leaked and compromised in the process of conducting outbound open innovation in practice, many organisations including IBM and Dow Chemical company achieved great profits from licensing out their technology to other enterprises (Enkel et al., 2013; Kline, 2013). Outbound open innovation introduces liquidity into the gradual assumption and application of technology among enterprises in technology trading markets and positively impacts development (Lichtenthaler, 2014). Hence, the commercial value of outbound OI increases as technical exchange and cooperation between international organisations get closer (Ji et al., 2016).

Commercialising tacit ideas in different industries (cross-industry innovation) can increase revenue immensely. Many organisations have successfully marketed their business ideas within various sectors. Pharmaceutical industries such as Novartis Pharma or Roche are well known for substances initially intended for one ailment but ended up being used to treat other diseases. For example, Botox was initially developed as a nerve toxin but is now successfully used for anyone who has wrinkles or other skin lines that they want to remove.

In addition, commercialising tacit ideas outside the industry, as well as outsourcing, can be effective to channel knowledge or ideas to the external environment. Commercialising comprises the acquisition of knowledge on a market basis and the licensing of technologies from a second party (Grandstrand et al., 1992; Haour, 1992; Leonard-Barton, 1995; Veuglers and Cassiman, 1999). There are numerous benefits of outsourcing, including gaining access to new areas of knowledge, managing capacity issues, concentrating core competencies, and sharing costs (Haour, 1992). In addition, inside-out OI processes help to decrease the fixed costs of R&D.

2.3.3.3. *The Coupled Process of Open Innovation*

Coupled OI is one of the key core processes of OI. It is defined as the purposeful and simultaneous use of both inbound and outbound open innovation by collaborating with firms or communities. Gassmann and Enkel (2004:1) suggested that in an interfirm context coupled innovation is the practice of “linking outside-in and inside-out by working in alliances with complementary firms during which give, and take are crucial for success”. Similarly, Wynarczyk (2013) suggested that ‘coupled process innovation’ denotes a partnership or “co-creation” mainly linked to complementary partners through supply chains, clusters, alliances, cooperation, and joint ventures.

Organisations adopt OI via alliances, cooperation, and joint ventures with other firms to commercialise innovation. Although Enkel et al. (2009) suggest that “coupled innovation processes” combine both inbound and out-bound knowledge flows, a comprehensive model of coupled innovation was developed by Dhalander and Gann (2010). Companies that choose to adopt coupled innovation as a critical open innovation process combine both inbound and outbound open innovation processes in order to co-operate strategically with other companies. A recent coupled innovative example is the new BMW car control mechanism – iDrive; a feature of the latest 7-series model, which was introduced in close co-operation with different industries.

A reciprocal relationship of knowledge is necessary to co-operate successfully with other industries. Therefore, a coupling of the inside-out and outside-in open innovation processes is fundamental for success. Coupling open innovation can be a strategic option in, for example, alliances with shared intellectual property. It has been suggested that firms adopt “coupled innovation process” by combining the “outside-in process” with “inside-out process”. In so doing, they jointly develop and commercialise innovation. However, this may come at the cost of having to share rewards (Enkel et al., 2009).

Coupled OI is a type of co-innovation with complementary partners through structured co-operation that often involves a set of inter-firm relationships and the recombining of external knowledge with existing knowledge (Mazzola et al., 2012; Schumpeter, 1934). Companies adopting coupled innovation gain ideas and knowledge that are not used by focal companies, but still have economic value in the marketplace. This approach allows the company to co-develop knowledge with another independent company (Chesbrough and Garman, 2009; Nieto and Santamaría, 2007).

However, Chesbrough (2003b) argues that firms sometimes relinquish their intellectual property opportunities by over-protecting the market. In such cases, co-patents become a feasible approach. Protective myopia may also impinge on opportunities to trade knowledge with suppliers, users, and rivals. When a firm lacks the necessary market knowledge or other complementary resources to exploit technologies fully, other firms' exploiting technologies help the firm to take full advantage of unseen intellectual property assets. Hence, organisations can exploit their prevailing ideas and knowledge with other firms (Chesbrough and Garman, 2009).

R&D inter-organisational collaborations help firms to scan their environment for new windows of opportunity and technologies (Faems et al., 2005; Ebersberger et al., 2012). Relationships between R&D inter-firm collaborations and the outcome of corporate innovation have been investigated by a significant number of scholars (Nieto and Santamaria, 2007; Vega-Jurado et al., 2009; Faems et al., 2010; Neyens et al., 2010). Collaborative patents (Co-Patents) are key indicators of coupled OI practices since they reflect a fraction of inter-firm collaborative relationships (Lin et al., 2012). Indeed, the co-patenting process demands collaboration during the course of the entire innovation process including, exploration and exploitation through to the utilisation of new technology in the marketplace. The development of co-patenting helps firms to improve both their innovativeness and their financial performance as this helps to reduce the costs and the lead times associated with new patent development. This can enhance the quality of technology usability and the market adaptability of innovation outputs (Mazzola et al., 2012).

Although R&D inter-organisational collaborations might lead to an escalation of financial outcomes, they may also introduce rationale risks as a result of opportunistic behaviours and increase the coordination costs required to implement monitoring mechanisms (Belderbos et al., 2010; Faems et al., 2010). Moreover, based on the sixty-eight studies of R&D intensive firms by Belderbos et al. (2010) suggest that the potential advantages of R&D inter-organisational collaboration such as complementary knowledge, sharing technological costs and risks appear not to reward the potential disadvantages. In contrast, both 'Inbound open innovation' and 'Coupled open Innovation' processes denote that a company needs to share rewards with its collaborative associates.

Although collaboration might increase the probability of producing new ideas and knowledge to increase innovation performance, it may also limit the ability of firms to attach value to such

activities (Ring and Van de Ven, 1994). Open innovation systems are cited more frequently as notable special mechanisms of organising innovation, and there is an increasing number of empirical studies which demonstrate a positive link between the use of external relationships and the innovation performance of the firm, regardless of the industry setting or size (Beckeman et al., 2013; Purcarea et al., 2013; Grunam et al., 2012). The idea of OI originated from the observation that ‘by enlarging your research organisation’ you may be able to tap into a much larger pool of ideas and find ideas faster than if you limit the potential of yourself by applying traditional closed innovation model (Torkelli et al., 2009:178).

However, there is a downside to implementing open innovation which means that sharing knowledge with others might increase the risk of reducing the potential distinctiveness of innovations that are developed in the market (Ferto et al., 2016). Therefore, open innovation does not guarantee success, and several researchers have studied the conditions of firms that implement open innovation systems and have concluded such conditions are more likely to lead to success than failure ((Lichtenthaler, 2011; Reed et al., 2012; Huizingh, 2011; Rese and Baier, 2011).

Past studies have highlighted the significant role of a firm’s absorptive capacity and the existence of complementary assets as important prerequisites for the success of open innovation (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Teece et al., 1997; Zahra and George, 2002; Escribano et al., 2009; Tsai, 2001). OI systems in their purest form require all information resources to be shared amongst all participants (Baldwin and von Hippel, 2011). Therefore, in such situations, the difference in innovation is significantly determined by the firm’s capacity to acquire and integrate and/or combine accessible information (Abrosini and Bowman, 2009; Eisenhardt and Martin, 2000).

Despite an increased interest in OI in scientific research, most previous studies have looked at large scale technology-based companies (Lee et al., 2010; Vrande et al., 2009). There are many reasons why OI has been ignored in the context of SMEs. Firstly, open innovation was typically studied mainly in big firms. On the other hand, SMEs are less able to access external resources. Also, SMEs have fewer technological assets to exchange than larger firms (Narula, 2004). However, few studies have confirmed that OI exists in SMEs, which focus on very specific markets, such as open-source software and tabletop role-playing games (Lecocq and Demil, 2006).

Secondly, a non-internal means of innovation has been used by SMEs to a greater degree than in bigger firms. In other words, SMEs consider alliances or networks to encompass their technological competencies (Edwards et al., 2005). Finally, SMEs regard external sources as a means of getting access to marketing and sales channels as the next phase of their innovation management (Lee et al., 2010).

The term ‘open innovation’ thrived in the relatively small cohort of open innovation practitioners. OI practice is mostly active in high-tech industries. In other words, the current literature on open innovation mainly deals with R&D incentives in large firms (OECD, 2008). The importance of OI was firstly identified by Drucker (1988) and Christensen (1997) in the context of corporate success, profitability, and sustainability. However, Chesbrough (2003) first suggested OI as a new paradigm for the management of innovation. OI was understood as ‘the use of purposive inflows and outflows of knowledge to accelerate internal innovation and to enlarge markets for the external use of innovation (Chesbrough et al., 2006). Therefore, OI comprises of both outside-in and inside-out movements of technologies and ideas; these are similarly denoted as ‘technology acquisition’ and ‘technology exploitation’ (Lichtenthaler, 2008).

2.3.4. Types of Open Innovation

In today’s world, modern businesses grow and succeed for a myriad of various reasons. Some businesses are well known for the products or services they offer to customers, and others for their brand. But one thing is common to all established organisations, they all embrace innovation. In the modern business world, ‘adapt or die’ is a statement that is commonly used to determine business success. In competitive markets, innovation is considered a major component of a firm’s long-term business success (Baker and Sinkula, 2012; Darroch and McNaughton, 2002; YuSheng and Ibrahim, 2020).

Table 2-3: A Taxonomy of Innovations

Product Innovation	Process Innovation
In goods	Technological
In services	Organisational

Source: Meeus and Edquist (2006)

Innovation refers to the development of a new or existing product. On the other hand, process innovation is concerned with creating, implementing, or improving methods of production (Handoko et al., 2014; Oke et al., 2007; Ueasangkomsate and Jangkot, 2019). Some firms specialise in product innovation, for example, Apple Inc, others are more into process innovation, for example, Dell (Johnson et al., 2011). The importance of product and process innovation typically alters as firms evolve over a period. Product innovation is usually dominant at the initial stages of the organisation (Johnson et al., 2011).

2.3.4.1. Product Innovation

Product innovation refers to the introduction of a significantly upgraded product or service with respect to its features, performance, and quality (Ferrari and Rocca, 2010; Atalay et al., 2011). The term ‘product’ covers both goods and services (Ferrari and Rocca, 2010). Product innovation can use new knowledge or technologies or can be based on new uses or the combination of existing knowledge or technologies. Product innovation can be implemented through changing product designs and improving quality to satisfy the needs of consumers (Bhaskaran, 2006; Yoshioka-Kobayashi et al., 2020). Through product innovation, firms can reduce the cost of a product. The aim of cost reduction is to differentiate a product from other products by competing on price or to ensure that the product remains price competitive. In addition, firms are involved in product innovation to create product improvements and line extensions, which provide consumers with improvements to original products, such as extra benefits or improved functionality.

Teece (2007) claimed that innovation can lead to and sustain a firm’s profitability. There is extensive literature on the role of management practices in enhancing innovation efforts (Bougrain and Haudeville, 2002; Laursen and Foss, 2003). However, Theyel’s (2013) study focused on the specific influence of open innovation practices on product and process innovation. The practice of open innovation leads to improved product innovation performance. Recent studies showed that firms that exploit effective relationships with their external partners in relation to their product innovations are generally more innovative (Kang and Kang, 2009; Laursen and Salter, 2006; Love et al., 2011). Therefore, it is obvious that relationships with external partners play a major role in effective product innovation.

However, some studies explained that in comparison to other manufacturing industries, the food industry does not substantially facilitate product or technology innovation activities

(Beckeman and Skjöldebrand, 2007; Hullova et al., 2019). Recent studies claimed that the food industry has been process-innovation oriented (Batterink et al., 2006; Triguero et al., 2013).

2.3.4.2. *Process Innovation*

Process innovation means the application of new technology and methods for doing something that guides firms to remain competitive. Process innovation involves changes in the way in which products and services are created and delivered (Oke et al., 2007). Similarly, Expósito and Sanchis-Llopis (2019) explained that process innovation is the introduction of new and enhanced methods of products or service delivery. In this type of innovation, the major focus is to improve effectivity and efficiency by reducing costs and time in production and organisational processes (Raymond and St-Pierre, 2010). In this way, firms become more competitive in the markets.

This type of innovation can be narrowly viewed as new changes in the manufacturing process. A lot of changes occur in the systems, reengineering activities also happen for the development of new products. Process innovation is sometimes referred to as administrative innovation, technical innovation, organisational innovation, management innovation as well as business system innovation because of all these diverse activities are involved in this innovation process (Rawley et al., 2011).

Process innovation aims to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of firms; hence, it is generally characterised by an internal organisational focus (Damanpour et al., 2009). Piening and Salge (2015) believed that process innovation is the intermediate outcome that is applied to attain higher level performance outcomes. Crossan and Apaydin (2010) believed that process innovations are incremental in nature. Process innovations add value to customers, employees, business partners, and to the actual organisation itself. Moreover, they can generate significant gains in product quality and level of service (Baer and Frese, 2003; Klomp and Van Leeuwen, 2001; Piening and Salge, 2015).

A plethora of research studies have been conducted on the food sector with a particular focus on the relationships between types of innovation (Menrad, 2004; Brewin et al., 2009; Capitanio et al., 2010). Successful firms utilise a combination of product, process, and market innovations for innovativeness. However, very few studies have been conducted into types of innovation in food sector SMEs (Beregheh et al., 2012). Moreover, no study has been conducted to identify

the types of innovation that UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs implement for innovativeness.

2.4. Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs)

2.4.1. Introduction to Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises

SMEs are recognised as the dominant vector of economic progress. According to World Bank (2019), SMEs play a significant role in most economies, as they account for a majority of businesses worldwide. SMEs represent 90% of the total businesses and account for the employment of more than 50% all over the world (The World Bank, 2019). In addition, 600 million jobs will be needed by 2030 to employ the ever-growing global workforce. This makes SMEs the top priority for many governments around the world.

SMEs have a certain number of employees. According to the UK government definition, a business with fewer than 250 employees and less than 50 million euros of annual turnover is categorised as an SME. According to Business Statistics (2021), there are 5.6 million SMEs across the UK, comprising 99% of the total number of UK businesses. The statistics also show that just over one in three UK businesses are based in London and the Southeast.

Table 2-4: SMEs Categorisations

SMEs Category	Employment	Annual Turnover (Euro)
Micro	0-9	2 million
Small	10-49	10 million
Medium	50-249	50 million

Source: EU (2020)

The successful activities of SMEs determine a country's economic development. These kinds of businesses are considered the drivers of economic recovery globally (Arshed et al., 2016; Beynon et al., 2016). SMEs provide new jobs, contribute to the markets, and enhance innovation (Beck et al., 2005; Kersten et al., 2017; Savlovski and Robu 2011; The World Bank, 2021). However, SMEs encounter a lot of business challenges in the markets which are critically discussed in the next section.

2.4.2. Roles of Small and Medium-Sized Firms for Facilitating Innovation

Innovation and technological modification are the essential sources of productivity growth, international competitiveness, and proliferated living standards. In past years, these areas have become the focal points of growing attention due to relentless competition from rapidly emerging knowledge-based economies (Talwar and Hancock, 2010). In particular, research and policy have begun to focus on SMEs as a fundamental source and driver of new product developments, innovation and new technologies (Wynarczyk and Piperopoulos, 2013). According to the report from the European Commission (2015/16), just under 23 million SMEs generated €3.9 trillion in value added and employed around 90 million people. Thus, innovative SMEs play a significant role in national and regional economic development and international competitiveness.

However, studies have demonstrated that only a small population of SMEs are responsible for most of the positive effects regarding innovation, new product development, R&D, exporting, creating employability and wealth creation (Nesta, 2009; Wynarczyk and Thwaites, 2000). Amongst such innovative firms, only a small number of SMEs have the desire, capacity, and opportunity to successfully pursue growth, expansion and diversification beyond their local marketplace. In the current knowledge-based environment, fledging SMEs in particular are inhibited by both internal and external structural barriers such as smallness, management capabilities, skilled workers, financial stability and access to external knowledge.

A report published by NESTA (2009) shows that only 6% of SMEs with high growth rates created half of the new jobs in existing businesses between 2002 and 2008, and innovation has been involved in competitiveness and the growth of these businesses. The rationale for OI adaptation in practice by SMEs varies amongst large and multinational firms. This is due to the size of the firms, as well as the extent of economic and financial gains and inter-firm relationships.

On the other hand, investment in research and development is considered the primary driver of innovation and increased productivity. The contribution of R&D to company growth and economic development has been recognised by many scholars in the past (Freeman, 1974). In particular, Cohen and Levinthal (1990) regarded investment in internal R&D as a significant asset in evaluating and utilising external knowledge and technology.

However, it has been argued that British businesses are not research-intensive in comparison with other advanced countries all over the world (Wynarczyk, 2013). The previous years' records showed that investment in R&D and patenting has been relatively low. R&D, research and employment are mostly concentrated in a limited range of industrial sectors in UK businesses.

A small portion of large firms is located in more affluent areas such as in the south-east. It has been estimated that over 80% of total R&D expenditure is conducted by the one hundred most active firms (Wynarczyk, 2013). Conversely, independently owned SMEs account for only 3% of total R&D expenditure in UK business. These are assumed to be amongst the most focal causes of the productivity gap that exists between the UK and other comparable economies (Sainsbury, 2007; European Commission, 2009).

The potential issues of SMEs can be identified and solved. The main challenge for business support intermediaries and policymakers with the recent economic and financial crisis is to recognise and support those factors which are capable of “making a difference” to promote firms with innovation and growth potential. It has been claimed that open innovation significantly helps SMEs to eradicate many boundaries such as location, technology and both internal financial and human resources. OI practice offers a different strategy through which growth-oriented SMEs can access inter-firm resources at low cost. It stands in the way of developing new products and entering into new markets (Chesbrough, 2003).

Initial research relating to open innovation primarily focuses on large technological organisations. Moreover, it disregards the role and the impact of national and regional innovation performance and governmental policies. Moreover, these research studies tend to be mostly qualitative in nature.

However, there has been a clear change in the nature of industry research. In recent research studies, scholars consider the size and the location of the firms (Laursen and Salter, 2006; Lee et al., 2010; Lichtenthaler and Ernst, 2009; Van de Vrande et al., 2009). Through an extensive review of the literature published to date, many challenges facing SMEs have been documented along with the positive effects of implementing OI in SMEs. One of the significant features of OI is industry-university collaboration.

In knowledge-based economies, universities, in general, are considered as a hub of fundamental discoveries, R&D and knowledge of the type needed by businesses to drive innovation (Huggins et al., 2008). Therefore, it has been argued that firms must work with universities to

discover new ideas and translate these into new product development or service development processes.

Firms must also commercialise these ideas through appropriate joint ventures (Lambert, 2003). Policymakers must firstly identify the importance of SME collaboration within the context of open innovation. In recent years, various policy initiatives and schemes have been introduced including knowledge transfer partnerships, university challenge funds, science enterprise challenges, Higher Education Innovation Funds, and the pledge of a £200m investment in the network of Catapult centres to enhance collaboration and guide businesses to commercialise British research. It helps to connect the dots between universities and businesses. Thus, collaboration between industry and universities is accentuated and so-called “third stream governmental funding” has generated a noticeable cultural change in universities who now seek to build their capacity. Hence, collaboration of this type helps to transfer knowledge and technology to the business community.

However, it has been argued that SMEs show a lack of engagement in collaboration (Lambert, 2003; Wilson, 2012). Hence, collaboration between industry and universities encounters significant barriers. This is due to variances in culture and incentive systems. Generally, universities create new knowledge and technologies as their prime purpose for research and education. Moreover, universities are increasingly proactive about commercialising their intellectual property (IP) through spin-out activity (Wynarczyk et al., 2012).

On the other hand, SMEs focus on profit by transferring new knowledge and technologies into product and service development to take to market (Bruneel et al., 2010; Fontana et al., 2006).

The UK government prioritises investment in business R&D in their agenda. Several schemes under the technology strategy board’s remit have been initiated and executed by the government to encourage greater investment in R&D and collaboration (open innovation) between SMEs and Higher Education Institutions (Department for Business, Innovation and Skills, 2011). However, small and medium-sized firms are relatively unskilled when it comes to investing in R&D. Moreover, as stated in the above paragraph, independently owned SMEs account for only 3% of total R&D expenditure in UK businesses (Whnarczyk et al., 2012). This shows the significance of SMEs in the UK market.

2.4.3. Applicability of Open Innovation for Overcoming the Challenges Faced by SMEs

SMEs are an essential part of most thriving economies worldwide. These enterprises are the focus of most business and management research (Amoros et al., 2013; Dobbs and Hamilton, 2007; Lussier and Halabi, 2014). SMEs are significant contributors to employability and the critical drivers for innovation (Franco and Haase, 2010; Unger et al., 2011). Despite the significant importance of SMEs in the global economy, SMEs encounter many challenges in the markets. The most common of these challenges include lack of resources, shortage of skilled labour, lack of networks, and inability to compete against bigger organisations (Gassman et al., 2010; Saguy, 2011; Depken and Zeman, 2017).

However, these challenges can be mitigated by collaborating and networking with external partners. Due to a lack of resources and lack of R&D, SMEs do not have access to market information. However, this issue can be overcome by collaborating with suppliers as they provide updated market information (Brunswicker and Vanhaverbeke, 2014).

In today's modern economy, businesses, particularly SMEs, need to adapt as quickly as possible to remain competitive (Kraus et al., 2020). Wynarczyk (2013) postulated that implementing new ideas into product development is critical to be unique and competitive in the modern marketplace. Therefore, practising OI strategies by establishing cooperation with other external firms can assist SMEs to overcome many business challenges. Santore et al. (2018) demonstrated that SMEs prefer partnerships with customers and suppliers for effective innovativeness in their product and process development. Their study also indicated that the innovativeness of SMEs increases when they collaborate with those external bodies. Moreover, Lee et al. (2010) indicated that networking supports SMEs in engaging in effective OI activities.

The relevance of OI in SMEs for mitigating business challenges is immense. Traditionally, SMEs are less bureaucratic and more risk taking for innovativeness than large businesses. SMEs innovate faster because of their flexibility and agility in product development (Hossain, 2015). The implementation of an OI strategy for SMEs can be seen as a possible way to adapt and thrive in a challenging market. Almeida (2021) stated that SMEs can mitigate their resource constraints by using external resources to develop their products and services. In this way, they can take advantage of market opportunities.

In the competitive market, SMEs are required to be innovative to overcome their business challenges by demonstrating technological sophistication (Dibrell et al., 2008; Baynon et al., 2018). The importance of open innovation and SMEs' innovativeness are explained below.

2.4.4. The Stimuli of Open Innovation in SMEs

SMEs are considered a vital source of innovation management (Acs and Audretsch, 1987). Small firms can apply radical change innovation, which is new to the world of innovation. OI is an alternative strategic approach for SMEs that have research and development outsourcing capabilities.

Many public and governmental policies are not suitable for SMEs as their innovation models and activities are dissimilar to larger organisations (Burnswicker and Vanhaverbeke 2015). In general, SMEs are more flexible and less formalised in nature. The challenges discussed above are due to the small size of firms. However, their size makes them more accessible for management bodies to make quick decisions and implement necessary changes. However, SMEs have limited financial resources to carry out internal research and development (Bessant, 1999 and Lee et al., 2010). Thus, such firms cannot cover all the necessary innovative strategies, which are considered one of the most significant challenges for sustainability.

One of the primary objectives of this research is to investigate South Asian wholesale food SMEs in the UK market. Brown and Mason's (2014) study of UK technology-based SMEs identified that policymakers struggle to understand SMEs. Conversely, Csath (2012) argued that applying OI is very crucial for SMEs in order to grow sustainably in the competitive market. Therefore, management bodies require training to develop their creativity, criticism, self-disciplined and cooperation.

Hemert et al. (2013) assert that various networking approaches for SMEs might not be understood by policymakers. Bevis and Kamp (2012) believe that innovation support systems from government and public policymakers are critical for small firms in terms of creating OI policy. Furthermore, McAdam et al. (2014) claimed that policymakers should make efforts to include SMEs in networking support programmes to encourage and build networks. Many countries provide financial support to local universities and large companies engaged in R&D to develop open innovation (Roper and Hewitt Dundas, 2013).

Therefore, the existing policy should be improved and take on a more linear approach to accelerate OI. Large organisations are more open to adopting an OI strategy, but SMEs have a higher concentration of OI than more prominent corporations (Spithoven et al., 2013).

2.4.5. Significance of Open Innovation to SMEs

OI is a broad concept that involves a variety of innovation related practices and processes in firms (Spithoven et al., 2013). Prior studies on innovation suggest that food firms were engaged in various types of innovations (Lefebvre et al., 2015). Menrad (2004) conducted a survey on small food SMEs, which found that two-thirds of firms were engaged with both product and process innovations. On the other hand, Baregheh et al. (2012) stated that food SMEs innovate, not just in terms of products and processes, but also in terms of marketing and business strategies. It can be argued that it is not reasonable to expect all food SMEs to adopt the same innovative approach. Tripl (2011) highlighted that the different forms of innovation in which Viennese Food firms are engaged with are incremental in nature. On the other hand, Beckeman et al. (2013) found that few Swedish food firms have demonstrated radical innovation. Spanish food SMEs concentrate on product-oriented innovations towards incremental innovations (Martinez and Briz, 2000).

The use of inter-organisational relationships for innovation is prevalent in many industries, such as pharmaceutical, chemical and IT industries, and the food industry is no exception (Bianchi et al., 2011; Berchicci, 2013 and Parida et al., 2011). Although OI is not new to large technology-based companies, some recent studies of food SMEs have demonstrated that they often apply OI (Fortuin and Omta, 2009; Sarkar and Costa, 2008; Knudsen, 2007). According to Beckeman et al. (2013), food firms develop inter-organisational relationships for innovation purposes with suppliers in particular, and the importance of relationships with customers has been explored in other literature (Menrad, 2004). OI helps firms to push both owners and employees to evolve. Innovation is a crucial element for all types of business success.

Recent changes in food demand, supply chain management, and competitiveness have accentuated the importance of innovation in the food industry. Martinez and Briz (2000) suggest the food industry has always been considered as a mature and slow-moving industry in term of growth. Christensen et al. (1996) added that the food industry has been very conservative in terms of its research intensity and applying innovation to the marketplace.

According to Lienhardt (2004), the food sector has traditionally focused on reducing production costs with no consideration of customer demand. However, based on the supply-based and demand-based approaches, a ‘chain reversal’ process has recently altered the whole perception of the food industry. Consumers now pre-order direct from producers (Boland, 2008; Bigliardi and Galati, 2013b).

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Bigliardi and Galati 2016.

Table 2-5: The Impact of open innovation in other industries on food industry

Source: Bigliardi, and Galati (2016)

The above figure illustrates how OI in other industries has a considerable impact on food sectors. Therefore, OI is essential for the food industry (Omta and Folstar, 2005). An OI strategy enhances competitiveness and satisfies fast-changing customer needs. However, Bercovitz and Feldman (2007) and Wallin and von Krogh (2010) argue that the implications of the OI paradigm are felt keenly in terms of management practices.

OI pushes employees and managers to think ‘outside of the box’, to not only fulfil the requirements of their job but to take position themselves at the next level (Carmichael, 2014). In addition, OI motivates new customers to purchase more goods and services and leads to repeat business and loyalty. Furthermore, innovation can help companies to take service to the next level. Usually, an organisation continually serves customers in the same way, and this affects business turnover growth. This does not attract new customers. What innovation does for the company is to reinvent new goods and services to reach more customers. The ultimate aim of business will be growth and revenue, as well as customer satisfaction and profit-making (Carmichael, 2014). OI strategies in the UK based food SMEs have been overlooked in recent literature. Therefore, the author seeks to fill this gap through the development of this study.

Although OI is not completely understood, it has potential for small and medium-sized firms (Lee et al., 2009). Conversely, Oahey (2013) criticised the OI strategy, which was developed by Chesbrough. He argued that OI in R&D is a costly and lengthy process. Therefore, it is considered a risky process. However, some theorists have criticised Oahey’s argument and believe that SMEs are more capable of applying OI than large organisations (Spithoven et al., 2013).

On the other hand, Lichtenthaler (2008) argued that most SMEs, globally still value closed innovation over OI. In contrast, Torok and Toth (2013) highlighted some of the benefits of OI for food SMEs. They found that firms which provide ideas to external parties are more productive than non-providers. In addition, the degree of novelty in a new product is lower for SMEs which deal with fixed with suppliers (Torok and Toth, 2013). Xiaobao et al. (2013) and Van de Vrande et al. (2009) stated that SMEs effectively use OI strategies in their business models. Limited resources, the complexity of the scientific field and access to up-to-date knowledge are amongst the challenges that SMEs encounter in the pursuit of innovation (Abouzeedan et al., 2013). OI is one way that SMEs can overcome these challenges to access external knowledge and broaden their technical competencies. SMEs, in this sense, apply OI extensively (Pullen et al., 2012).

Recent academic research has highlighted the benefits of OI for SMEs. Gassmann et al. (2010) claim that OI is a promising means for SMEs to overcome barriers and ultimately increase their profitability. OI allows SMEs to gain strategic advantages which are not feasible in the context of closed innovation (Colombo et al., 2013). Furthermore, OI might offer great benefits for SMEs to compensate for sized related issues (Petersen, 2000). There are some benefits of

utilising open innovation in food SMEs. Companies adopt OI in the food sector to lower costs when conducting R&D. It is accepted that shared technology, in the long run, proves cheaper if they turn out to be efficient and relevant to the operation. In addition, there would be high production because of the improved and cost-effective methods being applied by the company (Avermaete et al., 2002). This represents a major reimbursement for a company that is involved in OI because total profit margins will improve, and savings can be spent on research. Furthermore, the implementation of OI is considered a potential way to distribute products to the market that have been produced because of the application of innovative techniques. Firms can earn the loyalty of customers through the practical implementation of open innovation strategies. Consequently, reputation can be built up incrementally. The complexity of scientific fields demands the integration of knowledge from various disciplines for successful innovation. However, solely building useful knowledge and technologies can take years and requires an enormous amount of R&D investment (Wynarczyk, 2013). SMEs have limited financial resources and limited internal R&D capacity. Hence, they should apply an OI approach to ensure that they can access the valuable information and technologies produced by internal sources (Sag et al., 2016).

SMEs which operate in developing countries cannot fail as a consequence of the scarcity of resources. However, Sag et al. (2016) argue that environmental changes increase the cost and the risk of innovation. Hemert et al. (2013) commented that innovative SMEs prefer to network with other enterprises or institutions to collaborate and adopt OI for product development or commercialisation. Small firms who lack the capabilities to manage the innovation process by themselves can co-operate with other firms (Edwards et al., 2005). Furthermore, less bureaucracy, a willingness to take risks, and the ability to react quickly can encourage SMEs to adopt OI (Parida et al., 2012). Although there are numerous benefits to implementing OI in food SMEs, many encounter challenges in adopting such strategies.

2.5. Open Innovation through Utilisation of Internal Resources

The effective utilisation of internal resources can lead to open and collaborative innovation, which can be critical to achieving competitiveness in the market (Rumelt, 1984; Liao et al., 2009; Price et al., 2013). Many studies suggest that firms involved in developing products and services tend to compete successfully through the development of new products and processes

(Allocca and Kessler, 2006; Gudmunson et al., 2003; Price et al., 2013). Innovation is of utmost importance for sustainable value creation for many organisations. Innovation enables an organisation to sustain in the markets because it raises the productivity of both capital and labour. Innovative ideas come from both internal and external bodies. Firms always look to access initial ideas from various sources. The amount of knowledge from external partners to an organisation is far more extensive than an organisation's internal knowledge (Kogut, 2000; Felin and Zenger, 2020).

However, some problems may arise from being too open to innovation. In the open innovation funnel, firms remain open to external bodies for ideas and knowledge from various sources. The more open the innovation funnel is, the better it is for the organisations, as discussed in detail in earlier paragraphs. However, the guidance to be open does not feature any form of firm-specificity about what firms should look for in the innovation process (Felin and Zenger, 2020). Moreover, external ideas do not come in a pre-packaged form. The core of being open to innovation is not just an easy choice to be open to outside ideas and knowledge, but to acknowledge and then have sound guidance on what to look for within the market surroundings. Felin and Zenger (2014) suggested that firms should often conduct internal analysis to assess whether or not the resources or knowledge they have leads to innovation.

2.5.1. Resource-Based View (RBV)

RBV is the most popular framework in strategic management research (Barney et al., 2001; Varandarajan, 2020; Pereira and Bamel, 2021). RBV was not the first or the only framework for firms for becoming effective or achieving greater profitability or attaining competitive advantages. However, RBV suggested practical options to firms for gaining competitive advantages in the marketplace (David-West et al., 2018; Kor et al., 2016; Upadhyay et al., 2020). RBV theorizes that firms compete based on resources that are valuable, rare, hard to imitate and non-substitutable for other resources (Barney, 1991). A firm's resources, which include the assets, capabilities, organisational processes, information and knowledge it controls, allow the firm to conceive of and implement strategies that develop its efficiency and effectiveness (Daft, 1983).

The notion of RBV is that firms that have resource heterogeneity and the competence to utilise those resources innovatively can attain competitive advantages over their counterparts (Collis and Montgomery, 1995; Safari and Saleh, 2020). The RBV framework not only analyses firms'

competitive positioning but effectively helps them elevate the strategic advantage of their resources to build competitive advantages (Pereira and Bamel, 2021). Accessing and transferring information from one business to another (i.e., through open collaborative innovation) is how a corporation's resource base is used to gain a competitive advantage. Das and Teng (2000) underlined this issue, stating that the overarching argument for engaging in a strategic alliance (in the RBV) is clear. When important resources cannot be economically gained through exchanges or mergers/acquisitions, then it is desirable to pool, share, or exchange them with other enterprises.

However, there are some limitations to RBV theory. Alchian and Demsetz (1972) argued that efficient production with heterogenous resources is not the result of having better resources, but rather knowing and acknowledging the productive performance of those resources. This gave birth to the idea of knowledge-based view (KBV) theory. Curado and Bontis's (2006) study postulated that knowledge is one of the key strategic resources of firms that determine its long-term performance in the markets.

2.5.2. Knowledge-Based View (KBV)

The KBV posits that knowledge is the most important strategic resource of a firm (Grant, 1996). With knowledge, firms become more efficient and effective; thus, they produce low-cost products and services. Considering knowledge as the primary competitive resource or asset has significant consequences for collaborative innovation analysis. Firms should integrate knowledge in a knowledge-based approach because knowledge sharing through the market mechanism is an expensive process.

The KBV is gaining popularity as a result of rapid movements towards knowledge-based economies. The primary goal of KBV for a firm is to utilise its existing knowledge to produce products and services (Grant, 1996). Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995) believed that knowledge and skills provide firms with a competitive advantage because through knowledge and skills firms can effectively innovate new products/services or improve existing products/services. Similarly, Leonard's (1998) study related KBV to innovation and proposed that successful organisations are those which build and manage knowledge effectively. The KBV developed from RBV, and its focus is on the intangible (knowledge) resources of firms. Therefore, knowledge is the most important strategic resource. The RBV argued that a firm drives its competitiveness through internal resources (Barney, 1991). KBV, as a theory, complements

this assumption by indicating that heterogeneous resources help firms gain a sustainable competitive advantage.

Successful innovation requires knowledge integration within the innovation environment. The collaborative approach is ideal for exchanging and combining different types of knowledge to foster innovation (Moller and Rajala, 2007). In today's markets, where products and technologies are in constant upgrade, the dynamism of knowledge for innovation, and hence competitiveness, is irreplaceable (Barney, 1991; Gupta and Barua, 2016). Frenz and Letto Gillies (2009) argued that knowledge is difficult to measure but it is easier to identify, capture, and access different sources of knowledge. The importance of knowledge-based capabilities in the innovation process for long-term competitiveness is emphasised in the past literature (Andreeva and Kianto, 2011; Peris-Ortiz et al., 2019; Tzokas and Saren, 2004).

In summary, it can be said that in the KBV theory, knowledge is considered strategically significant for any organisation as it facilitates innovation through the understanding of the existing knowledge that a firm possesses. In addition, through collaborative knowledge sharing, firms can develop better strategies, innovate new products and services, or improve existing products and services, which will give organisations a competitive advantage. Open collaborative innovation, like transaction cost economics, occupies a middle ground between hierarchy and market. By reducing opportunism, trust between working parties helps address the disclosure challenge. Furthermore, while corporations (i.e., hierarchies) are normally more efficient in this area, collaborative innovation can build specific routines that allow knowledge integration and the transmission of tacit knowledge. Nonetheless, as the variety and diversity of information grows, collaborative innovation may outperform the hierarchical firm (Grant, 2002).

2.6. UK Food Industry: A Contextual Review

2.6.1. UK Food Wholesale Industry

Food is important for our lives; it is considered a fundamental need and therefore is important for every nation. The food industry is not entirely one sector. It is a collection of many types, such as agricultural, food processing, packaging, distribution, retail, and catering sectors. The UK food industry is considered the largest manufacturing sector within the UK; it contributes £29 billion to the UK economy which is more than any other sector (Food and Drink

Federation, 2020). According to a Food and Drink Federation (2020) report, the UK food industry raised the gross value added by 2.3% in 2019 compared to 2018. According to this report (Food and Drink Federation, 2020), the industry had a total turnover of £104 billion in 2019. The food and drink industry directly employs almost half a million people across the UK. This industry represents 20% of the total manufacturing sector in the UK.

However, this industry is facing a decade of seismic shifts. According to the Food and Drink Federation (2020) report, this industry will be pushed and pulled in various directions by diverse forces due to rising demand of consumers, increasing product innovation, and the advancement of new technology. Wholesalers will face more challenges from the emergence of intense competition, rapid advancement in new technologies as well as a major shift in how customers want to interact and transact. Therefore, innovation in the food sector is a must to cope with these rapid changes in the markets.

2.6.2. UK-Based South Asian Food Wholesale SMEs and their Product Lines

The UK's leading Asian food wholesale suppliers built a long-standing reputation in the UK markets. They sell the finest authentic Asian meals and ingredients for the British people. These food wholesalers supply authentic South Asian curry spices, halal meats, ghee, rice, Asian-grown vegetables, Asian snacks, frozen fish, and many more items (Eurofoods, 2021; Surya, 2021). They supply to restaurants, takeaways, catering sectors, hospitality sector, and retailers throughout the UK. However, they face a lot of challenges as competition is ever-growing in the UK market. Therefore, attention needs to be paid on how these challenges can be tackled by being more competitive and by implementing open innovation strategies.

2.6.2.1. South Asian Cuisine

South Asia is a subregion of Asia; it includes the countries of Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Afghanistan, and Maldives (Britannica, 2021; Illinois Library, 2021). The terms Indian subcontinent and South Asia are often used synonymously. However, the term Indian subcontinent is now used more restrictively to refer to Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan (Britannica, 2021).

In human history, cooking is the oldest activity undertaken by people. South Asian cuisine is a combination of many cuisines popular in the Indian subcontinent. This food was greatly

influenced by culture and religion. This type of food is highly flavoured and popular all around the world. This type of food is also called Asian food in a broader sense. South Asian cuisines gained popularity in the UK in the 1980s and continue to be popular. The history of South Asian cuisine in the UK reflects the changes in global migration patterns as well as changes in attitudes towards migrants in the UK.

According to Manchester Museum (2020), to date, there are more than 9000 Indian restaurants in the UK. They are mostly run by Bangladeshi employees. British supermarkets sell South Asian meals and ingredients in huge quantities. These meals and ingredients are not just for people born in the UK but also for migrants who are settled in the UK. According to Lincoln International (2021), 1.5 million South Asian people live in the UK, which raises the demand for South Asian foods. There are many Asian food wholesalers all around the UK, including micro and small and medium-sized firms. Asian food contributes £4 billion to the British economy annually. Therefore, it is clear that Asian food plays a significant role in the British economy.

2.6.3. Open Innovation in the Food Industry

To date, innovation is increasingly acknowledged as one of the key factors behind organisational success. Innovation has also become of particular interest to the food industry, even though the extensive literature on this industry means it is usually considered as a sector defined by low research intensity (Christensen et al., 1996; Martinez and Briz, 2000). On the other hand, the food industry is considered one of the biggest manufacturing sectors within the European Union (EU) in terms of its contribution to both economic results and employment (Avermaete et al., 2002; Menrad, 2004; Traill and Meulenber, 2002).

A benchmark report on competitiveness by the European Confederation of the food and drink industry (CIAA) illustrates that innovative potential should be enhanced if they are willing to remain competitive in the market in future (CIAA, 2008). The type of innovation introduced recently in the food industry has embraced scientific and technical approaches to food processing. Some studies illustrate that new food products are more successful than incremental innovations such as line extensions and me-too products that generate only short-term gains and low margin benefits (Knox et al., 2001; Van Trijp and Meulenber, 1996).

The extant literature traditionally considers the food industry as a mature and slow-moving sector with low research intensity. Thus, the industry is very conservative regarding the

introduction of innovation to the market (Christensen et al., 1996; Martinez and Briz, 2000). The food industry links with numerous sectors in the value chain such as the agricultural, retail, pharmaceutical industries as well as the chemical and packaging industries (Brasilia and Fanfani, 2006).

From a historical perspective, the food sector is associated with the low-tech processing of agricultural products. R&D is of secondary importance to the food industry compared to other industries, e.g., the chemical industry or the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) industry (Samadi, 2014). However, due to the necessity of exploiting profits, the food industry is increasingly implementing modern technologies in their business models.

Moreover, recent significant changes both in the nature of food demand and supply chain organisations and competitiveness in the market have increased awareness of innovation as a corporate activity that is fundamental to the overall profitability of the industry (Costa and Jongen, 2006). In particular, the demand for food is evolving food and drink into a mass customisation market (Boland, 2008). Therefore, food consumers in need of more products are closely tailored to individual needs and preferences (Costa et al., 2001; Costa et al., 2007). This new trend in 'food consumer' demand has led firms to use more sophisticated marketing techniques to better understand differentiated consumer needs (DeJong et al., 2006). This forces food firms to develop new radical products and to adopt innovative technological solutions and new business models.

As far as supply chain organisations are concerned, innovation remains a highly challenging and multifaceted process to manage the food industry. This is mainly due to the many actors involved in food production. The main actors in the food supply chain are distributors, retailers, suppliers, wholesalers, and end users (the final consumer or another firm). The actors involved in supply chain collaboration mechanisms are both large firms and SMEs. As food products and services continue to grow in complexity, it is increasingly likely that potentially useful knowledge will reside outside of firms (Bercovitz and Feldman, 2007). Therefore, intermediate consumers and end-users are also considered as key actors who are involved in the food supply chain, and food firms continue to encounter a number of challenges in meeting all of the different and often contradictory demands of these actors (Grunert et al., 2005; Mikkelsen et al., 2005).

From the above considerations, it is clear that innovation must be managed by both individual company as well as within and/or across organisational boundaries and along the value chain

as a whole (Costa and Jongen, 2006). Based on the above-mentioned arguments, it appears that innovation in the food industry is based on the decisions and activities of the company itself as well as other entities involved in the innovation system. Similar considerations are valid in terms of open innovation in the food industry. Due to the number of actors involved in the development of innovative products and services, innovation activities must be co-ordinated very carefully (Bigliardi et al., 2010).

The main aim of implementing open innovation in such a scenario is to access external sources of knowledge and actively take part in the creation of inter-organisational knowledge and skills. Innovative food businesses may institute more or less formal agreements with supply chain actors as well as with other external firms such as universities and research centres to gain external knowledge. However, Knudsen (2007) argues that food sector firms prefer to build partnerships with companies belonging to the same industry. Therefore, it is characterised as highly overlapping knowledge, skills, and competencies. This overlap is approached as a facilitator of the management of innovation processes. As a result, the probability of success as a consequence of the innovation process is increased. However, companies in more traditionally innovative industries are often involved with the food chain, and many of the innovations initiated in the food sector have been developed outside the processing industry (Maula et al., 2006).

Biotechnological and preservation technology industries offer many opportunities for added value in food sector firms (Juriaanse, 2006; Maula et al., 2006). Nanotechnology is another technological approach that can be applied to the food industry for added value. Nanotechnology can briefly be described as the engineering of a minimal system and structure. This consists of a set of technologies that can be developed and used in various activities and in the agro-food sector (Serrano et al., 2014). Although Nanotechnology is an emerging technology with extensive potential to meet customer demand, it is limited to the food industry due to safety reasons (Juriaanse, 2006).

There is very limited empirical evidence regarding OI strategies. However, some studies discuss how different companies succeed in overcoming some of the obstacles to innovation (Bigliardi and Galati, 2013). Thomke and von Hippel (2002) suggested in their study of 'Flavours' suppliers for the food industry (e.g., the International Flavors Fragrances) that involving consumers in the innovation process and outsourcing new product design to customers can be effective. In effect, the International Flavours Fragrances managed to gather

valuable information on consumer tastes which also helped them to avoid costly marketing research and reduced trial and error cycles.

Similarly, Huston and Sakkab (2006) introduced the successful case of Proctor and Gamble and suggested that the company minimises the time required for marketing its product through the insourcing of technology to print edible images. This was implemented and used on a new type of 'Pringles' potato crisps. There are many other stories of successful open innovation implementation in the food sector.

The food and drink industry is highly diversified, comprising of a range of companies of different sizes. The industry is considered the largest manufacturing sector in the European Union in terms of turnover. According to the "Food Drink Europe" report (2017), the food and drink industry turned over a total of €538 billion generated from SMEs and €102 billion value-added in 2016. In addition, SMEs also provided two thirds (2.8 million) of total employability. The food and drink industry accounts for over 285,000 SMEs. This shows the importance of food and drink SMEs to the global economy. The food and drink industry is a mature and relatively low-tech industry mostly dominated by small firms (Acosta et al., 2013).

Innovation trends in the food and drink industry are geared towards sustainability and bio-based economies (Boehlje et al., 2011; Lybbert and Sumner, 2012). Innovation in food and drink sector SMEs are incremental rather than radical (Galizzi and Venturini, 1996; Grunert et al., 2008). These firms mostly focus on improvement or variances to existing products. The predominant application of incremental innovation by food SMEs is mainly due to demand constraints and conservative consumer behaviour. However, Bayona-Saez et al. (2017) noted that the traditional use of incremental innovation strategies in this sector represents a significant trend change in terms of the complexity of innovating. This could result in a number of radical innovations in an area where collaborative options illustrate good outcomes.

In addition, there are various factors which favour the implementation of open innovation, for example, intense collaboration along the value chain (food processing and distribution), a revolution in technological change, the maturity of the food market, intensive competitiveness in the marketplace and the small size of firms (García et al., 2014). As a result, the sector might show more interest in innovative development paths.

Many authors who have studied open innovation practices in firms (Vanhaverbeke et al., 2007; Sarkar and Costa, 2008; Fortuin and Omta, 2009; Bigliardi and Galati, 2012; Acosta et al., 2013; Bayona-Sáez et al., 2013). These studies evidence that open innovation is an appropriate

paradigm for addressing new challenges encountered by the food industry. Open innovation practice provides an alternative strategy through which growth-oriented SMEs can collaborate with other firms. As a result, they can access inter-firm resources at low-cost and develop new products in new markets (Chesbrough, 2003; Chesbrough et al., 2006; Teresco, 2004; Wynarczyk, 2013).

2.6.4. Challenges Food SMEs Face Whilst Adopting Open Innovation

SMEs are considered the backbone of most economies. For example, 99.1% of Europe's 274,000 food and drink companies are SMEs. These SMEs account for 48.7% of turnover (£404 billion) and 63% of employment (2.7 million jobs) in Europe's food and drink industry. Despite their enormous contribution to the economy, SMEs have received very little attention, and are overshadowed often by large and multinational companies. Thus, the implementation of open innovation in SMEs is an area that is not well understood (Saguy and Sirotinskaya (2014).

Lindegaard (2010) notes that there are three kinds of organisations which are champions, who are very small (around 10%) in numbers, contenders representing 30%, and pretenders representing 60%. The champions benefit from open innovation processes because of their mastered disciplines. Contenders are aware of the advantages of open innovation management. On the other hand, pretenders are ignorant of open innovation management practices. This suggests that the implementation of open innovation is far from straightforward and real challenges remain salient.

OI entails a continuous search of the internal environment for new ideas, information, and technologies. However, search strategies offer less benefit for small firms in comparison to large organisations (Lee et al., 2010). SMEs face many challenges in implementing OI strategies. Small businesses face challenges such as limited resources, financial constraints, the complexity of scientific research, limited access to up-to-date scientific excellence and many other constraints (Abouzeedan et al., 2013). Christensen et al. (2005) argued that OI often incurs high transaction costs. In addition, they highlight the complexity of interplays with technology entrepreneurs and incumbents.

However, Pullen et al. (2012) explain that though SMEs face challenges in implementing OI, it is still extensively practised. Chesbrough and Crowther (2006) study on OI in low-tech industries found that SMEs picked up OI adoption to some extent. Moreover, Vanhaverbeke et

al. (2012) indicate that SMEs undoubtedly practice OI in one way or another by focusing on short-term profitability.

On the other hand, Van de Vrande et al. (2009) argues that the challenges facing SMEs are related to organisational and cultural issues, for instance, venturing, customer involvement, external networking, and research and development. Moreover, Hossain (2015) states that SMEs experience different challenges in different parts of the world. In developing countries, government agencies set up innovation hubs that guide SMEs to connect and collaborate with independent bodies for effective innovation practice (Vrgovic et al., 2012). On the other hand, in terms of international competitiveness, SMEs rely heavily on two major internal components and two external primary components. The internal components are 'R&D capacity and managerial structure' and 'competencies'. On the other hand, the two external components are 'Open Innovation Practice' and 'the ability of the firm to attract government for governmental support' (Wynarczyk, 2013).

Open innovation requires a predominantly internal knowledge base and additional capabilities to turn externally gained knowledge and technologies into commercially viable products by integrating them with internal expertise and technologies. Therefore, after addressing valuable external ideas, knowledge and technologies firms should absorb and combine these with internal knowledge to turn these into commercialised viable products (Sag et al., 2016). However, SMEs experience lower impacts from open innovation methods due to a lack of skilled workers and technologies in comparison to large firms (Spithoven et al., 2013). Similarly, Chesbrough (2010) highlighted that SMEs lack the capability to both seek and absorb external resources in comparison to big organisations.

In addition, SMEs encounter challenges such as transforming and exploiting scientific results from universities and other research laboratories into ideas because many do not have scientific expertise. This limits the ability of SMEs to 'absorb capacity'; a concept that speaks to the firm's ability to recognise the value of new information and to apply it commercially (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990).

Firms are required to monitor collaboration with external actors after detecting useful internal knowledge and choosing the right partners. However, scarce resources and competencies affect the ties SMEs have to other organisations to establish and maintain networks and collaborations (Dodourova and Bevis, 2014).

Moreover, established partnerships and other practices need to be managed for higher returns and to support the successful innovation process. Brunswicker and Ehrenmann (2013) argue that SMEs need more managerial capabilities as part of their basic administrative system to achieve OI. However, SMEs lack both the requisite managerial and technical skills (Rahman and Ramos, 2010). Finally, the open innovation approach demands innovation through partnerships. Theyel (2013) emphasises that open innovation depends on best practice and appropriate partner choice. SMEs, in contrast, lack the resources and managerial capacity to find suitable partners and create and continue collaborations (Sag et al., 2016).

In summary, the factors that prevent SMEs from adopting OI are their small size, their limited managerial capacity, and their lack of skills.

Although many articles have highlighted a number of challenges and consequences related to open innovation, no studies have been found on the operational challenges in the context of UK-based South Asian food and drink Wholesale SMEs. Therefore, the principal objective of this study is to address this knowledge gap.

2.7. The Importance of Collaboration and Networking to Open Innovation

Open innovation is useful mainly for commercial purposes and for SMEs to fulfil consumer demands and compete with potential competitors (Vrande et al., 2009). To successfully commercialise products and services, SMEs must interact with source innovation as part of the recognition phase of the innovation process, and at the end of the innovation process (Hemert et al., 2013). Kang et al. (2013) believed that government support could guide SMEs towards successful commercialisation. However, a lack of financial resources and other resource requirements means SMEs struggle to commercialise their products and services (Lee et al., 2010). Hence, many other scholars advocate that this issue can be resolved if SMEs collaborate with other partners as intermediaries (Hossain, 2015). Commercialisation can be more effective if the owners more effectively network with other professional bodies.

Today's globalised market conditions are pushing organisations to adopt change to grow and to compete sustainably. The changes that are salient are inter-company cooperation and networking, which enables firms to compete and innovate in the dynamic environment (Sirec and Bradac, 2009).

SMEs have limited financial resources and face a shortage of human resources. They have limited access to relevant information and shorter time limits. Moreover, SMEs are usually reluctant to take a risk and show little interest in engaging with external help.

Networking can be defined as activities in which SMEs build and maintain business relationships with other professional bodies (Carson et al., 1995). A networking system has been characterised based on three groups by Witt (2004), and this is presented in the figure below.

Figure 2-3: The attribution of entrepreneurial network

Source: Witt (2004)

The first characteristic of Witt's (2004) attribution is the capacity to build and develop a network. Secondly, the structure of networking and finally, the information provided by the network partners are key. This is how firms benefit from entrepreneurial networking activities (Witt, 2004). According to Sirec and Bradac (2009), the benefits of networking activities can be measured based on new information that has been provided by contributors to the network. Therefore, it can be said that networking plays a pivotal role in OI in any industry.

The need for SMEs to draw on their networks as a means to complement their scarce internal resources has subjugated much of the academic debate (Zeng et al., 2010). Cumbers et al. (2003) promulgated that SMEs can offset the size-related advantages of big organisations through the benefits they derive from localised networks and learning. Likewise, Rammer et

al. (2009) have illustrated that SMEs without in-house R&D can yield similar innovation success as R&D performers if they source for external knowledge while also effectively applying human resource management or teamwork to facilitate the innovation process. Nevertheless, concerns are highlighted in the literature regarding the aptitude of driving innovation related benefits from external linkages (Hoffman et al., 1998). SMEs are usually defined by a specific knowledge base associated with core business (Bianchi et al., 2010; Huggins and Johnston, 2009). Small and medium-sized firms encounter barriers when they deal with new knowledge in unfamiliar areas. Moreover, the often-limited numbers and qualifications of employees in SMEs can result in low absorptive capacity (Spithoven et al., 2010). Insufficient knowledge or dissimilarities and cultural and institutional differences between collaborative partners can create problems (Van de Vrande et al., 2009). Research on academia-industry collaboration has identified organisation and culture as one of the most salient constraints to collaboration (Saguy, 2011).

Previous studies on innovation in the food industry note that food SMEs are involved in several types of innovation management. For example, Menrad's (2004) study of "innovations in the food sector in Germany" illustrated that most food SMEs engage with both product and process innovations. Food SMEs not only engage with product and process innovations, but they also engage with marketing innovations (e.g., the launch of a new website) and business strategies (Baregheh et al., 2012). Similarly, Tripl's (2011) study of the Austrian food sector also demonstrates that food firms are involved in new product development as well as in process and marketing innovations (Lefebvre et al., 2015). Previous studies have established that food firms embrace innovation, but not to the same degree as other industries such as the high-tech sector (Fortuin and Omta, 2009; Gassman et al., 2010; Sarkar and Costa, 2008).

2.8. Conceptual Framework

Innovative ideas can emerge from within and outside firms (Chen et al., 2006; Chong et al., 2011). In past studies, the role of innovation in creating competitiveness has been discussed by Distanont and Khongmalai (2018), who developed a conceptual model based on a quantitative methodology involving a survey. The existing literature confirms that innovation has a significant influence on competitive advantage. External factors at the micro-level (market orientation) influenced the development of SMEs' innovation systems more than external factors at the macro-level (international context). The influence of competitors who introduced new products and services to the market resulted in other firms imitating or following the same

paths (Distanont and Khongmalai, 2018). Suppliers also drive SMEs to be innovative. Since SMEs have low bargaining power, exchanging data and working with suppliers plays a significant role in creating value as part of an innovation strategy. Customers are another important stakeholder group to consider in terms of product and process innovation (Distanont and Khongmalai, 2018). Based on the literature presented in this chapter, the following conceptual framework is formulated.

Figure 2-4: Research Conceptual Framework

Source: The Author

The top management bodies set an organisation’s operational strategies and innovation directions. However, the innovative ideas come from employees and R&D departments. Innovative idea generates with the combination of both external and internal bodies is more effective. Innovation studies suggest that SMEs cooperate and collaborate to reduce costs and business risks and to extend skills and competencies (Huang et al., 2009; Martinez et al., 2014). SMEs utilise OI strategies by interacting with their internal and external bodies to improve

products/services. Innovation processes are systematic and interactive as they involve other entities, such as suppliers and players, in developing innovative products (Rahman and Ozuem, 2018, 2019). Similarly, past studies showed that collaboration and interactions with external parties, such as consumers and suppliers, positively impact product innovation (Freel, 2000; Faems et al., 2005). The main benefits attributed to these types of collaboration and partnerships are that they enable firms to get better product development and fulfil customer expectations (Dries et al., 2014; Moskowitz and Saguy, 2013).

Aziz et al.'s (2017) study suggested that collaboration with suppliers improves product quality and reduces costs and time to markets. A firm's suppliers are the critical stakeholders in contributing knowledge as they share common goals with the firm. Similarly, other studies also showed that a firm's interaction with its suppliers helps product innovation through knowledge sharing (Nieto and Santamaria, 2007; Wilhelm and Kohlbacher, 2011; Indarti and Postma, 2013). Moreover, Inkpen and Pien (2006) believed that collaboration with competitors is positively related to a firm's innovativeness as it enables firms to attain good insights into their technological know-how.

In contrast, Saguy and Sirotinskaya (2014) indicated that collaboration with other partners, such as competitors, could lead to information leaks. However, there is no evidence that collaboration with external partners leads to information leaks (Shadat and Nasrat, 2020). It is also essential for firms to understand and recognise the innovative ideas from external partners. Rothwell (1992) identified that innovation success depends on factors such as creating good internal and external communication systems, effective articulation of successful sources of scientific and technological know-how, and the willingness to gather effective feedback from external parties.

2.9. Summary

This chapter presented a critical review of open innovation. It provided a broad review of open innovation in SMEs. The researcher looked at the core processes of open innovation and how these are applied in different industries. The chapter critically reviewed the literature gaps in open innovation, and the types of open innovation were also critically reviewed. In addition, this chapter discussed SMEs and their categories. The underpinning theories in relation to SMEs' competitiveness, the benefits of open innovation, the importance of networking, and

collaboration were also critically discussed. The chapter ended by developing a conceptual framework of the study. After critically reviewing the extant literature, the intention is to provide an overview of how collaborative networks guide firms to develop new or improved products or existing products and services through open innovation strategies. The next chapter discusses the research methodology of this study.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Introduction

The previous chapter critically reviewed the literature on open innovation strategy. It examined the core processes of OI, the implementation of the strategy in different industries and the importance and economic contribution of the food sector in the UK market. Furthermore, the opportunities and the benefits of OI strategy to UK-based food sector SMEs and micro-businesses were examined.

This chapter provides a clear overview of the methodology applied for this study. It explains the chosen research paradigm that was used to critique open innovation strategies in the food sector. The chapter continues to defend the qualitative research as a suitable methodology for this study. In addition, it describes the methodological approach, research design, case study format, pilot study, sample size and data collection technique and procedure relative to this thesis. Finally, a number of ethical considerations are discussed.

3.2. Research Paradigm

Identifying a research paradigm is the initial stage of choosing an appropriate method and design for any study. There is a necessity to illuminate and clarify the framework upon which research will be conducted. The term ‘paradigm’ originates from Kuhn’s (1970) analysis of revolutions in science. The word ‘paradigm’ means a philosophical way of thinking about the world. The paradigm explains the significant collection of beliefs shared by scientists. A paradigm is a set of agreements regarding how research problems should be understood, how the world is viewed, and how to conduct research (Creswell, 2003; Rahi, 2017).

In management research, the term ‘paradigm’ is used to describe a researcher’s worldview (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). Denzin and Lincoln (2000) define paradigm as a human construction that considers researchers’ views in the construction of meaning embedded in data. More specifically, a research paradigm is simply a belief system or theory that guides the way we establish a set of practices. Thus, it contains a basic set of beliefs or assumptions that can lead to research inquiries as part of a specific study (Guba and Lincoln, 2005). Myers and Avison’s (2002) study stated that ‘the most recommended method for defining a valid research is to follow a research paradigm’. There are four principal research paradigms that have been

extensively used, and these are positivism, interpretivism, realism and pragmatism (Saunders et al., 2009).

Johnson and Clark (2006) stated that, as a business and management researcher, it is necessary to be aware of the philosophical commitments that every researcher should make when it comes to the research strategy. In addition, the paradigm makes it clear to the reader about the nature of the research. However, Johnson and Clark (2006) also argue that it is not necessary for the research method to be philosophically informed. Rather, it is important for the researcher to precisely reflect upon the selected philosophical choice.

Positivism is an epistemological position which supports the application of the methods of the natural science to the study of social reality (Bryman and Bell, 2007). Positivism, also known as logical positivism, is the mainstream philosophical position of management studies (Johnson and Duberly, 2000: 38). Positivism is a philosophical approach which recognises a scientifically verified issue. Positivism comes from the natural sciences, where researchers are the independent observers. Therefore, biased is excluded from positivism.

The term positivism was coined by Auguste Comte (1798-1857), and it refers to an assumption that only legitimate knowledge can be found from experience. Positivist research produces facts and accounts that correspond to an independent reality. Positivism is value-free and prioritizes observation. Positivists believe in empiricism: the idea that observation and measurement are the essence of scientific endeavour. Positivism has some relevance within business research, but it is more closely related to logic and ways of doing quantitative research (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2016). In addition, qualitative research can apply some aspects of positivism when theory testing is at the forefront of research. However, other philosophical stances are more applicable to qualitative research than positivism.

In addition, positivism chiefly analyses quantitative data which is necessary for the current study. According to Bryman and Bell (2007), positivism entails both inductive and deductive approaches. The main purpose of the positivist research is to test theories and provide materials for business development laws (Bryan and Bell, 2007). Positivism is generally used in natural science, and it is a critical and objective based method. Saunders et al. (2003) study stated that the positivist research approach includes numerous philosophies relating to natural science; for instance, universal law and the view of everything that exists in nature. He also stated that, in using a positivist philosophy, the researcher plays an important role as an objective analyst to evaluate data for the purposes of the research and its objectives.

Therefore, social constructionism has been applied in this research in order to explore open innovation strategy in the food sector SMEs. Social constructionism is a new paradigm that has been developed by philosophers during the last half-century, largely due to the limited success from applying the principles of positivism in social science research. The idea of social constructionism focuses on the ways people make sense of the world by interacting with each other via the medium of language. Gergen (1985:260) stated that ‘social constructionist inquiry is principally concerned with describing the process by which people explain, enlighten, or otherwise they account for the world in which they live.’ Social constructionism is an ontological position which states that social phenomena and their interpretations are continually being conveyed by people (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Moreover, it suggests that social phenomena and categories are produced through social interaction as well as through a constant state of revision. Constructionism implies that the categories that people employ in seeking to understand the natural and social world are in fact, social products. These categories do not have built-in essences. Instead, they are interpreted through social interactions. For this current study, such an approach would allow the researcher to develop a better understanding of open innovation application in the food sector by interpreting people’s thoughts. According to social constructionism theory, the existence of all cultural and social reality, for instance, values and meaningful actions occurs because of social actions and practices which are collectively performed and generally taken for granted (Barger and Luckmann, 1966; Segre, 2016).

The implementation of social constructionism entails an explorative and qualitative research design (Burr, 2003; Rahi, 2017). Social constructionism is one of a group of approaches that Habermas (1970) has referred to as interpretive methods. For interpretivists, the world is too complex to be condensed into a set of observable laws to understand the real conditions behind reality. This is seen as a more important issue than generalisability (Gray, 2004).

According to Leitch et al. (2010), interpretivism is recognised as an ontology that argues that all observation is based on theory and value, and that the exploration of the social world is not, and cannot be, a quest for an isolated independent reality. On the other hand, the premise of positivism is a realist ontology that assumes that observation is not obstructed by theory, and that the role of the researcher is to identify laws like generalisations and reasons for what was observed. It is not possible to establish any arguments to build knowledge without understanding the social world (Bernstein, 1995; Johnson, 1987). Interpretation is essential for

all research, and it is important that we acknowledge the role of values, histories, and interests in the production of knowledge (Koch and Harrington, 1988).

In other words, interpretivist research represents a shift away from explaining human behaviour by way of casual relationships between variables. An interpretivist approach guides the researcher to view social phenomena in a robust way by implementing the multifaceted and dynamic quality of the social world through interviews and surveys undertaken with participants (Bogdan and Taylor, 1975). Interpretivists do not prefer using methods that deal in objective or precise information. Rather, interpretivists view the world through “a series of individual eyes” and choose participants who “have their own interpretations of reality to encompass the worldview” (Mcqueen, 2002:16).

Thus, quantitative methods are not an ideal mode of interpretivism (Thanh and Thanh, 2015). Instead, interpretivists defended the claim that qualitative methods are approachable means for examining reality. In addition, Creswell (2009:4) argues that “qualitative research is a means of exploring and understanding the meaning individuals and groups ascribe to a social or human problem.” Interpretivism is perfectly compatible with the research purposes of a management study as its focus is to understand what is happening in a given context (Carson et al., 2001). The epistemological stance of interpretivists holds that knowledge is only gained through social constructions such as language, shared meanings, tools, and documents (Walsham, 1993).

Interpretivism is slightly different to positivism. Positivism is based on large samples, whereas interpretivism uses small samples to target for data collection processes. Using interpretivism, the researcher can express his own feelings.

Therefore, the epistemology of social constructionism has been chosen as a reasonable approach from a subjectivist’s perspective to conduct this research of open innovation strategy in UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. Social constructionism/interpretivism is a preferable philosophical stance for this qualitative study. Extant studies on open innovation in the food sector SMEs tend to be based on mixed methods approaches.

However, this study is solely based on a qualitative approach. Therefore, data were gathered through interactions with owners and managers of food SMEs. Schwandt (2002) remarks that there are both weak and strong versions of social constructionism that vary in their views regarding social constructionism. Constructionist views of knowledge production is useful in qualitative research as they accentuate the close relationship between the researcher and the

area of research. They focus on interactions and understanding as the basic tenets of research (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2016).

The following section provides the research approach adopted, underlining what methods have been employed, along with justifications.

3.3. Research Approach

Methodology in research, refers to the way in which we approach research problems and seek answers to particular problems. In social science studies, the term ‘methodology’ applies to how research is conducted. Our assumptions, interests and purposes frame which methodology we select. Qualitative methodologies denote, in the broadest sense, research that produces descriptive data that are gathered from people’s own written or spoken words and observable behaviours.

In qualitative research, researchers are concerned with the meaning people attach to things in their lives (Taylor et al., 2015). Qualitative research understands people from their own frame of references and their own experiences of reality (Corbin and Strauss, 2008). This study uses qualitative research to enhance the understanding of open innovation implementation in UK-based food wholesale sector SMEs, especially South Asian food wholesale companies. Qualitative research discusses the meanings, definitions, characteristics, metaphors, symbols and descriptions of things.

Qualitative and quantitative methods provide different, complementary pictures of the things that a researcher observes. Qualitative research tends to evaluate the research area with words, images, and descriptions. In contrast, the most quantitative analysis relies predominantly on computers, numbers, and graphs. Thus, quantitative strategies are more scientific than those employed in qualitative research (Lune and Berg, 2017). In qualitative research, the researcher endeavours to get to the core of what exactly happened to participants and what led them to the decisions that they made (Curry et al., 2009; Yin, 2015). However, qualitative research is often questioned for its dubious trustworthiness by some readers and quantitative researchers because the traditional concepts of validity and reliability are measured inversely between the two research approaches (Shenton, 2004; Ritchie et al., 2013).

There are many good reasons why qualitative research studies are conducted. Qualitative research studies are conducted to arrive at a complex, detailed understanding of an issue. The detail can only be established by interacting directly with people. A naturalistic approach is

useful in qualitative research which seeks to understand the phenomena in the context of specific settings, such as “real-world setting (where) the researcher does not manipulate the phenomena of interest” (Patton, 2001:39). Qualitative research assists with a study of issues that requires depth and detail.

Qualitative researchers approach field work without being constrained by pre-set categories of analysis that contribute to the depth, openness, and detail of qualitative inquiry. On the other hand, quantitative methods require the use of standardised measures so that the varying perspectives and experiences of people can fit into the limited number of pre-determined response categories to which numbers are assigned.

The advantage of using a quantitative approach is that it is possible to measure the reactions of large numbers of people with a limited number of questions, thus facilitating a comparison and statistical aggregation of the data (Patton, 2001). A broad, generalisable set of findings can thus be presented very briefly and clearly. In contrast, qualitative research methods typically yield a wealth of detailed information about a much smaller number of people and cases. This increases the depth of understanding of cases and situations, but it reduces generalizability.

Table 3-1: The common features of qualitative research

- Qualitative research tends to be concerned with words rather than numbers. It does not include statistical analysis and empirical calculation (Brink, 1993). It is usually involved with fieldwork.
- The aims and objectives of qualitative research studies are to provide in-depth knowledge and interpret participants by learning about the sense they make of the social world.
- Qualitative research is concerned with an inductive view of the relationship between theory and research.
- Qualitative research interprets people’s perceptions of different events and takes a snapshot of the people’s perceptions in a natural setting (Gentles et al., 2015).
- Qualitative research is less structured in description because it formulates and builds new theories (Leedy and Ormrod, 2001).
- Qualitative research consists of logic, ethnography, discourse analysis, case study, open-ended interview, participant observation, grounded theory, focus group, historical research (Cibangu, 2012).

- A qualitative researcher needs to spend a lot of time in the research setting with participants.
- Data are detailed, rich and complex (again, the precise depth and complexity of data may vary between studies).
- It requires clear information and a detailed analysis of opinions.
- The analysis retains complexity and nuance, and respects the uniqueness of each participant or case as well as recurrent, cross-cutting themes.
- The researcher is responsible for gathering true information to ensure ethical treatment.

Based on qualitative research, the researcher stresses the socially constructed nature of reality, the intimate relationship between the researcher and what is studied, and the situational constraints that shape inquiry. Qualitative researchers accentuate the value-laden nature of inquiry (Denzin and Lincoln, 2008). Qualitative research is based on a constructivist epistemology, and it explores what it assumes to be socially constructed dynamic realities through a framework which is value laden, descriptive, holistic and context sensitive. This involves an in-depth description of phenomena from the perspective of the people involved (Yilmaz, 2013).

In explaining qualitative research, Denzin and Lincoln (1994) state that qualitative research studies emphasise processes and meanings that are not scrupulously investigated. Therefore, qualitative researchers are keen to discover insights and interpret phenomena, rather than testing hypotheses (Merriam, 1988; Noor, 2008).

Both qualitative and quantitative researchers “think they know something about the social world worth highlighting to others, and they apply variety of forms, media and means to communicate their ideas and gain findings” (Becker, 1986:112). However, qualitative research differs from quantitative research in various significant ways (Becker, 1999). Though both research approaches are concerned with individual points of view, qualitative researchers think that they can get closer to the actor’s perspective through detailed interviewing and observations. Furthermore, qualitative research investigators dispute that quantitative researcher often unable to capture their subjective perspectives due to their reliability on more remote and inferential empirical methods and materials. Many quantitative researchers regard

the empirical materials produced by interpretivist methods as unreliable (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011).

Quantitative research studies are concerned with outcomes, generalisation, and cause and effect relationships through deductive reasoning. In contrast, qualitative studies are concerned with process, context, and interpretation according to human participants through inductive reasoning. Therefore, an inductive approach has been employed for this study to describe and understand the phenomenon of open innovation implementation to South Asian food wholesale SMEs by capturing and communicating participant experiences in their own words via interviews.

Figure 3-1: The Inductive Approach

Source: Goddard and Melville, (2004)

(Figure 3-1 reproduced with permission of the rights holder)

On the other hand, a deductive approach emphasises scientific principles, moving from theory to data observation. This is also called a highly structured approach. Thus, the research is independent of what is being researched (Saunders et al., 2009). However, the deductive approach generalises the conclusion of the research. Therefore, the current research has been conducted employing an inductive approach.

People can express how they make sense of the world around them and their experiences through interviews with open-ended questions. Responses from open-ended questions let the researcher understand phenomena as they are experienced by participants without pre-determining any standpoints. This gives qualitative researchers an in-depth knowledge of the

issues. Hence, the findings of qualitative research studies are far longer and more detailed and variable in content than quantitative studies. Thus, the researcher designed a set of open-ended questions to interview participants for this study.

The next section discusses the thinking behind the choice of an appropriate case study for this research.

3.4. Case Study Research

Prior to the commencement of data collection, it is important to elucidate the foundation of the research to confirm a well-defined focus (Mintzberg, 1979). A case study guides the researcher to a particular interest in the field of research by understanding the concept of the phenomenon (Morris and Wood, 1991).

The current study is a case study-based research. The case study looks, in depth, at a small number of organisations over a particular period of time. In management research, researchers tend to coalesce around either a single case or multiple cases. A single case study-based research strategy, also known as mono-case study, generally comes from a constructionist epistemology. On the other hand, those who endorse multiple cases typically fit with a more positivist epistemology (Easterby-Smith et al., 2018). Easterby-Smith et al. (2018) study also indicated that case studies have widely been adopted in social scientific research and are particularly valuable in practice-oriented fields such as management, education, and social work studies.

3.4.1. Single Case Study Strategy

For this research, a case of UK-based South Asian food wholesaler SMEs is reviewed by utilising a mono case study. In other words, a single case study research.

According to Dyer and Wilkins (1991), mono case study research is appropriate for creating better quality theories. Similarly, Yin (2003) suggested that a single case study is a better choice for identifying and evaluating a single and specific phenomenon. This study is conducted to explore OI strategy implementation for enhancing the competitiveness of South Asian food wholesale SMEs. Therefore, the researcher interviewed a small group of people in a top-level position of those wholesale SMEs to gain in-depth knowledge of the phenomenon.

Previous studies showed that a qualitative single case study provides empirically rich and context-specific information (Bianchi et al., 2010; Gardet and Fraiha, 2012; Brunswicker and Ehrenmann, 2013). It facilitates the researcher to get direct insights into a specific phenomenon. According to Eisenhardt and Graebner (2007), combining qualitative and case study research designs and methodology offers both opportunities and challenges for theory building from particular and unique cases.

On the other hand, in multiple case study research, researchers conduct studies to understand the differences and the similarities between the cases (Baxter and Jack, 2008; Stake, 1995). Multiple case study research can be ostentatiously costly and time-consuming to implement (Baxter & Jack, 2008). Another difference is that it enables researchers to analyse data both within each situation and across situations (Yin, 2003). Multiple case studies can be used to achieve either contrasting results for expected reasons or similar results (Yin, 2003). Therefore, this study is a single case or mono case study-based research.

Case study-based research empowers researchers to diligently examine the data within a specific context. A small geographical location or a limited number of individuals as the subjects of study, in most cases, are chosen in case study-based research. Case studies investigate contemporary real-life phenomena through detailed contextual analyses of a limited number of events. The case study research method “as an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, when the boundaries between the phenomenon and the context are not fully clear, and in which case the multiple sources of evidence are used (Yin, 1984:23).” The phenomenon of open innovation implementation in the context of UK-based South Asian-food wholesale SMEs has not extensively been exercised as yet.

A plethora of research studies on open innovation to the SMEs have been examined in past studies, but no research has been assessed in the context of South Asian-food wholesale SMEs. Hence, it is imperative to offer an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon and its context. A case study is a comprehensive description of an individual case and its analysis. According to Anderson (1993), a case study method is concerned how and why things happen to investigate contextual realities and the differences between what was intended and what actually transpired.

A case study never intends to investigate whole organisational issues but rather focuses on a particular issue (Noor, 2008). Open innovation implementation in UK-based South Asian food

wholesale companies enables the researcher to understand a specific problem or situation in great depth. A case study method guides the researcher on how OI implementation strengthens competitiveness in the context of UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs.

There are many benefits to adopting case study-based research. One of the important pros of adopting case study research is the opportunity for a holistic view of the process. Using case study research, “the detailed observations entailed in the case study mode enable researchers to study many different aspects, examine them in relation to each other, view the process within its total environment and also use the researchers’ capacity for *verstehen*” (Gummesson, 1988:76).

Case study research is mostly described as qualitative inquiry (Creswell, 2014; Denzin and Lincoln, 2011; Miles et al., 2014). Detailed qualitative research often shapes case studies that not only seek to discover or describe data in a real-life environment but also explain compound situations which may not be discussed through experimental or survey research. Case studies have been seen as viable methodological tools for three types of research which are exploratory, descriptive, and explanatory (Yin, 1994; Creswell, 1998).

Figure 3-2: Case study methodology

Source: Fisher and Ziviani (2004)

An exploratory case study sets out to explore any phenomenon which serves as a point of interest to the researcher. An exploratory research study is a valuable means of finding out 'what is going on to attain new insights, to evaluate a phenomenon in a new light' (Robson, 2002). Using exploratory case study research, a prior fieldwork and small scale of data collection may have to be gathered before research questions and hypotheses are proposed. A pilot study is considered an example of an exploratory case study (Yin, 1984; McDonough and McDonough, 1997).

There is also a need to determine the research protocol that will be used in the research. For descriptive case studies, the natural phenomenon is described, which occurs within the data in question. The goal set by the researcher is to depict the data as they transpire. The descriptive research design portrays an accurate profile of persons, events, or a situation (Robson, 2002).

Descriptive research answers questions such as what, who, where how and when. Descriptive research is more common in social sciences in a socio-economic survey and job and activity analysis, but it is also widely practised in other research studies such as the physical and natural sciences (Khazode, 1995). The aim of descriptive research is to portray the phenomenon and its characteristics. A descriptive case study is more concerned with 'what' rather than 'how' and 'why' something has ensued. Therefore, in descriptive case study research, observations and surveys are employed as tools for data collection processes (Gall et al., 2007). In a descriptive case study, the researcher must begin with a descriptive theory to support the description of a phenomenon (Zainal, 2007). This is considered a challenge associated with adopting descriptive case study research.

Based on an explanatory case study, the data are examined very rigorously both at a surface and deep level to explain phenomena in the data. The researcher may form a theory on the basis of data, and then set out to test the theory (McDonough and McDonough, 1997). Explanatory case studies are used for causal studies to examine certain phenomenon in very complex and multivariable cases. Explanatory research studies form causal relationships between variables. This is also called a causal research study. The emphasis here is on examining a problem in order to explain relationships between variables.

This study is exploratory to some extent since the primary objective was to look at the business phenomenon of South Asian food SMEs in the UK market. One of the objectives of this research was to look at the current situation of South Asian food SMEs from the perspective

of the UK market. This was achieved by interviewing various business managers and through observations of problems in South Asian small and medium-sized businesses. According to Robson (2002), asking questions and observing situations provides an understanding of the barriers these businesses face, which can easily be assessed in a new light (Robson, 2002). In addition, this study attempts to understand innovation strategies undertaken by these businesses to become competitive in the market.

The research sets out to explore the open innovation implementation in the UK-based South Asian food SMEs for the competitiveness. Thus, the researcher investigated how open innovation strategy implementation has helped South Asian-food SMEs to become competitive in the UK market. The researcher looked at the challenges of South Asian-food wholesale SMEs face in the multicultural UK market. The study also sets out to understand why these micro and small and medium-sized businesses implement OI in their business strategies to become more competitive. Thus, an explanatory case study design was selected to redefine the theory of open innovation in the context of South Asian-food wholesale SMEs in the UK market. In addition, the extent to which open innovation implementation can improve competitiveness in the market has been examined.

The study employed a case study based on grounded theory. According to Glaser and Strauss (1967), grounded theory is the perfect matchup for an inductive approach. Grounded theory guides the researcher to predict and develop a theory (Goulding, 2002). According to Saunders et al. (2009) grounded theory can explore a wide range of business management issues while conducting the research. However, grounded theory is often misunderstood when it comes to data interpretation (Suddaby, 2006). Grounded theory does not, for example, present raw data. These data are considered at a conceptual level to provide a reasonable conclusion.

The following section highlights the sample selection for this study.

3.5. Sampling

Choosing a sample population is essential for any research. Sampling procedures are not as fully prescribed in qualitative studies as in quantitative research. A lack of clear principles for selecting an appropriate sample provides much bewilderment in qualitative studies (Morse, 1991). In qualitative studies, sample selection has a profound effect on the ultimate quality of research. Sampling techniques can be divided into probability or representative sampling and

non-probability or judgemental sampling (Saunders et al., 2007). Probability sampling is selected in a case study where the population is known, and it is often equal for all cases.

A quantitative sampling approach draws a representative sample from the population so that the results of studying the sample can be generalised back to the population (Marshall, 1996). The selection of sampling method depends upon the aim and objectives of the research. According to Patton (2002), qualitative methods attain a depth of understanding, whereas quantitative methods intend to achieve a breadth of understanding. A qualitative study aims to illuminate and understand a complex issue in a more naturalistic way. The process of selecting a random sample is defined very rigorously.

According to Marshall (1996), the random sample provides the best opportunities to generalise the results to the population, but it is not an effective way of developing an understanding of complex matters which relate to human behaviour.

In qualitative business and management research studies, the research questions, aims and objectives, and the choice of research strategy may necessitate the use of non-probability sampling (Saunders et al., 2009). The researcher applied non-probability sampling to gain knowledge about open innovation strategy implementation in food SMEs. There are many approaches to selecting sampling techniques for a qualitative study.

The technique applied to the sample selection for this study was purposeful sampling. According to Patton (2015), the logic and power of purposeful sampling lie in selecting information-rich cases for in-depth study. Studying information-rich cases yield insights and in-depth understanding of a phenomenon. Purposeful sampling applies specifically to any qualitative study (Gentles et al., 2015). Some of the purposeful sampling techniques that are known are set out in the table below.

Table 3-2: Sampling Techniques with definitions in qualitative research

Sampling techniques in qualitative research	Explanation

Quota Sampling	Quota sampling is entirely non-random and usually applied for interview surveys, and it is therefore a type of stratified sampling. It is less costly and can be set up very quickly. This sampling system is usually applied to a large population.
Purposive Sampling	Purposive sampling enables the researcher to use judgement to select cases that will convey answers to the research questions. The sample size depends on researcher's choices and work with a very small sample group. The cost of applying purposive sampling for data collection is reasonable. This sampling technique is adopted for a grounded theory strategy.
Snowball Sampling or Chain Sampling	Snowball sampling is commonly used when the members of a desired population are difficult to identify. It is arguably the most commonly applied method when it comes to sampling strategies for qualitative research. It is often used as an effective way to gain information and access to hidden population (Sifaneck and Neaigus, 2001).
Self-Selection Sampling	This sampling strategy occurs when the inclusion and exclusion of the sampling units is determined by whether the units themselves agree or disagree to participate in the sample.
Convenience Sampling	Convenience sampling or haphazard sampling involves selecting those cases that are very simple to access in terms of the research sample. The cost of gathering the sample is reasonable. Control over sample content is low (Saunders et al., 2009).
Criterion Sampling	This type of sampling strategy comprises reviewing and studying 'all cases that meet some predetermined criterion of importance' (Patton, 2002). Criterion sampling helps to get more information from a small scale of samples. This saves time and money.
Critical Cases Sampling	In this sampling strategy, the researcher makes logical generalisations by taking a handful of cases which provide enough information about the general population.
Combination or Mixed purposeful Sampling	The process of triangulation or a combination of two or more methods of sampling strategies to attain more effective results.

Opportunistic Sampling	More samples are chosen during the data collection process.
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Source: Patton (2002)

The researcher selected a mixed combination of sampling strategies comprising of purposive sampling, convenience or haphazard sampling, criterion sampling and also snowball or chain sampling. Convenience sampling is also known as accidental sampling and is a non-probability sampling technique that is useful where the sample size of the target population meets certain practical criteria, such as easy accessibility, availability at a given time and willingness to participate in the study.

Purposive sampling has been selected to extract answers to the research questions. Convenience sampling is affordable to some extent, when the participants are willing to take part in the research. The main assumptions associated with convenience sampling are that members of the selected population are homogenous. Therefore, the research results obtained from random sampling are not radically different. The drawback of convenience sampling is that it is likely to be biased (MacKey and Gass, 2005). In addition, the researcher deployed criterion sampling for this research. Criterion sampling involves selecting cases that meet some predetermined criterion of importance (Patton, 2001).

The criterion sampling strategy was chosen because the researcher only contacted those participants who fell under the predetermined criteria. The list of criteria is presented in the below table.

Table 3-3: Inclusion and exclusion criteria for purposeful sampling.

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Annual Revenue	£50 million or less	More than £50
Total employees	250 employees or less	More than 250 employees
Ethnic Food SMEs	Only Asian food wholesale and cash and carry firms	Other ethnic wholesale food firms
Company Locations	UK-based only	Outside the UK

Rating	At least 1* or over (Customer Service Rating)	No ratings
Establishment	At least 5 years of running	Less than 5 years of running

Source: The Author

The researcher only contacted food wholesale SMEs who distribute or supply South Asian food across the UK. Companies with an annual turnover are £50 million or less were approached. The researcher excluded those firms who had more than 250 employees. Information about the companies was taken from corporate websites. In addition, the sample groups were selected based on a search of Google.

Criterion sampling may not be the only appropriate sampling strategy for qualitative studies. However, qualitative methods are often contrasted with quantitative methods on the basis of depth and breadth. In order to develop a comprehensive understanding of phenomena, the researcher used a snowball sampling technique to recruit more participants for this research. This sampling technique involves seeking information from key informants about the details of other ‘information-rich cases’ in the same field. The researcher asked participants who had already been interviewed to identify other people they know who fit the selection criteria. The snowball sampling technique is a useful technique for diverse and small populations.

The rationale for the sample size is stated below, along with a discussion of data collection and analytical methods.

3.5.1. Sample Size

Sampling is a core concern for a researcher in seeking to determine the success of a project (Tuckett, 2004). The sample size in qualitative research is smaller in numbers than that which is used in quantitative research. Qualitative research is often concerned with garnering an in-depth understanding of a phenomenon. In qualitative inquiry, purposive strategies are given precedence over methodological rules (Patton, 1990). According to Gaskell (2000), in qualitative research, the researcher does not follow any particular procedures in selecting respondents for sampling.

The main purpose is not to count opinions or people, but to discover the range of opinions and different representations of an issue. There is no rule of thumb in selecting a sample size for qualitative inquiry. In qualitative research, sampling usually relies on small numbers in which the main focus is to study issues in-depth and in detail (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Patton, 1990). In other words, sampling in qualitative research is concerned with the richness of information (Kuzel, 1992).

Sample size in qualitative inquiry has been the subject of enduring discussion (Sandelowski, 1995; Morse, 2000). The number of participants depends on the nature of the research topic (Bauer and Gaskell, 2000). Unlike straightforward statistic-based rules to set the sample size precisely for quantitative research, there is no straightforward answer for qualitative sample sizes. According to Patton (1990), the sample size depends on what you want to know, the purpose of inquiry, what will be useful and, what can be done within the available time and resources. Morse (2000) postulates that the more useable data is collected from each respondent, the fewer participants are required. However, the researcher must take into account parameters such as the scope of study, the nature of the subject area (i.e., complexity and accessibility), the quality of data gathered and the study design. The general aim of sampling in qualitative inquiry is to acquire extensive information that is important to understand the context of a research phenomenon.

According to Lincoln and Guba (1985), sample size determination can be guided by the criterion of 'information redundancy'. In other words, sampling continues until the researcher gets to the point where there is no new information elicited from interview participants. Moreover, the final sample size is determined by thematic saturation; the point at which new data appears to no longer contribute to the findings due to repetition of themes or comments by participants (Morse, 1995). This is the point where data generation is terminated. Qualitative researchers agree that it is impossible to specify a sufficient sample size in advance of a study (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). Charmaz (2006) suggests that the aims of research studies are the ultimate drivers of research designs, and therefore of sample size. Thus, a small study with modest claims might achieve data saturation quicker.

Many researchers have drawn general guidelines around sample sizes for qualitative inquiries. According to Morse (1995), ethnography and ethnoscience research studies can require up to between 30 and 50 interviews to reach saturation point. Creswell (1998) suggested that 20 to 30 interviews were enough to get to the data saturation point when choosing a grounded theory

methodology for a qualitative inquiry. However, 15 is considered the smallest acceptable sample size for all qualitative research studies (Guest et al., 2006). Previous studies on open innovation in food SMEs applied mixed methods to carry out between 8 and 12 in-depth interviews. However, this is purely qualitative study-based research, and the researcher reached the data saturation point after holding 22 individual in-depth interviews.

3.5.2. Respondent's Profile

The list of participants' names (using pseudonyms), their role in the company, along with the location of the various companies is set out in the table below.

Table 3-4: Participants, their role in the company and the locations of companies

Participant's Name (Pseudonym)	Employer Company	Role in the Company	Participant's Industry Experience	Location
Participant A	Company 1	Account Manager	8 Years	Cwmbran, Wales
Participant B	Company 2	Managing Director	15 Years	London
Participant C	Company 3	Operation's Manager	6 Years	Middlesex
Participant D	Company 4	Managing Director	25 Years	East London
Participant E	Company 5	Managing Director	12 Years	Middlesex
Participant F	Company 6	Managing Director	18 Years	Enfield
Participant G	Company 7	Operation's Manager	10 Years	London
Participant H	Company 8	Managing Director	12 Years	London
Participant I	Company 9	Managing Director	19 Years	Manchester
Participant J	Company 10	Managing Director	12 Years	Old Ham, Manchester
Participant K	Company 11	Managing Director	20 Years	Birmingham
Participant L	Company 12	Operation's Manager	5 Years	London
Participant M	Company 13	Operation's Manager	8 Years	London
Participant N	Company 14	General Manager	5 Years	China Town, London
Participant O	Company 15	Operation's Manager	9 Years	Essex
Participant P	Company 16	Managing Director	25 Years	London
Participant Q	Company 17	Operation's Manager	6 Years	Essex
Participant R	Company 18	Account Manager	7 Years	Luton
Participant S	Company 19	General Manager	5 Years	Hertfordshire

Table 3.5 presents a brief background to each of the companies involved, setting out their year of inception, their size, and their estimated market revenues.

Table 3-5: Company Information

Company Name	Company Background	Service Regions	Number of Employees	Annual Revenue s (£)	Key Products
Company 1	A leading manufacturer and distributor of frozen and fresh foods, supplier serving Asian restaurants, and specialist supermarket sectors. (Founded in 1991)	All over the UK	80 employees (Medium sized)	£20M	Frozen and fresh foods, chicken, meat, Indian spices (masala).
Company 2	A leading national manufacturer and distributor of premium desserts to the Asian restaurants and catering industry. (Founded in 1989).	All around England and Wales	20 employees (Small)	£4M	Asian especially the authentic Indian food, desserts for the Indian restaurants and Asian catering.
Company 3	An authentic spice and nuts supplier for the Asian supermarkets and restaurants. (Founded in 1998).	All over the UK	34 Employees (Small)	£10M	Indian spices, herbs, oils, yogurts, grocery items.
Company 4	Asian Restaurant supplier in southeast England. A wholesale and catering industry. (Founded in 1969).	Southeast of England	16 Employees (Small)	£5.5M	South Asian groceries, confectionary, drinks, spirits, catering, world food.
Company 5	An Asian supermarket and wholesale supplier serving restaurants and hotels around England. (Founded in 1982).	Supplies all around in England	120 employees (Medium-Sized)	£25M	Ethnic foods predominantly the South Asian foods such as chicken, fish, mutton, spices, oils, Asian confectionary items, Indian sweets, and savoury.
Company 6	Frozen food supplier for the Asian Restaurants. (Founded in 1960).	All around the UK	12 Employees (Small)	£5M	Chicken, Mutton, Prawns, King Prawns, Bangladesh Fish, Frozen Vegetables.

Company Name	Company Background	Service Regions	Number of Employees	Annual Revenue s (£)	Key Products
Company 7	A distribution company supplying to restaurants all over the UK. (Founded in 1989).	All over UK	25 Employees (Small)	£15M	Poultry chicken, meat, prawns, King prawns, wine, Indian beers, whiskey, containers.
Company 8	Fresh fruits and vegetable wholesale supplier. (Founded in 2004).	All around the UK	17 Employees (Small)	£2M	South Asian Fresh fruit and Vegetables.
Company 9	Asian food Cash and Carry and Wholesaler in the town serving the local community. (Founded in 2003).	Manchester	20 Employees (Small)	£3M	Asian grocery items.
Company 10	A family run authentic South Asian food supplier. (Founded in 2010).	Manchester, Liverpool, Newcastle, and some part of Scotland.	50 Employees (Medium-sized)	£7M	A range of fresh vegetables, chicken, meat, fish and all the Asian spices.
Company 11	A retailer and wholesale supplier for the restaurant and catering industry. (Founded in 1995).	West Midland Region	12 employees (Small)	£2.5M	South Asian spices, oils, chicken, meat, and fish and other grocery items.
Company 12	A wholesale supplier for restaurants and takeaways. (Founded in 2006).	All around the UK	45 Employees (Small)	£15+M	A major supplier of Prawns and Fish. Indian, Chinese, Japanese spices, and herbs.
Company 13	An ethnic food retail and wholesale shop. (Founded in 2000).	London	10 Employees (Small)	£2M	Spices, rice, oils, and other grocery items.
Company 14	Asian food wholesale and retail shop.	All around the UK	56 Employees	£5M	Bangladeshi, Indian, Pakistani, Malaysian, and Thai continental row and cooked food.

Company Name	Company Background	Service Regions	Number of Employees	Annual Revenue s (£)	Key Products
	(Founded in 2011).		(Medium-Sized)		
Company 15	A recognised leading importer and distributor of oriental foods. (Founded in 1982).	All around the UK	50 employees (Medium-sized)	£10M	King prawns, shellfish and molluscs, fish, meat and poultry, rice, noodles, spices, curry powder and all sorts of kitchen equipment.
Company 16	The leading distributor of the Asian food in the UK. (Founded in 1983).	All around the UK	50 Employees (Medium)	£8M	All kind of Asian grocery items including, fish, meat, spices, rice.
Company 17	UK's leading Halal meat Wholesale shop, a retail terminus built to satisfy the specific needs of halal meat consumers in the UK. (Founded in 2000).	All around the UK	10 Employees (Small)	£4M	Halal meat and poultry.
Company 18	An Asian food wholesale company in the UK market. (Founded in 1988).	England and Wales	20 Employees (Small)	£4M	Saffron Rice, nuts, cooked food, spices, herbs, and many South Asian items.
Company 19	A leading importers and distributors of Asian foods specialising in frozen products. (Founded in 1996).	All around the UK	51 Employees (Medium)	£12M	Frozen vegetables, noodles, dairy, canned food, rice and flour and many Indian, Filipino and Thai foods.

Table 3.3: Industry experts who participated in the study

Participant's Name	Participant's Position
Mr X	Industry Expert
Mr Y	Industry Expert
Mr Z	Industry Expert

The interview participants, especially the managers of these South Asian wholesale firms, were the key informants for this study. These managers were suitable for this study as they make all the operational decisions. The managers operate at a strategic level and are responsible for policymaking and decision making within the organisations. These participants were thought to be the most knowledgeable persons and have years of experience in South Asian food wholesale businesses. Moreover, the participants have extensive ideas about the current market situation.

Goffee and Scase (1995) argued that managers exercise control over their businesses through directly imposed but mostly unwritten guidelines and instructions. They may employ as many as 50 or more employees according to their ability to exercise control through informal, face-to-face processes rather than formalised structures and job descriptions. They retain almost total control and remain at the centre of the decision-making web, in a unique and powerful position within the firm (Goffee and Scase, 1995; Aaboen et al., 2006).

The interview participants of the study were the group of individuals responsible for the day-to-day running of the business, such as managing directors, general managers, and other senior executives. Sandada et al. (2014) stated that managing directors, general managers, operation's managers, and other senior executives are directly linked to the strategic decisions of firms; hence, in this study, they were found to be in the best position to answer any questions regarding the firm's strategy.

The above tables provide key information about the respondents and their companies. Furthermore, industry experts also provided insights and information about current Asian food markets. These experts are the most knowledgeable individuals in the South Asian food industry, and some of them are members of the Asian Catering Federation and the British Catering Association.

These selected South Asian wholesale food SMEs are representative of the UK as they trade nationally. In other words, these wholesale SMEs supply their products to South Asian restaurants, catering sectors, and other ethnic shops all over the country. These firms were selected from diverse regions with a high proportion of South Asian immigrants.

The selected participants were enough for this study as the primary purpose of the qualitative approach is not about the sample size but to provide in-depth and detailed information about the chosen phenomenon (Patton, 2002). In addition, there is no true representative in qualitative research as the main focus of this type of study is to explore a phenomenon in greater depth. The value of a qualitative study may depend on its lack of external generalisability in the sense of being representative of a large population (Maxwell, 2013).

Past qualitative studies on SMEs involved a similar sample size. For instance, Hoang et al.'s (2021) study on the influence of leaders in innovation in the context of Vietnamese tourism SMEs interviewed 20 participants from Hanoi, the capital of Vietnam (Hoang et al., 2021). Furthermore, another case study-based research on OI in SMEs conducted by Radziwon and Bogers (2019) held 23 interviews with staff from 12 firms in the southern part of Denmark.

After interviewing the managing directors and other operational managers from 19 South Asian wholesale firms and 3 industry experts, the researcher reached the data saturation point. Hence, adequate information had been gathered for this study. Scholars emphasise the richness of the data to get in-depth knowledge of a particular phenomenon (Dibley, 2011; Burmeister and Aitken, 2012). Furthermore, Bernard (2012) indicated that the exact number of interviews could not be quantified for data saturation in qualitative research, but researchers take what they can get for the study.

3.6. Data Collection Methods

In short, interviews are generally used in qualitative research. The researcher was interested in garnering facts, and understanding opinions, experiences, and processes in detail. Questionnaires can be used to gather responses from a large population to generate findings that are more generalisable. The researcher applied interviews as a method for data collection to gain more details and insights.

3.6.1. Semi-Structured In-Depth Interviews

In qualitative inquiry, interviews are the most widely employed tools for data collections (Cassell, 2005; Nunkoosing, 2005). Interviews are very common data collection techniques in qualitative studies that deal with ‘talk’ transformed into texts. According to Mason (2002), interviews are the most appropriate and commonly used form of qualitative research methods, as using interviews can guide the researcher to approach the research questions in such a way as to attain sufficient data and information from participants. Similarly, Ozuem et al. (2014) study outlined that the focus of qualitative interview is to extract the direct description of a particular situation.

Semi-structured interviews were selected as a means of data collection for this study. This type of interviews is well suited for the exploration of perceptions and opinions of respondents. It also enables the collection of more in-depth information and clarified answers to the most complex and sensitive issues. Semi-structured interviews help to make sense of information which was previously unknown. The participants are considered as experts on account of their experiences in the field. Semi-structured interviews are the most widespread format of interviews in the social sciences and the only format that receives attention in textbooks on qualitative research (Flick, 2002). Unlike structured interviews, which follow the same defined set of questions for all interviewees, the distinctive characteristics of semi-structured interviews mean they have a fluid-structure.

In semi-structured interviews, the researchers have a list of themes and questions to be covered to obtain sufficient information in relation to the research topic. This is preferred to a sequence list of standardised questions. Semi-structured in-depth interviews provide the opportunity to probe for answers where researchers want the interviewees to explain or build on their responses (Saunders et al., 2009). This is essential when the interpretivist epistemology is adopted. Therefore, semi-structured interviews were selected as an appropriate tool for understanding the complex phenomena that are the topic of this study. Prior to collecting main data for the research, a pilot study was conducted to ensure the data collection instruments are fit for purpose.

3.6.1.1. Pilot Study

Before collecting the main research data, a pilot study was undertaken. The main purpose of a pilot study is to refine questions that can be asked to respondents for the purposes of data collection (Polit et al., 2001; Baker, 1994). A pilot study can help to ensure that the research instrument is adequate and suitable for achieving the research objectives. “Pilot studies, also called as feasibility studies, are “small-scale versions or trial runs done in preparation for the major study” (Polit et al., 2001:467).

One of the advantages of conducting a pilot study is that it enables the researcher to assess the questions in terms of their validity and the likely reliability of the data they will yield. It provides advance warning of whether the main research instrument is fit for purpose in terms of meeting the objectives. The pilot study includes pre-testing the questionnaire, which can help establish content validity and enable the researcher to make any necessary amendments before the data collection process commences. The researcher should check the completed pilot questionnaire to ensure that respondents have a full understanding of the questions (Fink, 2003b).

For this research, a pilot study was undertaken for the above reasons. The semi-structured interviews were pre-tested with experts in the same field and then with a smaller population to refine the content. Modifications to the interview questions were made after the pilot study was undertaken. This helped to clarify the information required for open innovation. The pilot study was conducted in July 2018. A total of 2 Directors from the UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs were interviewed. The interview transcripts were analysed to ensure the collected data was adequate for achieving research objectives. Besides, following the completion of the interviews, the participants were requested to provide their suggestions regarding the interview process. They suggested that the researcher should spend more time building rapport with the participants and making them aware of the complex terms such as ‘Open Innovation’. These suggestions were considered carefully during the main data collection process.

3.6.1.2. Main Data Collection

Following the pilot studies, the main study was conducted and a total of 19 managers and directors from 19 UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs were interviewed. The

interviews lasted from 30 minutes and 1 hour and 15 minutes. The average time was 41 minutes. The preliminary list for potential participants was compiled based on internet searches and by looking up the top ranked Asian-food suppliers in the UK. The researcher then looked at company websites to gather basic information. Eventually, those who met the predefined inclusion criteria were contacted through emails, telephone, and social media platforms such as linked-in and Facebook. The participants were sent invitation letters via email, along with some attached files, including a participant information sheet and a set of questions to guide the interviews. Most of the participants selected their office as a preferred interview location.

All of the interviews were recorded. The interviewees were given consent forms to be signed. The researcher was always keen to note the key points during all interviews. In addition, the participants' body language was carefully observed throughout the entire interview period. According to Dunn (2005), interviews are verbal interchanges where one-person (the interviewer) attempts to elicit information from another person (the interviewee). Therefore, body language and the expression of the participant is crucial to observe.

3.7. Researcher's Reflexibility

A qualitative approach was chosen since this provides an accurate treatment of data. Most previous open innovation research was conducted by implementing mixed methods. Quantitative researchers obtain causal determination, predictions and generalisability of findings. On the other hand, qualitative researchers pursue an understanding of phenomena in detail. The researcher chose a qualitative approach for this study to gather, observe, describe and interpret relevant data.

The biggest challenge for the researcher was to collect data through interviews. It was a challenging task to convince the participants to take part in interviews. The sample groups were the directors and managers of Asian-food wholesalers. The initial challenge was to reach out to these participants. The researcher contacted them via telephone and email. It was very difficult to get reach them, as they had busy work schedules.

However, the researcher managed to gather sufficient interviews to achieve the research objectives. The motives for choosing to explore open innovation in the UK-based South Asian food industry stemmed from the observation that open innovation is a relatively new but trendy concept in business management. In addition, the Asian food industry makes a significant

contribution to the British economy every year. Not many studies have been conducted on open innovation in the context of UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. In addition, the researcher worked in the Asian catering sector for several years. The researcher was interested in working on a familiar research topic to develop a theory that could contribute to the literature and management practice.

3.8. Research Quality

The concept of research validity is often discussed in quantitative research. The trustworthiness of qualitative research is frequently questioned by positivist scholars. This is because the concept of validity and reliability are perhaps not addressed in the same manner as quantitative research analysis. However, many naturalistic researchers prefer to use different terminologies to distance themselves from positivists. There are four aspects that can be used to measure the trustworthiness of qualitative research, and these are credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability.

Lincoln and Guba (1985) claimed that credibility is one of the dominant factors that can determine the trustworthiness of research. The credibility of this study is established by interpreting the data in the context of open innovation amongst food SMEs. This approach was used to identify the characteristics and elements that were most relevant to the problem or issue under study.

The data for this study were collected from various individuals such as the directors and managers of food wholesalers, and industry experts. The informants were given the opportunity to decline to participate to ensure that the data collection sessions involved only those who were genuinely willing to participate. The participants shared their ideas and experiences without any fear of losing credibility in the researcher's eye. The participants were given the right to withdraw from the study at any point in time (Shenton, 2004).

Transferability is a type of external validity which refers to the degree to which the phenomenon or findings described in the study are useful in the context of theory, practice and future research (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). In positivist research studies, efforts are often made to demonstrate if the results can be applied to a wider spectrum. It is impossible to demonstrate that the results of a qualitative study are applicable to other situations due to the small number of participants (Shenton, 2004; Maxwell, 1992; Flyvbjerg, 2006).

However, if the practitioners believe that the situation resembles the study described, then they may relate the findings to their own setting (Baassy, 1981). Similarly, Firestone (1993) suggested that it is the researcher's responsibility to provide the necessary contextual information about the fieldwork sites to enable readers to make sense of the analysis. Therefore, all the required information was provided for this study to ensure the transferability of the findings.

To address research reliability, positivist researchers employ techniques to show results that would be repeated if the work was carried out in the same context, using similar methods and a similar research population (Shenton, 2004). However, this may not be possible using qualitative inquiry because of the changing nature of the phenomenon being scrutinised by qualitative researchers (Fidel, 1993).

However, the process within the study should be reported in detail to ensure data dependency as part of qualitative research (Shenton, 2004). Therefore, the researcher detailed the whole process to ensure the dependency of qualitative inquiry so that future investigators can repeat the work in a different setting.

To gain confirmability, the results must be clearly linked to the conclusion in a way that can be followed and replicated (Moon et al., 2016). Shenton (2004) believes that the researcher allows readers to administer confirmability by delivering a detailed methodological description, illustrating how the data emerge and how theories were developed based on the data. The confirmability of this research was achieved by outlining the methodological strategy. This research was achieved through in-depth interviews with directors and managers as well as industry experts.

3.9. Ethical Considerations

In qualitative inquiry, communication between the researcher and the participants can be ethically challenging since both are personally involved at different stages of the study. Therefore, adhering to specific ethical guidelines is mandatory to avoid conflict. Many major ethical issues were safeguarded in this study. The privacy of participants was protected, and the author ensured the confidentiality of all participants at all stages of the research. During the process of carrying out individual interviews, informed consent was obtained via a signed document. In addition, the author strictly followed the ethical guidelines of the University of the West of Scotland during and after the research.

3.10. Summary

This chapter presented the research paradigm underlying the study. A social constructionist, interpretative approach was used to gain insights into a social phenomenon. The chapter defended the selected qualitative approach for this study with extensive justifications, and it also outlined the necessity for conducting this study in the selected manner. In addition, the researcher confirmed the credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability of the research findings. The researcher also ensured that the research was conducted without breaching any ethical guidelines provided by the University of the West of Scotland. The following chapter analyses the research findings and the discussion of the study.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Introduction

This chapter presents data analysis of participant responses from interviews. The findings of this study are presented in two steps. Firstly, it analysed the strategic positioning of the South Asian food wholesale SMEs as well as their challenges. And secondly, it considered how OI strategies are used by UK-based South Asian food wholesale firms to evaluate their effectiveness for mitigating these challenges. The latter part of the chapter discusses the findings of this research by locating them in the broader context.

4.2. Analysis of the Research Data

In this research, thematic analysis is used to analyse the interview transcripts. Qualitative research is undertaken to generate knowledge grounded in human experience (Sandelowski, 2004; Nowell et al., 2017). Qualitative has become increasingly acknowledged and valued amongst researchers (Attride-Stirling, 2001). The research is undertaken rigorously and methodically to yield meaningful and useful results. Data analysis is characterised as the most complex phase of qualitative research (Thorne, 2000). Qualitative researchers need to be clear about what they are doing and why they are doing it, and they must include a clear description of the analytical methods employed to deliver a full understanding of how the research was analysed (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Malterud, 2001; Thorne, 2000).

Qualitative semi-structured interviews are one of the most dominant and widely accepted data collection methods in social scientific research (Bradford and Cullen, 2012). Semi-structured interviews are valuable data collection methods that allow researchers to explore subjective viewpoints (Flick, 2009). Denscombe (2010) suggests a number of principles to support an effective outcome from qualitative data analysis. A key principle is to compact large and diverse raw data into a succinct structure. This can be achieved by organising interview data and writing data into charts and tables.

This provides the researcher with the opportunity to isolate, compare and determine which areas to focus on. All respondents' transcripts were compared, the similarities and dissimilarities were identified and the patterns in the data ultimately recognised which led to

the formation of the themes (Ozuem, 2004). It also helps form a relationship between the research objectives and the summary. Denscombe (2010) also suggests that the researcher should conclude by developing a conceptual framework based on the research. Some researchers use programming software to prepare and analyse qualitative data, while others choose to use traditional methods.

Computer-based software, for example NVivo can produce more effective qualitative data analysis in terms of gathering evidence and subsequently organising and grouping it into similar themes or ideas. Using software to prepare qualitative data helps to produce more rigorous and validate findings. On the other hand, Welsh (2002) argues that software might not prove as helpful as one might expect. Because software is less effective in terms of addressing issues of validity and reliability in the thematic ideas. Particularly, NVivo is less useful to gain deeper understanding of data searching it is capable of doing through the thematic ideas.

Therefore, the researcher combined multiple methods for effective qualitative data analysis. NVivo software was used to filter repetitive words used by participants to come up with primary themes. These were then manually sorted to complete the process of data analysis. The themes were organised manually since these reflect the main objectives of the research. The thematic data analytical process followed the six steps established by Braun and Clark (2006). The researcher first applied NVivo to generate the initial codes, and then developed the main themes manually. Thematic analysis is a method that organises and describe datasets in rich detail. It also helps the researcher to interpret various aspects of the research topic (Boyatzis, 1998; Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Although thematic analysis is widely used for data analysis, there is no clear agreement about what it is, and how researchers should go about it (Attride-Stirling, 2001; Boyatzis, 1998; Tuckett, 2005). The thematic analysis is very flexible for data analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Similarly, Ozuem et al. (2008) study noted that the thematic analytic framework allows researchers to familiarised, reconsider and rework with the collected untidy data. Data analysis was conducted inductively for this study so that the themes are strongly linked to the data itself (Patton, 1990). The coded data were not extracted from a pre-existing coding framework. Thus, the findings offer a data-driven thematic analysis.

A social constructionist paradigm was applied to understand the social phenomenon of open innovation in South Asian food SMEs in the UK. In-depth interviews were conducted with the managers and directors of South Asian wholesale suppliers. The researcher applied a latent

approach in carrying out analysis. This meant it was possible to not only identify the surface meaning of the data, but to look beyond what was been said by each participant.

In applying thematic analysis rigorously, six major themes were generated. The first two major themes identified the circumstances surrounding the current Asian-food industry and the challenges they face in the market. The rest of the themes highlighted how South Asian-food wholesale firms overcome these business challenges to become competitive in the market.

4.3. Research Findings and Discussions

The researcher rigorously followed the six steps of thematic analysis which were developed by Braun and Clark (2006) before writing-up the findings in a report. The first step was to become familiar with the data by reading and re-reading the interview transcripts. As part of this process, all interviews were transcribed into a word document. The researcher then generated an initial list of ideas about the content of the data including any noteworthy patterns. The next phase involved searching for initial themes. These were reviewed and refined into headline themes. The table identifies these major themes together with their corresponding codes and keywords.

Table 4-1: Research Findings

Major Themes	Description	Codes	Key words
Hostile markets	A hostile market means one which is associated with over capacity, low margins, intense competition and management in turmoil. Firms compete with each other to gain attention and business of customers.	(1) Changes in food choice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthy food choice • Grilled food • Cosmopolitan food • Less oily food
		(2) Declining market/Business failure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supermarket superiority • Low profit margins • Closing down Asian food shops • Brexit uncertainty. • Staff shortages • Immigration policy • Low product range. • Too many wholesales shops
The Challenges of SMEs in the market	The lack of financial and technological resources, skilled workers, market access and market knowledge impact on the ability to be competitive in the market	(1) Intense competition in the market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High competition • Pricing issues • Too many shops around • Lack of buying power
		(2) Supply issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product availability
		(3) Customs rules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Import charge • Customs tax • Pesticide problems
		(4) Local authority	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Council support
		(5) FOB: - Free on Board	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transportation cost • Import cost

Major Themes	Description	Codes	Key words
		(6) Market knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of market awareness • Lack of skilled workers
		(7) Economies of scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of buying power
Motives for open innovation implementation	Something that causes organisations to act in order to reach their desired goals.	(1) Rollout products quickly in large market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using supplier's transportation to roll out goods
		(2) Fulfilling customer demand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer needs
Triggers for innovation implementation	Innovation potential are the sources that drive firms to be innovative in the market.	(1) Gap in the market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bridging the gap • Understanding customer needs • Competitive market
		(2) From customers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer feedback • Customer suggestions
		(3) From the area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modern business world • From competitors
		(4) Senior management bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Board of directors • Senior managers
OI strategies to	Defines what innovative measures Asian-food firms implement to overcome such barriers.	(1) Infrastructural Change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modernisation • Market diversification

Major Themes	Description	Codes	Key words
overcome business challenges		(2) Food processed innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New packaging • Food innovation • Processed food
		(3) Technological usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology utilisation • Digitalisation • Online ordering system • PDQ machines • Self-service system
		(4) Branded products and stock control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exclusive brand • Stock up exclusive branded items • Own branded products • Unique products • Own logistics • Different ethnic branded products
		(5) Open innovation with customers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building better customer relationship • Maintaining good-will • Customer feedback • Customer suggestions

Major Themes	Description	Codes	Key words
		(6) Collaboration with suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building Partnership with suppliers • With competitors • Building reciprocal relationship • Keep prices competitive
		(7) Open innovation implementation with employees' involvement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Managing Directors • Senior management body
Factors hinder implementing OI in Asian food SMEs	The aspects that affect SMEs in terms of implementing open innovation with external sources	(1) Technological incompatibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the value of technology
		(2) Collaborating with suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stock availability • Delivery waiting time
		(3) Collaboration with competitors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of stocks • Lack of trust between companies • Cultural issues between companies

Source: The Author

4.3.1. Theme One: Hostile Markets

The term ‘hostile market’ is a market defined by overcapacity, low margins, and intense competition. In such markets, management is typically in turmoil situation to compete. More specifically, companies compete with each other under these conditions to attract customers.

Hostile markets are the fundamental test of the ability of management. In a hostile market, too many competitors compete for the same consumer groups. The returns are low, sometimes abysmally low. The industry is plagued with excess capacity either due to a drop in demand in the market or high competition (Potter, 1994).

The findings suggest that the demand for South Asian food has dropped recently for several reasons. Food preferences have changed for the following reasons:

.....Our choice of food has been changed, going from unhealthy to healthy. So, people prefer to have more grilled food, you know, less oil. So, our Asian food particularly, Indian food, almost everything cooked with oil and Ghee (butter) and it's very unhealthy. So, people are choosing to have healthier food than Indians. Because of that, the industry actually is declining at the moment....

(Participant A, Account Manager)

Another respondent illustrated

..... I think the current situation of South Asian food is in a declining position in the UK market at the moment. Because the young generation is not into Asian food, they are more into all sorts of fast foods and things like that. They have a cosmopolitan food choice rather than a purely Asian choice of food. Therefore, it is in a declining situation.....

(Participant I, Managing Director)

Based on these views, sales revenue has declined as a consequence of changing food choices. People are health-conscious nowadays, especially the younger generations who follow a strict diet. A survey study conducted by ‘Nielsen global health and wellness’ on 30,000 consumers in more than 60 nations reported that younger consumers are far more concerned about everything from food ingredients, genetically modified food to organic foods (Watson, 2015). Today’s younger consumers are more willing to take the initiative on behalf of their wellbeing. This has a significant impact on the sales revenue of Asian-food cash and carry shops. One of

the industry experts also emphasised that people's food preferences have changed over the years.

..... People choice of food has been changing over the decade. People are more concerned about their health, especially the younger generation. Asian food, especially curry, was a weekend fun dining for the people with friends and family. It still is but not as much as it was back in the days. The younger generations are more into healthy food options....

(Mr X, Industry Expert)

Changes in food preferences have had a significant impact on the Asian food industry. The main customers of these South Asian wholesale companies are Indian restaurants and takeaways. When these shops' sales increase, they order in large quantities as they require more goods supply. The majority of the business conducted by wholesale businesses depends on these Bangladeshi and Indian catering firms. Wholesale cash and carry shops supply goods to many of these restaurants and takeaways.

Changes in food preferences do not just impact on the South Asian food market. There are many other issues that impact what is largely considered to be a declining market. Supermarket superiority is one of the main reasons why SMEs have to face the conditions of a hostile market. Local superstores have taken over what was once a thriving industry from small and medium-sized firms in the UK, as illustrated below:

.....A lot of competition nowadays have come from multiples such as Aldi, Asda, Lidl, Tesco, Sainsbury's and so on. So, the multiples are into the ethnic market. If you go to your local supermarket, you will see they have dedicated Asian foods. So, we find that difficult to compete with them. These supermarkets have more buying power than us. So, we are trying to compete, but that also means we are reducing our profit margins. So, that's how we are finding it difficult to compete with multiples at the moment....

(Participant E, Managing Director)

.... The big companies such as Asda, Morrisons, and Tesco started selling ethnic food in their stores which affected quite a lot to our business...

(Participant M, Operation's Manager)

These small and medium-sized shops find it difficult to compete with major supermarkets. Because of cutthroat competition with big firms, profit margins for South Asian food wholesalers are low.

Other respondents also emphasised the extent of market domination by supermarkets:

.... The market is mainly being dominated by big companies now. The big companies have a huge range of products. They have a variety in the product range. On the other hand, a company like us got a very limited product range. I think that's the main reason why SMEs and micro-companies are struggling now...

(Participant F, Managing Director)

..... The way the big supermarkets such as Asda, Tesco and Sainsbury's are catering for the Asian now, I believe we will not last more than 15 years in the retail side....

(Participant K, Managing Director)

He also made some remarks about the product lines of these market-dominant companies:

.... Now we have seen the shift in a lot of products. If you go to Asda and Tesco in the Asian people dominant areas, you will see a lot of Asian product lines. If they weren't selling it, they wouldn't still have it in stores. So obviously, they are selling Asian food products, and as a result of that we are losing out our customers...

(Participant K, Managing Director)

These superstores have more buying power than South Asian food wholesale SMEs. Indeed, their buying power distorts competition in the food industry, and they use it to reduce prices. This leaves many South Asian micro and SMEs in a weak position, and they find it hard to compete and survive.

The shortage of staff is one of those issues that South Asian food businesses are failing to survive. The respondents believe that staff shortages in the Asian catering industry are one of the big reasons why all the restaurants and takeaways are closing down rapidly. Thus, South Asian food suppliers are struggling at the moment.

.... The workforce is very much in a problem at the moment. As we mainly deal with restaurants and catering sectors, those sectors are suffering because of the shortages of qualified chefs, as a whole lack of skilled staff put those businesses under enormous pressure to survive....

(Participant G, Operation's Manager)

.....Some catering is closing down because of the staff shortages, which affects us a bit at the moment.....

(Participant D, Managing Director)

.... Half of Britain's curry houses will be forced to close within the next ten years. This means the end of approximately 17,000 Indian restaurants will be disappeared from high streets within a decade. The danger of closure arises from the threatened lack of skilled manpower to develop and improve Indian cuisine.....

(Mr Y, Industry Expert)

The above respondent claims that British-Bangladeshi restaurateurs run 90 per cent of curry houses in the UK. He also emphasises that the shortage of skilled staff and rising operating costs are to blame for many difficulties.

.... The prices of ingredients have gone up, but we can survive with increased prices if we have staff. Our main concern is not having staff available....

(Mr X, Industry Expert)

The industry contributes £4 billion to the British economy every year. Industry experts have highlighted the importance of the South Asian food industry to the British economy, as stated below:

.... The industry has created over 100,000 jobs for south Asian in the UK...

(Mr Z, Industry Expert)

.....At the moment, the industry is dying due to staff shortages. The next generation is not coming into this business, so if we do not get skilled workers from abroad, you will not see Indian restaurants on the UK streets. We can't get staff from the UK because people just don't want to do it....

(Mr X, Industry Expert).

Brexit uncertainty and immigration policy are two major issues that explain why these businesses are in a difficult situation. Immigration policy has changed recently, and the UK government has implemented a new points-based system immigration policy which will begin in January 2021.

Skilled workers have to earn £30,000 a year and will have to speak English fluently. Meeting this salary cost will be very challenging for these restaurateurs.

.... No ordinary curry chef earns £30,000, where the industry average is £20-22,000 but the cooks who marinate lamb chops and mix raita get less than that....

(Mr Z, Industry Expert)

The interviewees noted that the Asian food industry relies on restaurants and takeaway businesses.

.... Our business relies on those takeaways and restaurants. If these businesses don't do well, then it impacts directly on our business. Because 80% of our sales revenue comes from supplying goods to these Indian restaurants and takeaway shops.

(Participant I, Managing Director)

The British-Bangladeshi catering association explained that the industry is facing a great deal of pressure, and approximately three restaurants have to shut down every month in the UK.

Brexit also impacted significantly on the process of importing goods from other European countries, as illustrated below by another participant.

.... At the moment, the South Asian food shops are not doing very well because of Brexit. We are getting out of the European Union. I would say this is one of the main reasons. Another thing is the Restaurant and Takeaway businesses are running a bit quiet. When these restaurants are busy, then we are busy. As a result, our sales go up, because we are so connected to each other. The lion share of our sales revenue comes from Restaurants and takeaway shops. Another reason I would say the price of goods such as onions and potatoes, green chillies are so expensive nowadays. A few years back, it was very cheap to import, but now it's way too expensive. And that is because of Brexit. In my view, Brexit is a big issue for Asian food businesses for not doing well....

(Participant J, Managing Director)

Despite the declining market, the South Asian food industry is still considered to be a thriving market. All participants were optimistic about the industry and suggested that it had significant future potential if carefully handled.

South Asian foods are very popular in the UK. People love to eat South Asian cuisine. The demand for Asian products is rising because of large communities over here such as the Bangladeshi, Indian and Pakistani people living in the UK....

(Participant H, Managing Director)

The wholesale sector has been thriving despite all the business surviving issues. There are two categories: - the catering sector in which we sell to the restaurants and takeaways, pubs and hotels. The second category is where we sell our products to the independent shopkeepers. So,

the catering sector is growing, and the profit margin is good as well. We are doing a bit different than the others. We have our own supply chain which gives us competitive advantage...

(Participant L, Operation's Manager)

The findings indicate that, despite the declining market, the South Asian food wholesale sector has been doing well because of growing demand. Having an integrated supply chain makes the company competitive in the market.

It is evident from the research findings that the Asian food market conditions are hostile. Donald Potter (1994) highlighted this market hostility and noted the challenges for SMEs. Potter (1994) suggests that hostile markets exist when there are too many companies in competition for the same customer base and where the returns on investment are low. Pricing seems to be self-destruction to other firms.

Most interviewees outlined that South Asian food SMEs face significant challenges than in the past. This is due to many issues, including fierce competition. This is illustrated by Participant E (Managing Director) who noted.

...A lot of competition nowadays have come from multiples such as Aldi, Asda, Lidl, Tesco, Sainsbury's and so on. So, the multiples are into the ethnic market. If you go to your local supermarket, you'll see they have dedicated Asian foods. So, we find that difficult to compete with them.

In addition, there are arguable too many South Asian wholesale shops which serve the same consumer base. This resonates with Potter's (1994) definition of hostile markets. In particular, hostile environments have been described as stressful and risky, with minimal opportunities for businesses. They are sites of intense competition, and they present an overwhelming business climate (Khandwalla, 1977; Covin and Slevin, 1989). The South Asian food industry, especially the catering sector, makes a significant contribution to the British economy. The Asian catering sector employs over one hundred thousand people and contributes over £4.2 billion annually to the British economy (Seymour, 2019). The importance of this sector in the UK market is evident. However, South Asian food SMEs face a declining situation. The dominance of supermarkets is one of the significant issues that the sector faces. Participant M (Operation's Manager) outlined this point:

..The big companies such as Asda, Morrisons, Tesco started selling ethnic food in their stores which affects quite a lot to our business...

It is evident that supermarkets are dominating the Asian food market currently. Most supermarkets are supplying Asian foods, including halal meats. Therefore, South Asian food SMEs face enormous challenges to compete in this thriving market defined by cutthroat pricing strategies. The superstores have more buying power than these South Asian food wholesaler SMEs. The buying power of the superstores, therefore, distorts the nature of competition in the Asian food market. In addition, food preferences have altered over the years. The younger generations are more inclined towards cosmopolitan foods.

Human resources are an integral part of any organisation. Staff are considered to be the fundamental building blocks of organisations and the primary vehicles of organisational change (Ang, 2002). Around 3.2 million people are employed in the UK hospitality industry in hotels, pubs and restaurants. The sector generates some £130 billion (UK Hospitality report, 2018). Staff shortages exist in all parts of the sector. Staff shortages in the Asian food sector also impact Asian entrepreneurs, as illustrated by Participant G (Operation's Manager) and Participant D (Managing Director). The respondents believe that the South Asian food industry is very much in a difficult situation due to a shortage of skilled workers, especially in the South Asian restaurants and catering sectors. These sectors are struggling to have qualified chefs. As a result, they are closing their businesses.

One of the respondents, Mr Y (Industry Expert) illustrated that British curry houses will soon face closures due to staff crises. This is what he had to say:

...Half of Britain's curry houses would be forced to close within the next ten years. This means the end of approximately 17,000 Indian restaurants will be disappeared from high streets within a decade. The danger of closure arises from the threatened lack of skilled manpower to develop and improve Indian cuisines...

The research findings indicate that the lack of skilled personnel impacts the Asian food industry negatively. The industry as a whole is experiencing a labour crisis (Pratten and O'Leary, 2007). According to many of the interview participants, immigration policy is another reason why the Asian food industry, especially the catering sector, is facing staff shortages. Rules around general work visas require restaurants that want to hire chefs outside of European countries is very expensive nowadays.

The high costs associated with recruiting and sponsoring chefs and cooks are prohibitive to restaurateurs from the subcontinent, including Bangladesh, India, Pakistan and other such countries (Falconer, 2017). The respondent Mr X (Industry Expert) outlined the skilled staff

shortages in the South Asian catering sector, which impacted the businesses severely. He thinks that the hard immigration policy is the main reason why the Asian catering sector is struggling with staff shortages. This is what he had to say:

..The shortage of skilled staff in this trade. The is due to the hard immigration policy in the UK. People are not coming from Asian countries such as India, Pakistan and Bangladesh. When I say the hard immigration, I mean it is not as easy as it was back in the days...

Similarly, another respondent named Participant G recognised the struggle of the Asian catering sector. He realises that the restaurants and other catering sector are very much in problem due to shortage of skilled workers. Because of hard immigration rules, skilled workers cannot afford to come into the UK from Asian countries.

...The workforce is very much in problem. As we mainly deal with restaurants and catering sectors. These sectors are suffering because of the staff shortages of qualified chefs. They do not get any more staff from abroad which they used to in the past....

Because the wholesale shops supply their goods to the restaurants and other catering sectors, these shops also face the consequence of it. Thus, a combination of staff shortages along with price rises and other business issues has forced caterers to shut down their businesses. Besides, Brexit is another issue of why this industry is facing a challenging business situation. One of the industry experts thinks that Brexit is a disaster for the curry industry.

Natural calamities such as the coronavirus pandemic could be another reason for small and medium-sized firms to be in a difficult situation. Many shops had made changes in business hours. The catering and hospitality industries had to remain closed due to this global outbreak. It affects goods imported from other countries.

Furthermore, another industry expert outlined that they support Brexit because they were promised that it would be easier to attract skilled workers from the subcontinent. However, strict immigration policy makes it even harder for catering owners to hire staff from the Asian subcontinent.

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at YouGov 2020.

Figure 4-1: Where SMEs stand on Brexit?

Source: YouGov (2020)

YouGov surveyed ‘Why businesses are wary of Brexit uncertainty’ in January 2020. A total of 1,025 SMEs from various industries which include the manufacturing and retail sectors responded (YouGov, 2020). The report reveals that 39% of UK SMEs think that leaving the EU will leave them worse off. Ironically, a similar percentage of SMEs think that Brexit will not impact on their businesses.

Brexit will have a significant impact on the supply of goods. South Asian food wholesalers import goods from many European countries. The price of goods has been fluctuating as a result of Brexit uncertainty. Moreover, this has poorly impacted on businesses. Participant J thinks that Brexit is one of the reasons why businesses are struggling in the current period.

...At the moment, the Asian food shops are not doing very well because of the Brexit. We are getting out of the European Union. I would say this is one of the main reasons. The prices of the goods rise due to Brexit....

However, some participants still believe that demand for Asian food is growing.

“The demand for South Asian products is rising because of large communities move over here such as the Bangladeshi, Indian and Pakistani people living in the UK....

(Participant H, Managing Director)

A growing population creates a higher demand for food products and thus creates opportunities for food suppliers to generate revenue and profit. However, there are several other challenges that South Asian food SMEs encounter in their attempts to remain competitive. These are discussed in the following paragraphs.

4.3.2. Theme Two: The Challenges in the Market

The world of business is probably the most dynamic it has ever been (Amit and Zott, 2001; Farsi and Toghraee, 2014). Small and medium-sized food companies face many challenges, including financial constraints, low R&D expenditure, skilled workers, and insufficient market intelligence that compromises efforts to become competitive in the marketplace. SMEs face intense competition in the market. Increasing competition and differing markets present both opportunities and threats to food businesses. The critical challenges of South Asian food SMEs that emerged from the interview data are discussed below:

4.3.2.1. Intense Competition in the Market

South Asian food SMEs face fierce competition in the market as a consequence of pricing issues, oversupply and a lack of buying power.

The interview data illustrates some of the key challenges they face due to intense competition, for example:

There is a huge competition in the market at the moment. A lot of people actually have opened up businesses such as cash and carry shops and food distributions with delivery services. The most difficult problem we are facing at the moment is pricing issues and profit margins....

(Participant A, Account Manager)

.... Price is the biggest challenge that affects the profit margin. Competitors try to give the lowest price possible than what we are offering. Sometimes the price they offer to customers is so low that we cannot compete with it. So, we just get out of it. Thus, we keep losing the market...

(Participant D, Managing Director)

The biggest challenge we face is the price. Every South Asian-food shop tries to sell products with lower than the others. It is a kind of price-fight between South Asian food businesses in the market. Customers always look around for cheap price products. The big issue is the South

Asian food business is that there is no fixed price. If there were any price mark in South Asian food, then it would have been easy for shopkeepers to stick with one price margin. However, different competitors put different prices on specific products....

(Participant J, Managing Director)

Price is the only major issue at the moment. I think it's a global issue. Not just in our company, it's everywhere in any businesses. Customers want to buy cheap price products as long as the quality is not compromised....

(Participant G, Operation's Manager)

Pricing issues are one of the main challenges that South Asian food shops encounter in the marketplace. This is often a consequence of the number of cash and carry shops. Customers have plenty of alternatives to shop. Therefore, cutthroat pricing strategies are implemented by SMEs in order to compete with each other.

This is because of high competition in the market. Too many shops are around. The customers have too many choices to buy from. Around 20-30 years ago, there weren't too many suppliers in the market, and we were doing very well...

(Participant Q, Operation's Manager)

One of the interviewees highlighted the competition issue they encounter in the market.

.....There are 200 competitors alone in this area. We are all doing exactly the same kind of businesses. However, the packaging could be different and exporting products from different countries. The challenges are such that you have to compete with 200 shops here. Therefore, we have to offer reasonable prices to customers to compete with those 200 wholesale shops. We find it difficult to maintain the quality of products at reasonable prices.....

(Participant H, Managing Director)

These SMEs have low purchasing power compared to larger superstores around the UK. The bigger superstores have much stronger buying power since they buy in bulk, which means they can reduce the unit price of their products.

.....As I said before, the Multiples do give us a lot of competitions. The biggest issue for us that they have a buying power. If we can buy one truckload, they can buy hundreds of truckloads. In pricewise, they can obviously be more competitive.....

(Participant E, Managing Director)

4.3.2.2. *Supply Issues*

There are many other challenges that food SMEs face in attempting to be competitive in the market. These food SMEs often encounter supply issues. Most of the SMEs do not have their own supply chain, and so sometimes a product shortage arises which impacts on their competitiveness.

.....Another issue we are facing other than pricing is the availability of the products. We have to depend on our suppliers because we don't have our own supply chain and logistics. If the supplier stops a certain product, then the customer would go to other shops to get that specific product. So, this way we lose out customers sometimes....

(Participant N, General Manager)

4.3.2.3. *Operating Expenses*

Every company must pay operating costs to run a business, and wholesale food firms are no different. Many factors influence what food firms charge for their products and services. Marketing bills, labour costs, transportation rates, advertising and other costs are taken into account. The findings show that medium-sized food wholesale companies find it challenging to compete with larger as well as micro and small firms.

According to one of the account managers of a medium-sized wholesale company, medium-sized firms, compared to smaller firms, face huge overhead costs, which they must take into consideration when setting prices for products and services.

.....Because our company is a medium-sized food firm, it has huge overhead costs. Obviously, there has to be a minimum of profit margin you have to do per order to cover all the costs. Competitors, especially the micro and small wholesale shops, do not have high overhead costs and therefore, they sell products with a minimal profit margin. Thereby, these competitors are creating problems for us in the market. Because of that, we had to drop a lot of prices of our products below the cost prices. For that, the company is actually suffering at the moment. It has become really difficult to cover the costs to run the business.....

(Participant A, Account Manager)

Another respondent outlined the difficulties they have been encountering from micro shops overpricing competition as illustrated below:

.....At the moment we are facing a lot of problems from the small competitors. Because small companies do not have huge operating costs, they run the business with a few employees. They do not have a system in place, but we have a robust system in place to operate our business. We have a sales team, and we pay the wages. So, the operating costs of our company to run is a bit higher than our local competitors.....

(Participant L, Operation's Manager)

The data suggest that medium-sized food wholesale shops encounter many challenges in matching up prices with local micro and small firms due to their size and the operating costs.

4.3.2.4. *Customs Rules and Transportation Costs*

South Asian wholesale companies import goods from different parts of the world, and especially from the Asian subcontinents. Customs rules typically differ from one country to another, as one respondent noted:

...The customs tax and customs rules are also another big challenges we face in the market. The customs tax is not the same everywhere. In Europe, the customs rules may have been the same, but we also import from different parts of the world, such as the South Asian countries. The customs rules and tax are different. In some countries, the importing tax is comparably high. Therefore, the selling price of such products also varies....

(Participant H, Managing Director)

.....We get most of our products from Asian countries. Because it is quite far from where we are, therefore, the transportation costs are high, and it takes time to get supply from Asia....

(Participant J, Managing Director)

.....You know, these kinds of businesses are facing many challenges nowadays, because of the high prices in goods to import, the government tax, VAT.....

(Participant M, Operation's Manager)

Besides, food SMEs typically encounter other import barriers such as pesticide testing. The health authority routinely carries out pesticide testing on imported goods to reduce the risk to health.

.... We used to import rice from India. However, this product got now banned for pesticides problem. The whole of Europe banned Indian rice because of that issue. I think that has fallen us behind compare to our competitors.....

(Participant K, Managing Director)

.....We used to get 10 tons of fresh vegetables from Bangladesh every month. However, now it is not easy to import fresh vegetables from Bangladesh. The quality does not remain the same because of delay in transportation, the poor packaging, sometimes problems in getting the right products. There are many reasons why we stopped getting food supply from Bangladesh. The exporters do not match the health rules and regulations while exporting such goods from this country.....

(Participant P, Managing Director)

Analysis suggests that food SMEs are very concerned about issues with importing goods from international markets.

4.3.2.5. *The Local Authority*

Small and medium-sized organisations are often walloped by the strength of competition in the marketplace. The global economic crisis in 2008 and its attendant financial constraints meant that many previously successful SMEs failed. There is evidence that SMEs in most countries were confronted with a definite downturn in demand for goods and services during that time. A recent survey conducted on 500 SMEs in the UK by the Association of Chartered Certified Accountants in 2012 revealed that decisions made around parking and traffic restrictions by local councils deter customers from shopping in town centres (ACCA, 2012). SMEs also face issues such as red tape introduced by the hospitality industry around business premises and expensive health and safety risk assessments (Mirkovic, The Guardian, 2013).

One interviewee highlighted the issues in relation to premises. He pointed out that the local council are not particularly helpful.

.....We also have a problem with our building size. We have contacted the local council, but they are not very helpful in this matter. The building is not big enough to fulfil the purpose of the business. This is one of the business problems we are facing now....

(Participant I, Managing Director)

The interviewees suggested that responses from local councils to SMEs tend to be slow, which hinders business planning. One interviewee claimed that, for local businesses to thrive and survive, local authorities have a part to play.

4.3.2.6. *Lack of Marketing Knowledge*

Marketing is another paramount essential driver for SMEs who aspire to be competitive in the market. Food SMEs struggle to come up with the right marketing knowledge and skilled workers. Inadequate marketing knowledge creates marketing problems for SMEs. Appropriate marketing skills determine the company's sustainability in the marketplace.

.....We do not have a properly skilled marketing staff. We just cannot afford to invest in employing marketing staff solely. We already have limited resources, and we have to adjust to it.....

(Participant C, Operation's Manager)

A number of other issues hinder the ability of SMEs to be competitive in the marketplace. As such, companies implement innovative strategies around sustainability to survive in the market. The motives of South Asian food SMEs to become innovative in the marketplace are illustrated below.

The food industry is the largest manufacturing sector and the leading employer in the UK (Lefebvre et al., 2015; Kuhne, 2011; Menrad, 2004). The Asian food industry contributes £4billion per year to the British economy. However, the industry has faced significant challenges recently. Participant A, an account manager, stated that there are too many food wholesalers in the UK.

...There is a huge competition in the market at the moment. A lot of people actually open up businesses like and cash and carry's and food distributions with delivery services. The most challenging problem we are facing at the moment is pricing issues and profit margins.

As a result of the excess of food shops, pricing competition has become a significant issue for South Asian food SMEs seeking to remain competitive. Most respondents identified 'pricing' as a major business challenge in the marketplace. The findings illustrate that pricing is considered to be a major issue at the moment. Many respondents think that pricing is not just

an issue in the Asian food market, but it is, rather a global issue because of intense competition in the marketplace. This was explained by Participant Q (Operation's Manager) who noted:

...This is because of the high competition in the market. Too many shops are around. The customers have too many choices to buy from. Around 20-30 years ago, there weren't too many suppliers in the market, and we were doing very well....

Customers are increasingly concerned about food prices since food consumption comprises a significant share of household expenditure (Banterle et al., 2013). The pricing policy is a part of most firms' marketing activity, and it should be aligned with general managerial objectives (Panigyrakis, 1997).

SMEs have weak buying power compared to larger firms. Therefore, the price of the goods is comparably higher than at superstores.

Participant E (Managing Director) illustrated this in the following comment:

...As I said before, the Multiples do give us many competitions. The biggest issue for us that they have a buying power. If we can buy one truckload, they can buy hundreds of truckloads. In pricewise, they can obviously be more competitive.....

South Asian food SMEs also encounter challenges in supplying goods. Supply chain management has gradually become one means to enhance competitive strength. The ability to develop a healthy business relationship across company boundaries is a paramount issue when managing supply chains. Despite the substantial benefits of supply chain management, it is also evident that it involves costs, hazards, and many other challenges (Vaaland and Heidi, 2007). The majority of South Asian food SMEs do not have their supply chain and logistics, and therefore, they import goods from external suppliers. Sometimes supply does not fulfil demand. Participant N stated that South Asian food SMEs depend on their suppliers because they do not have their supply and logistics chain. He noted:

...We have to depend on our suppliers because we don't have our own supply chain and logistics. If the supplier stops a certain product, then the customer would go to other shops to get that specific product. So, this way we lose out customers sometimes...

It is clear that SMEs can lose its competitiveness with other SMEs and large shops.

High operating costs are another business challenge for SMEs in terms of their competitiveness. High operating costs are reflected in product prices. Food SMEs take market bills, labour costs, transportation costs, advertising costs and other essential expenses into

consideration in setting prices. The findings suggest that wholesale food companies, especially medium-sized firms, have comparably much higher operating costs than micro and small-sized firms. Participant A stated that his medium-sized South Asian food wholesale shop faces high overhead costs compared to micro and small enterprises:

Because our company is a medium-sized food firm, it has huge overhead costs. Obviously, there has to be a minimum of profit margin you have to make per order to cover all the costs. Competitors, especially the micro and small wholesale shops, do not have high overhead costs and therefore, they sell products with a minimal profit margin. Thereby, these competitors are creating problems for us in the market. Because of that, we had to drop a lot of prices of our products below the cost prices. For that, the company is actually suffering at the moment. It has become really difficult to cover the costs to run the business.

Micro and small-sized firms often sell their products with small profit margins which create problems for medium-sized companies. This is because medium-sized food firms have higher operating costs. Such companies encounter challenges as illustrated by Participant L (Managing Director) below.

They run the business with a few employees. They do not have a system in place, but we have a robust system in place to operate our business. We have a sales team, and we pay the wages. So, the operating costs of our company to run is a bit higher than our local competitors.

The findings indicate that medium-sized businesses not only compete with large supermarkets in terms of pricing but also compete with local micro and small wholesale shops.

Customs rules play a vital part in shaping the fortunes of food SMEs. Most products sold by these shops are imported from different countries. Customs rules and taxes vary from country to country. Sometimes they are higher when goods are imported from the subcontinent and other parts of the world. Participant H stated that the customs tax impacts on product pricing.

The customs tax is not the same everywhere. In Europe, the customs rules may have been the same, but we also import from different parts of the world, such as the South Asian countries. The custom rules and tax are different. In some countries, the importing tax is comparably high. Therefore, the selling price of such products also vary.

This issue was also illustrated by another interviewee, Participant J (Managing Director) who argued that they import most of their goods from Bangladesh, Indian, Pakistan and other Asian countries. The respondent illustrated, which is stated below:

We get most of our products from Asian countries. Because it is quite far from where we are, therefore, the transportation costs are high, and it takes time to get supply from Asia...

Other respondents also discussed the complications they faced caused by delays when importing from international markets. H&M Revenue and Customs (2014) pointed out that import delays are commonly cited issues amongst SMEs and intermediaries that carry both the associated costs and reputational impacts. A common complaint is that not knowing when imported goods will arrive means having to pay for lorries to wait at the port. SMEs often remain ignorant of the fact that imported goods have been delayed until their customers contact them. These customs issues have a significant impact on Asian food SMEs. The selling price of goods is often increased to cover importing duties and transportation costs.

There are some other issues that SMEs face. A survey conducted by ACCA in 2012 on 500 UK SMEs showed that parking and traffic restrictions levied by local councils deter customers from shopping in town centres (Mirkovic, 2013). In addition, the data suggest that local councils are not providing sufficient support for local businesses. One respondent, Participant I (Managing Director), detailed the issue as follows:

We also have a problem with our building size. We have contacted the local council, but they are not very helpful in this matter. The building is not big enough to fulfil the purpose of the business. This is one of the business problems we are encounter at the moment...

Market knowledge is an important factor for organisational success. Market knowledge refers to organised and structured information about the marketplace. Market knowledge competence is defined as the process that generates and integrates market knowledge. It is critical for SMEs' success (Bocconcelli et al., 2018; Bacon and Schneider, 2019). However, food SMEs struggle to obtain useful marketing knowledge because of scarce resources and the absence of skilled manpower. Inadequate market knowledge creates marketing problems for SMEs. Participant C (Operation's Manager) illustrated the issue as follows:

We don't have a properly skilled marketing staff. We just can't afford to invest in employing market staff solely. We already have limited resources, and we have to adjust with it...

This is consistent with Murphy's (2006) argument that inadequate marketing skills amongst owners create marketing problems for small business sectors. Strong management and marketing skills are identified as critical for business growth and success in the market.

The findings suggest that South Asian food SMEs lack sufficient marketing knowledge as a result of a lack of resource and capital. As such, SMEs spend very little on R&D. Therefore, firms are unable to understand customer demand.

4.3.3. Theme Three: Motives and Triggers for Open Innovation Implementation in the South Asian Food Wholesale SMEs

Food SMEs are more open to innovation, primarily for market-related motives. Organisations tend to take action in order to reach the desired goal. The main motives of South Asian food wholesalers to become innovative, which include the need to meet customer demands, and the ambition to quickly roll out their products to the broader marketplace.

One interviewee outlined the main motives behind the openness of South Asian food wholesale SMEs to innovative ideas:

.....The motives for innovation are to be competitive in the market. Understanding the market and customer demand is paramount to being competitive in the market. To fulfil customers' demands, we always introduce innovative ideas. We are more open to innovation in that process. We work with our suppliers as well as customers.....

(Participant B, Managing Director)

Analysis suggests that the main motive of embracing innovation is meeting customer demands. This statement corresponds with the work of Gans and Stern (2003), who stated that SMEs innovate to meet their customer needs effectively. In addition, Intense competition in the marketplace is another reason to be innovative. To overcome the challenges that South Asian food SMEs face in the market, they tend to implement innovative ideas in collaboration with suppliers, customers, and competitors.

.....Some of our suppliers buy from us as well as distribute to their network. So, it is not just the case of our suppliers coming to us and says we are going to deal with this because they have a broad scope of deliveries. We distribute our products through them as well, because they can cover a bigger area for us. We work hand in hand. It also cuts the cost. This is how we market the products quickly and efficiently....

(Participant C, Operation's Manager)

One interviewee highlighted the motives of South Asian food SMEs to work on innovation strategies and to work with suppliers to roll out their products more quickly and efficiently. In so doing the company not only distributes their goods quickly but also reduces its transportation costs.

The theme illustrates more about the motives for South Asian food wholesalers to implement innovative strategies.

SMEs are different compared to large organisations (Edwards et al., 2005). They are flexible in terms of decision making and quicker to react to changing customer demands (Vossen, 1998; Chesbrough et al., 2014). The triggers for open to innovation in the South Asian food wholesale SMEs are highlighted below:

.....It is the gap in the market. We usually have staff meetings, the adviser, the sells people in the market. These people find the gaps in the market and come up with ideas, right! So, knowing the gaps, we then come up with new plans. We just try to fulfil the gaps, and that's how we make customers not to go anywhere.....

(Participant G, Operation's Manager)

The motives to innovate come from perceived gaps in the market. SMEs routinely try to bridge gaps in the market, which makes them more competitive.

Innovative ideas derive from everywhere. The smallness of SMEs makes them able to make decisions quickly. SMEs face limitations in terms of their choice of materials, human resources, and capital. Therefore, they continuously look for new ideas to challenge their competitors. Innovative ideas sometimes come from customers, as the following quote underscores.

.....It comes from customer feedback. Obviously, we have one to one talk on the phone every week. We listen to our customers and pull all together and come up with an idea to implement.....

(Participant A, Account Manager)

A strong relationship with customers that responds to their suggestions helps SMEs to become more competitive by implementing innovative ideas. South Asian food SME managers in this sample talk to their customers over the phone and get feedback on the goods and service they provide. It can, therefore, be argued that one of the triggers of innovation is customer feedback.

In addition, some interviewees identified that the triggers for innovation come from everywhere.

.... It comes from everywhere. We encourage our employees to speak to our customers when they go to deliver the products. It builds a relationship with our customers and the level of confidence if something that we do not have, the employee will discuss with the customers asking ok! Where do you normally get it from, what kind of price point do you get it from and what volumes you are buying? Our employees bring the information across to us in the office and say right! This is what my customers are looking for, help them to support. We then go to the market get to not just our priority products, but even our competitor's products. We continuously are working closely with our customers to fulfil their needs. We do not want to become a market follower; we want to become the market leader....

(Participant C, Operation's Manager)

Sometimes the triggers of innovation come from advancements in technology. Technology makes the work environment easy and saves time.

I remember we had a manual till in our shop. For every price, we had to put it in manually. By the grace of the advanced technology, the scanning system is introduced in the store. We save times and customers are happier with the service they are getting it from us...

(Participant K, Managing Director)

Employees and senior managers play a crucial role in implementing new ideas by talking directly with customers. They come up with new ideas and strategies based on customer feedback and market knowledge. Understanding market demand plays a significant role in the process of innovation in the marketplace, as illustrated below:

.... We take ideas from our employees and senior managers to be competitive in the market. Our director sometimes comes and give some ideas to apply to our store so we can improve our service and thereby get more customers.

(Participant N, General Manager)

Openness to innovation is motivated by a desire to stand out and become more competitive. This is how food SMEs maintain its sustainability in the competitive market.

Sometimes these small and medium-sized firms collaborate with their suppliers to distribute products across larger areas. This is one of the benefits of working with suppliers to be efficient and cost-effective. This eases some of the costs associated with delivering goods to customers.

It can be said that the motivation for innovation in organisations is to understand market demand. Taatila et al. (2006) advocated that an innovative idea is generated by a social network which ‘concentrates’ its network knowledge via one or more central people. Furthermore, previous studies confirm that collective innovation is worth pursuing when competing based on innovation.

SMEs are different from large organisations (Edwards et al., 2005). SMEs are more flexible in their decision-making processes and quicker when it comes to responding to and meeting customer demands. The triggers to innovate in South Asian food SMEs mainly emanate from gaps in the market. SMEs identify gaps through staff, and through sales teams who deliver goods to restaurants, small shops, and takeaways. They gather information about products by directly interacting with customers while delivering goods. Based on this process, SMEs know about market gaps and come up with ideas to bridge gaps in the market.

In addition, a healthy relationship with customers and suppliers also guides SMEs in terms of their products, processes and service innovations. Customers and suppliers play a significant role in helping SMEs to gather market information. They are the primary sources of SME intelligence (mainly South Asian food SMEs) when it comes to introducing new ideas into their businesses and thus gaining a competitive foothold. This view corresponds with Bigliardi and Galati (2013), who stated that consumers and suppliers play a vital role as a source of information, offering the opportunity to gain knowledge about competitors.

The respondents emphasised that the triggers for innovation in SMEs also come from customer feedback. Analysis suggests that the managers of Asian food SMEs talk to their customers and get feedback on their products and services, and then act upon it. The delivery drivers also play a significant role in this context, as confirmed by Participant C (Operation’s Manager) who had this to say:

We encourage our employees to speak to our customers when they go to deliver the products. It builds a relationship with our customers and the level of confidence if something that we don’t have, the employee will discuss with the customers asking ok! Where do you normally get it from, what kind of price point do you get it from and what volumes you are buying? Our employees bring the information across to us in the office and say right! This is what my

customers are looking for, help them to support. We then go to the market get not just our priority products, but even our competitor's products. We continuously are working closely with our customers to fulfil their need. We don't want to become a market follower; we want to become the market leader.

Each employee is, therefore, involved in innovation. Each gathers information about products and services to gain as much information as possible about products which are not successful.

This is how they fulfil customer demand to become a market leader.

Asian food wholesale shops are very agile in meeting customers' demand. They take on board creative ideas and knowledge from all employees. Furthermore, the technological advancements may also play a pivotal role in for triggering the innovation system in SMEs. Epos online ordering systems have revolutionised the process of taking orders. Also, the app (Application system) is a new edition to local wholesale shops for customers ordering goods in advance. The introduction of electronic tills has improved service in Asian food SMEs. Participant K (Managing Director) explained that electronic tills and scanning systems reduce the time it takes to serve customers:

..I remember we had a manual till in our shop. For every price, we had to put it in manually. By the grace of the advanced technology, the scanning system is introduced in the store. We save times and customers are happier with the service they are getting it from us...

4.3.4. Theme Four: Open Innovation Strategies to Overcome Business Challenges

The analysis identified several business challenges faced by Asian food wholesalers. Food SMEs encounter many issues, including competitive markets, evolving customer demands, pricing issues, shortened product life cycles and market competitiveness. To overcome such barriers, Asian food SMEs implement many innovative ideas. Open innovation is not a new concept for the food industry. Food firms collaborate with suppliers, customers and sometimes with competitors to innovate and enhance their competitiveness. Open innovation implementation in SMEs has arisen as a result of effective collaborative approaches. SMEs collaborate with suppliers, customers, intermediaries and sometimes with competitors.

Several innovative measures are implemented by Asian food SMEs in order to overcome such business challenges in the marketplace. These measures are discussed below. Some Asian SMEs implement unique strategies which are unrivalled, and which set them apart from competitors.

4.3.4.1. *Infrastructural Changes*

Asian food SMEs should make structural changes to overcome business challenges in order to become more competitive. Both managers and business experts emphasise the central role of infrastructural changes that are required in Asian food SMEs. Otherwise, the situation would be worse than it is now, as illustrated below:

.....I think this industry needs a big change in the market. It needs modernisation in terms of doing businesses. The technological utilisation should need to be up to the mark so that the younger generations can order using online platforms. A positive marketing strategy needs to be applied. The most important thing is diversifying or adopting mixed cuisines in Asian food. This would give the industry a competitive advantage....

(Mr X, Industry Expert)

.....Market diversification is important at the moment. We have to make some infrastructural changes to be competitive in the market. Rather than concentrating on just Indian cuisine, we could go on different kind of restaurants.....

(Participant A, Account Manager)

Asian food SMEs should, therefore, diversify their product range and include different cuisines. In addition, technological utilisation in food SMEs should be given priority. Furthermore, a positive marketing strategy is also essential to the process of overcoming these business challenges.

...The business strategy should always be customer focus strategy. I have worked in cash and carry shops. I have worked for IT companies. I have worked for a waste recycling company. You have always got to focus on customers. Without customers, there is no business....

(Participant C, Operation's Manager)

The findings suggest that the Asian food industry must undergo infrastructural changes to enhance competitiveness. The managing directors of Asian food wholesale shops and business experts emphasise that infrastructural changes are required in the Asian food industry, or the hostile environment will become worse. Mr X, an industry expert illustrated the need for change in the Asian food trade. He emphasised that modernisation and the implementation of technology are essential in this regard. As part of this process, young customers can be attracted

to the South Asian food sector. The younger generation can use online platforms to order food. This is what he had to say:

...I think this industry needs a big change in the market. It needs modernisation in terms of doing businesses. The technological utilisation should need to be up to the mark so that the younger generations can order using online platforms...

This finding resonates with research by Avermaete and Viaene (2002) who suggest that the food industry should undertake innovative processes to improve product quality, expand consumer confidence and encourage modernisation. Online platforms can also be used for marketing purposes, for instance, using social media to advertise products and services. The South Asian food industry must look beyond its traditional marketing strategy. In addition, the owners and directors should have a positive attitude towards change. South Asian food wholesalers should diversify its product offer to enhance their competitiveness. Mr X also illustrated the importance of diversification.

..The most important thing is diversifying or adopting mixed cuisines in Asian food. This would give the industry a competitive advantage.

Participant A also highlighted the importance of market diversification. He suggested the infrastructural changes for enhancing competitiveness in the market. He emphasised that South Asian restaurateurs should also encircle their tradition cuisine with other different cuisines to be diversified.

The findings underscore the importance of both market and product diversification to enhance the competitiveness of South Asian food SME wholesalers. Diversification is crucial element of growth. Wholesale shops should not just concentrate on their traditional product range but should include other cuisines. Product diversification creates the opportunity to develop business by growing sales revenue from existing customers or opening out new avenues to entirely new demographics.

Visnjic et al. (2016) also highlighted the importance of market diversification, suggesting that entering into new markets can create learning and operating advantages by making use of cumulative knowledge from existing markets. Furthermore, product diversification is an important aspect of competitiveness in the food sector which means businesses can meet consumer demands in terms of quality and nutrition (Nath et al., 2010; Riganelli and Marchini, 2017).

Arguably, a positive business strategy is also important for overcoming such business challenges. Participant C (Operation's Manager) thinks that a business strategy should always be customer centric. The main priority should be satisfying customers. He believes that without customers, there is no business.

This resonates with Awaad et al. (2013) study that customer satisfaction is the main priority to any businesses. Companies should need to concentrate on how to fulfil the demand of customers. It also includes after-sale services, product support, product information and product promises. The company should also think about the quality and costs of the products. The quality is a competitive weapon to be competitive in the market. Quality products stimulate competitiveness. The company should compete with the competitors and beat the price of the products in the market. This can be happened by the intense supervision of labour and tight cost control. Product differentiation is also vital to compete in the market. In addition, flexibility is another significant factor for competitiveness. Firms should be mastering the changes and meeting any uncertainty arise in the market while fulfilling customer's demand.

4.3.4.2. *Food Packaging Innovation*

Approaches to packaging have changed in the Asian food industry, and modern, sophisticated packaging systems now add value to products, as illustrated below:

.... There is a big change in packaging nowadays. We import the packaging products from within the UK and some European countries and sell them to our customers. The younger generations, like the packaging items...

(Participant P, Managing Director)

.... We tried to see what the current trend is in the market. There is an influx of students in the area, and we tried to bring in the Asian food products that are ready meals...

(Participant E, Managing Director)

....The industry should also include some vegan items in their product range....

(Mr X, Industry Expert)

Packaging innovations have made a substantial impact on food SMEs. Many companies receive positive feedback from their customers in response to this subtle innovation process. Furthermore, Asian food wholesale and retail shops have improved their product quality by

including product information on new packaged goods, which is relatively recent. The perishable goods used to be sold without sophisticated product packaging systems. However, now the introduction of innovative product packaging system makes products look elegant. Furthermore, investing in more vegetarian and vegan items could also result in a more significant competitive advantage.

.... We have introduced the product labelling in every single item...

(Participant P, Managing Director)

Most South Asian food wholesalers and retailers sell canned foods, and this reflects their popularity. Canned food reduces waste and has a long shelf life. This is especially the case with vegetables which are more nutritious than frozen, packaged goods.

.....Canned foods are easy to purchase. It reduces food waste as it comes in various sizes. Canned foods have been used for many years. Canned foods can easily keep the freshness and nutrients locked in for longer than usual fresh foods....

(Participant S, General Manager)

It is clear that many Asian food wholesale companies collaborate with their suppliers in terms of food packaging innovation.

Innovation is recognised as making an important contribution to organisational success. Innovation is often driven by external pressures such as customer demands, competition, deregulation, and scarce resources (Baregheh et al., 2012; Damanpour, 2009). The food industry is considered the most significant manufacturing contributor, both in terms of economic output and employment (Avermaete, 2002; Menrad, 2004; Traill, 1998). The importance of innovation is evident for firms in this sector. They play a pivotal role in sustaining and enhancing competitiveness (Capitanio et al., 2010; Rama and Von Tunzelmann, 2008). Asian food wholesalers have demonstrated innovation through product packaging. Asian food firms imported a new packaging product to attract younger customers. The introduction of new packaging systems was successful, as suggested by Participant P (a Managing Director).

There is a big change in packaging nowadays. We import the packaging products from within the UK and some European countries and sell it to our customers. The younger generations like the packaging items.

The introduction of product labelling has had a significant positive impact on products. Wholesalers have received positive responses from customers in this sense. A lot of South Asian loose fruits and vegetables are used in cooking such as citrus fruits called 'shatkora' Boro and other vegetables, for instance, Kachur Mukhi, Kochur Mura, Chichinga, Parwal, Korola and so forth. These fruits and vegetables used to sell loose with no packaging.

However, recently these items are packaged and labelled in a sophisticated manner which gives customers a sense of product knowledge. These food items are preserved and packaged in a manner that they last longer than the loose items would usually have lasted. This is what he had to say on the introduction of product labelling in Asian food.

We have introduced the product labelling in every single item with the expiry date on which brings positive responses.

Many participants collaborate with their suppliers in terms of food packaging and labelling systems. Furthermore, understanding the current trends and demands in the market could give both wholesalers and retailers a competitive advantage. Participant E (a Managing Director) had this to say:

We tried to see what the current trend is in the market. There is an influx of students in the area, and we tried to bring in the Asian food products that are ready meals.

Many participants realised the centrality of current market trends and the necessity for readymade cooked food to attract university students. The introduction of canned food has created a positive impact on the product range. Canned food, especially vegetables and fruits are long-lasting. They are very easy to store and have a long shelf life. Participant S (General Manager) illustrated the convenience of canned food as follows:

Canned foods are easy to purchase. It reduces food waste as it comes in various sizes. Canned foods have been used for many years. Canned foods can easily keep the freshness and nutrients locked in for longer than usual fresh foods.

Tinned foods are often considered less nutritious than fresh and frozen foods, but this is not always the case according to diet experts (Roberts, 2019).

A survey was conducted on 2000 adults by YouGov in 2016, and it found that 1 in 3 people throw away food regularly because it has reached its expiry date. The study also found that 53% of the sample believe that buying tinned food reduces waste (YouGov, 2016).

4.3.4.3. *Branded Products and Stock Control*

Asian food SMEs could expand their products ranges and stock up on branded goods to satisfy customers looking to buy all their groceries from one supplier.

.....We can improve our service by introducing more products in the business. Even if we serve the same customers with a variety of new products, then the total sales revenue will increase; hence the profit margin will increase....

(Participant F, Managing Director)

.....We are developing our own branded products such as rice, oil, tomato sauce items. If we can improve our own branded products, then we can have a monopoly on the market. If the customer wants a particular product, then they have to come for this product as they have no choice....

(Participant D, Managing Director)

This finding suggests that developing own-brand products could give SMEs a monopoly in the market, and competitive advantage.

....All we can do is to stock up more products, stock up exclusive branded products so that the other competitors cannot get hold of it. If you are aware of your strengths and weaknesses, I think you can stay in the market for a long time....

(Participant G, Operation's Manager)

Stock control is also vital for SMEs. Finding the right balance in terms of stock is necessary. The problem with inventory is that sometimes too little stock may result in more inferior distribution. Keeping too much stock means investing much money unnecessarily.

....I would say the stock control system can be improved if we use the system in place by using our stock management system, which we currently do not do. So, I think that would be beneficial for the company a lot. We will have fewer losses, less expired products on our shelves. We don't overstock so that our money is not held in stock. It will be a better stock turnover. I think that's one of the main key things in business. If you are monitoring the stock, then you are not understocking or overstocking. It's just the right amount of stock....

(Participant E, Managing Director)

.....I will keep a limited stock of goods. I make sure the only quality of products is kept in the stock.....

(Participant H, Managing Director)

It is clear that inventory management is of paramount importance, especially in the food industry. The right amount of stock reduces loss and maintains quality standards.

Brands are the symbols of organisations and the identity of a company. Branding is crucial for SMEs, especially, the food sector because it allows organisations to create a self-image. Knox and Bickerton (2003) stated that the role of branding is to differentiate a product in a customer's mind. Although branding is a critical marketing strategy for organisations, the concept has received very little attention in the context of SMEs (Krake, 2005). This is due to the lack of SMEs' financial resources. The respondents believe that branding could enhance competitiveness in markets. SMEs could expand their product ranges and develop their own branded products as well as other renowned branded items.

In this way, wholesale firms can satisfy customers. Customers prefer to buy what they need from a single provider. Participant D (a Managing Director) believes that developing a brand identity could potentially lead to a monopoly in the market.

We are developing our own branded products such as rice, oil, tomato sauce items. If we can improve our own branded products, then we can have a monopoly on the market. If the customer wants a particular product, then they have to come for this product as they have no choice.

This will not only allow SMEs to increase their product range but could also increase the product mix. By having a broader product range on the shelf, a competitive barrier could be created in the marketplace. Participant G (Operation's Manager) believes that stocking up exclusive branded products and broad product lines could create a competitive advantage.

All we can do is to stock up more products, stock up exclusive branded products so that the other competitors cannot get hold of it.

SMEs must not only stock up on shelf products. They must also consider what counts as the right amount of stock. Stock control systems or inventory management systems are essential in the overall performance of a business, regardless of its size. Inventory management or stock control is not just vital for business operations. It also contributes to customer satisfaction (Stevenson et al., 2014). Participant E (Managing Director) suggested that the right level of inventory management is necessary to reduce losses:

I'd say the stock control system could be improved if we use the system in place by using our stock management system, which we currently do not do. So, I think that would be beneficial

for the company a lot. We will have fewer losses, fewer expired products on our shelves. We don't overstock so that our money is not held in stock. It will be a better stock turnover. I think that is one of the main key things in business. If you monitor the inventory, you are not understocking or overstocking. It's just the right amount of stock.

Mwangi and Nyambura (2015) suggest that inventory management plays a significant role in organisations as unproductive inventory systems will lead to delivery delays, production disorganisation or loss of customers and sales. Participant H (a Managing Director) suggested that stocking the right amount of quality products can lead to a better outcome, as illustrated below:

I'll keep a limited stock of goods. I make sure the only quality of products is kept in the stock.

These findings are consistent with Widyastitu et al. (2018) who suggest that raw materials used by food sectors cannot be stored as they tend to spoil, and therefore quality cannot be maintained. Products such as perishable goods must be stored correctly. Micro and SMEs have rarely done anything about this due to a lack of knowledge about managing inventory. Suratman et al. (2013) argue that raw material inventories are rarely implemented amongst food and beverage SMEs. Furthermore, Sunday and Joseph (2017) believe that inventory management affects financial performance, so organisations ought to maintain accurate inventory levels to improve profitability and reduce losses.

4.3.4.4. Open Innovation with Customer Involvement

The turbulence within competitive markets necessitates the adoption of several responsive approaches. Increasing uncertainty and intense competition force companies to diversify and innovate. Since SMEs lack resources and capabilities, they are unable to spend much on research and development. Therefore, inside out innovation strategies for Asian food SMEs are productive, for example, obtaining customer feedback. The interview excerpts below illustrate how Asian food SMEs obtain innovative ideas from customers.

.... We are open to innovation in our business. We do get customer feedback on a regular basis. We gather feedback from our salespeople as they are the main source of collecting feedback from customers. We take every single feedback seriously regardless of whether it is positive or negative. Let me give an example while delivering products; we're told that some of the boxes were broken. So, they accepted the goods, but they were not happy. What we did in return, we went there again and changed the boxes. These are the quick responses we do, and it is normal

practice for any ordinary person. We always make sure that the quality of products and services must not be compromised. By doing this, customers not only feel happy, but they feel secure of the money they have used.....

(Participant G, Operation's Manager)

...We ask for customer opinions about whether they are happy with the products and services they are getting from us. We reflect on their feedback and try to improve our business accordingly. If we get any complaints from our clients regarding our goods, we straightaway reflect on that and replace the product. We do not want to compromise the quality we have been maintaining over the years...

(Participant F, Managing Director)

....We obviously get customer feedback to improve our products and services. It is the most common form open innovation strategy we implement to be competitive in the market. Whatever constructive suggestions we get from our customers on our products and services, we obviously work on that to improve the business.....

(Participant J, Managing Director)

Analysis suggests that customer feedback is an essential aspect of food SMEs when it comes to managing innovation. Such intelligence allows food firms to understand what and how end-users want their particular products. Such knowledge means that businesses can satisfy customer demand based on feedback.

In today's fast-moving business environment, innovation is of paramount interest. Intense competition and uncertainty in the marketplace force organisations to innovate. Managing uncertainty can be measured as a core practice of successful innovation management. Innovation relies on a strong understanding of the business and its customers. Creating value for customers allows companies to create competitive advantage. Since SMEs have limited resources and capabilities, they are unable to invest in R&D.

Therefore, inbound, open innovation such as gathering ideas and knowledge from customer feedback is one form of open innovation that South Asian food wholesale SMEs implement. The findings suggest that South Asian food wholesalers gather ideas in relation to product and service development by interacting with customers. This statement corresponds with Saldanha et al. (2017) work, stating that gathering customer information enables a firm to recognise what customers want in their products. Customer feedback is a common source of generating

innovative ideas and knowledge for South Asian food micro and SMEs. One respondent, Participant G (Operation's Manager) noted:

We are open to innovation in our business. We do get customer feedback on a regular basis. We gather feedback from our salespeople as they are the main source of collecting feedback from customers. We take every single feedback seriously regardless of whether it's positive or negative.

Customer and user domains usually provide ample information about demand. Lusch and Vargo (2006) stated that customers play significant roles in different innovation and value creation activities, for example, their involvement at the product design stage. This involvement assists firms to have better knowledge about customer desires. Customers are active partners in both product development and service improvements. In von Hippel's (1978) study, the 'customer-active' paradigm, he introduces highlights that customer can be active participants in new product development processes, and these can be transmitted to manufacturers. Furthermore, Wecht and Baloh (2006) suggest that thoroughly executed customer integration in product development can be beneficial for innovative performance. Participant F (a Managing Director) also outlined the importance of customer interactions to improve products and services.

..We ask for customer opinions about whether they are happy with the products and services they are getting from us. We reflect on their feedback and try to improve our business accordingly. If we get any complaints from our clients regarding our goods, we straightaway reflect on that and replace the product. We don't want to compromise the quality we have been maintaining over the years...

Customer feedback is critical, especially for food SMEs. Companies can attain rich information about products which can be applied in the innovation process. This notion corresponds with Presenza et al. (2016) who stated that customers are the most important external source for innovation as they provide valuable information. Customer satisfaction is the main priority for SMEs, which enhance competitiveness. Therefore, understanding customer needs can only be acknowledged by interacting with customers. As Participant J (a Managing Director) pointed out, customer feedback improves products and services.

We obviously get customer feedback to improve our products and services. It is the most common form open innovation strategy we implement to be competitive in the market. Whatever constructive suggestions we get from our customers on our products and services, we obviously work on that to improve the business.

Collaboration with customers can improve SMEs ability to fulfil customer needs. It also helps SMEs to keep up with their competitors (Berends et al., 2014). It is clear that customers play a significant role in innovation processes, whether this is related to product or service innovation in South Asian food wholesale SMEs. However, SMEs also need to have the resources and capacity to implement the innovation.

4.3.4.5. *Open Innovation with Suppliers*

Quality is an important issue in the food industry. A number of quality assurance principles are required for food businesses to gain a competitive advantage in the market. Asian food wholesale shops are keen to provide quality food with exceptional service.

.....We are based on quality and service. So, as long as we maintain these things generally, we will be okay. We position ourselves as to where we have got better quality products, better services than our competitors...

(Participant B, Managing Director)

The interviewee also outlined that they form partnerships with specific suppliers to import goods which are not sold anywhere else. In this sense, they remain competitive by creating barriers to their competitors.

.... We are quite simple and niche. Regarding the other things we do, we create barriers in the market by partnerships with suppliers. So, we might have one supplier that the biggest in the market. We make an agreement with this supplier which they are not allowed to supply any other wholesalers. That enables us to control a certain aspect of the market. So, we do that with certain products. We've got better relationships with suppliers. They are not allowed to supply anyone else in the UK except for us....

(Participant B, Managing Director)

.... I think networking and collaborating with suppliers helps gain better knowledge and better understanding since SMEs have lack of resources and skilled workers. We do a lot of collaboration with our suppliers such as KTC, NATCO and so on. They support us, and we support them. It's a reciprocal relationship between us.....

(Participant E, Managing Director)

The above excerpts suggest that some South Asian food wholesale SMEs form partnerships with certain suppliers to create competitive barriers. In addition, collaborating with suppliers helps businesses to attain better knowledge about current market demands. Furthermore, these Asian food SMEs are always keen to ensure better quality products by working with their partners.

.... We manage our company in a very sincere manner. We are representing high-quality products at favourable prices. We are always maintaining quality assurance control. We fulfil our customers' demand and be innovative in the market. We collaborate with our suppliers to give the best quality food to our customers. We maintain food safety and management control systems. We have been working with our partners for better quality products and high-quality packaging....

(Participant R, Account Manager)

..We always focus on thriving and be the leader in the market. Therefore, innovation is a must to be competitive and business sustainability. Our main focus is to give our clients the best price possible as we understand our client's need and expectations. We understand how important it is for you to keep your prices competitive and maximise your margins, so we work hard to keep our prices low – through negotiation with suppliers, keeping our own overheads down, and a variety of special offers. So, we negotiate with our suppliers in way that we can buy from them at certain amount at a certain price. We also keep our overheads checked minimising unnecessary expenses.....

(Participant E, Managing Director)

The increasing number of complexities in relation to innovation processes has led food SMEs towards a greater dependency on interactions with external sources within networks (Edwards et al., 2005; Zeng et al., 2010). Sharing knowledge is a prerequisite for learning and consequently for innovation (Lundvall et al., 2002). In food SMEs, quality assurance is an essential component of sustainability. To improve and maintain quality, food SMEs have always focussed on innovative ideas and knowledge. However, innovation is not entirely based on R&D in the food industry. Instead, it involves a learning process and interactions between different parties.

SMEs face many internal problems such as limited resources, and insufficient skilled manpower which results in limited organisational capability and a lack of any strategic vision (Avermaete et al., 2003; Scozzi et al., 2005). Therefore, SMEs collaborate with suppliers and

other external parties to create innovation processes. The findings suggest that Asian food SMEs collaborate with suppliers to enhance their competitiveness in the market. Participant E (a Managing Director) noted:

I think networking and collaborating with suppliers helps gain better knowledge and better understanding since SMEs are lack in resources and skilled workers. We do a lot of collaboration with our suppliers such as KTC, NATCO and so on. They support us, and we support them. It's a reciprocal relationship between us.

In addition, the findings confirm that Asian food wholesalers sometimes build partnership agreements with suppliers to create competitive barriers, as illustrated by Participant B (a Managing Director).

We create barriers in the market by a partnership with suppliers. So, we might have one supplier that the biggest in the market. We make an agreement with this supplier which they are not allowed to supply any other wholesalers. That enables us to control a certain aspect of the market. So, we do that with certain products. We've got a better relationship with suppliers. They are not allowed to supply anyone else in the UK except for us.

The importance of networking, knowledge-sharing and collaboration with suppliers was acknowledged by all participants. Companies can gain a competitive advantage by establishing relationships and long-term collaborations with suppliers. In collaborating with external sources, SMEs can attain better knowledge about customer demands. Furthermore, South Asian food SMEs are keen to ensure better quality products by working with external partners, as Participant R (Account Manager) explains:

We manage our company in a very sincere manner. We are representing high-quality products at a favourable price. We are always maintaining quality assurance control. We fulfil our customers' demand and be innovative in the market. We collaborate with our suppliers to give the best quality food to our customers. We maintain food safety and management control systems. We have been working with our partners for better quality products and high-quality packaging....

Asian food SMEs collaborate and build partnerships with suppliers to create product development and improve services. This study results support the recent study of Theyel (2013) as he revealed that SMEs are more innovative when they collaborate with suppliers for product development. Grönlund et al. (2010) study stated that external collaboration activities with other partners have been ongoing since innovation was introduced. The collaboration is a

broader concept of open innovation that helps to leverage external source of knowledge to drive internal growth. Through the collaborative open innovation approach, these food firms develop existing products and packaging systems.

4.3.4.6. *Open Innovation and Employee Involvement*

Asian food SMEs receive innovative ideas from experienced employees. They have weekly and monthly meetings with senior staff to identify if anything is needed to improve their products and services.

...So, we always try to improve our business for the competitiveness in the market. We always take on board whatever customers say, what the staff members say. We always have a staff meeting where we discuss all sorts of business issue. We try to keep everyone happy. If you don't do that, you lose your customers, and you lose your staff as well. It's a big thing. So, you have to listen to your customers and staff...

(Participant Q, Operation's Manager)

It is clear that South Asian food wholesale SMEs are open to innovation. Innovative ideas do not just come from customers, suppliers or competitors. Employees also play an integral part in implementing innovation. This is a form of knowledge sharing whereby experienced employees drive competitiveness.

Employees play a significant role in implementing innovation in Asian food SMEs. Innovation is about the successful exploitation of ideas and knowledge (Pittaway et al., 2004). Ideas are generated from all sorts of external partners. Asian food SMEs are often inspired by employees. Many respondents noted that weekly and monthly meetings with employees generate innovative ideas. Participant Q (Operation's Manager) stated that they are always keen to improve products and services to remain competitive in the marketplace. He also added that the organisation takes on board whatever both customers and employees say. This is what he had to say:

So, we always try to improve our business for the competitiveness in the market. We always take on board whatever customers say, what the staff members say. We always have a staff meeting where we discuss all sorts of business issue. We try to keep everyone happy. If you don't do that, you lose your customers, and you lose your staff as well. It's a big thing. So, you have to listen to your customers and staff.

Through regular interactions with employees, food SMEs can reduce the time it takes to create innovative ideas and implement strategies rapidly. All participants believe that innovative ideas do not just emanate from customers, suppliers, and competitors, but also employees who play an integral part in generating ideas. Employees share their valuable knowledge and experiences in the innovation process. Asian food SMEs are very flexible and apply intra-organisational innovation platforms within their innovation systems. This aligns with Bergendahl & Magnusson's (2014) study who argue that collaborative approaches with employees, customers and suppliers benefit the innovation platform as they combine different types of knowledge sets for better performance.

4.3.4.7. *Technological Usage*

Asian food SMEs routinely use technology to improve their services. According to the interview participants, the utilisation of technology has streamlined services by minimising human error, as illustrated below:

.... We have facilities for digital answer machines. We digitalised everything. There are fewer mistakes in taking customer's order. We have a computerized system. We've tried to cut out of the mistakes by using computers. We try to minimize human mistakes as much as possible. So, that's the only way we can really satisfy our customers....

(Participant B, Managing Director)

Some firms use EPOS (Electronic point of sale) systems to calculate sales and prepare invoices for customers.

....We have been using EPOS for a few years now, and it's very efficient and cost-effective....

(Participant O, Operation's Manager)

Furthermore, the warehouse manager outlined that they have collaborated with similar firms and have used their online ordering systems to provide better service, as illustrated below:

...We have an online ordering system using the website. This is our subsidiary company in which people can order online to get it delivered at their doorsteps. We do a free delivery service at a minimum amount of goods....

(Participant Q, Operation's Manager)

Some firms developed apps to improve service. One of the Asian wholesale firms developed an app system to take customer orders.

.... We used to call customers to get their orders. We had to make the invoices manually. But now, from the last three years, we have developed an app and get the customers to order through the app. The customer can log in on their own account, and they can go through the whole products' catalogue and make their own order. It saves us at least about 20 minutes on per customers. The customers are now pleased....

(Participant K, Managing Director)

Some Asian food SMEs have also imitated supermarket customer service systems. SMEs have, for example, introduced self-checkout services to scale up the pace of service in shopping. In addition, some have introduced PDQ machines to take payments. Other medium-sized firms have already introduced larger shopping trolleys and spacious car parks, emulating larger supermarkets.

...We used to have fewer tills to serve customers, but now we have opened more tills and self-service tills to reduce the queue up....

(Participant N, General Manager)

South Asian food SMEs are therefore slowly, but surely introducing technology to improve the quality of their service. Some managers and directors are collaborating with suppliers and other subsidiary firms to implement innovation to drive their competitiveness in the marketplace.

Innovation is the cornerstone of a successful business. Food firms face many business challenges and must meet customer demands while coping with shortened product life cycles, fierce competition, and cluttered retail shelf-space (Bellairs, 2010; Saguy and Sirotinskaya, 2014). Intense competition, a lack of skilled manpower, pricing issues, evolving customer demands, shortened product life cycles and Brexit are amongst the key challenges. To overcome these business challenges and enhance competitiveness, Asian food SMEs have adopted many innovative strategies. Collaborating with customers, suppliers, and competitors, and sharing knowledge are some of the innovations used to overcome such business challenges.

Technology plays a crucial role in developing any innovation system. Technological progress is one of the theoretically accepted measures applied to diminish the frontier barriers of economy, since it increases productivity and efficiency. The findings suggest that Asian food SMEs apply technology to improve their services. The participants emphasised the usefulness of technological applications in their businesses to provide seamless services. Participant B (a Managing Director) illustrated how replacing manual operations with computerised systems reduced human error.

We have facilities for digital answer machines. We digitalised everything. There are fewer mistakes in taking customer's order. We have a computerized system. We have tried to cut out of the mistakes by using computers. We try to minimize human mistakes as much as possible. So, that's the only way we can really satisfy our customers.

Advancements in Technology make businesses more efficient, productive, and apt to make fewer mistakes. In recent years, many SMEs have realised the importance of the internet for customer relationships by harnessing interactivity. Many marketing professionals now believe that interactivity is critical to forging relationships with customers. There are many benefits of using internet marketing. Online content involves lowering the cost of exchanging information. This enables a broader audience to be reached by SMEs (Sparkes and Thomas, 2001).

The findings also underscore the importance of online platforms for recording orders. Some Asian food companies use Electronic Point of Sale Digital Systems (EPOS). This is a computerised system that is used in shops, restaurants, and other retail outlets to calculate the amount owed by customers and to prepare invoices. It is simple and more cost-effective than traditional till systems. In addition, it boosts staff efficiency and monitors sales and inventory management. Participant O (Operation's Manager) stated the benefits of using EPOS:

We have been using EPOS for a few years now, and it's very efficient and cost-effective.

There are various electronic till systems available in the market such as izettle and many more for small and medium-sized wholesale and retail shops. Choosing the appropriate one is imperative to attain the benefits.

Some Asian food wholesale shops use online apps to record orders as Participant K (Managing Director) outlines:

We used to call customers to get their orders, and we had to make the invoices manually. But now, for the last three years, we have developed an app and gotten the customers to order

through the app. The customer can log in on their own account, and they can go through the whole products' catalogue and make their order. It saves us at least about 20 minutes on per customer. The customers are now pleased.

The use of apps not only saves time but makes ordering more efficient. A customer can log in and place an order any time using a smartphone.

Another respondent, Participant Q (Operation's Manager) collaborated with another company using their online platform to take orders. This is what he had to say:

We have an online ordering system using the website. This is our subsidiary company in which people can order online to get it delivered at their doorsteps.

The use of electronic and self-service tills is notable in South Asian food wholesale and retail shops. In addition, some medium-sized shops have introduced larger trolleys, and have provided car parking facilities. Clearly, South Asian-food wholesale SMEs are slowly but surely imitating supermarkets to improve their services and enhance their competitiveness.

4.3.5. Theme Five: The Openness in Innovation Strategy in South Asian food Wholesale SMEs and its Benefits

Innovation is paramount for any business to be competitive in the market. Innovative ideas come from anywhere. Choosing the right innovation and implementation strategy at the right time is even more critical. South Asian food SMEs are attracted to open innovation implementation as much as other SMEs in the business world. Customer feedback is the most common form of open innovation. Suppliers and internal employees play a significant role in innovation management.

.... It's an open market. We are working in an open market. Everybody has their right to say and the right to express their opinion. So, that gives us the platform to develop ourselves where the problems within our organisation. We do analysis to find our strengths and weaknesses. If we understand the strengths and weaknesses, then we can improve the business. Moreover, this is possible only in the open market. If we follow the closed strategy and don't want to listen to anybody, then we don't know what our strengths and weaknesses are; how would we know your opportunities and threats.....

(Participant G, Operation's Manager)

.... There is a huge benefit in implementing open innovation in our business. We know what customers want and how they want it. We work on that immediately without any delay. Therefore, the sales grow a noticeable amount, so does the profit.....

(Participant J, Managing Director)

Open innovation strategies are essential for Asian food SMEs, which seldom have the available resource to provide research funding to support promising academic research. Besides, SMEs often lack institutionalized, well-structured innovation processes. Therefore, working directly with customers, suppliers, and sometimes with competitors is a more compelling way to improve products and services for competitiveness. These open innovative strategies guide SMEs in building market awareness.

...The suppliers advise us on how to improve the products or services. We do take some ideas from them for business improvement. There are some other companies in the same industry, and they have got even better ideas than us. We can learn from them. We also get customer feedback on a regular basis for business improvement. We listen to our clients carefully and take the necessary actions to keep the customer happy....

(Participant K, Managing Director)

....It's very beneficial. We always speak to our suppliers. If we face any price issues, we let our suppliers know about it. Sometimes customers say, they buy certain products from the different shops at a low price. We request our suppliers to reduce the price of that certain product if they can. Most of the time, they agreed to reduce the price of that product. In that way, we keep our customers happy....

(Participant M, Operation's Manager)

There are countless benefits of collaborating with suppliers to become innovative in the marketplace. Suppliers provide funds on a retro basis.

.... We buy goods from our suppliers on a retro sale. If we buy ten palates of prawns, the supplier will refund us £2 in every case. For example, every 100 cases, we get £2000 back from our supplier. By this process, we can at least compete in the market. The suppliers provide us with funding. So, if we made any loss, then it would be covered by our suppliers. This is the beauty of collaborating with suppliers. This gives us a competitive advantage in the market....

(Participant L, Operation's Manager)

Asian food SMEs collaborate with suppliers to reduce the possibility of failing in the marketplace. As a consequence, SMEs receive financial support from suppliers.

Open innovation is about combining internal resources, ideas, and knowledge with external sources to enrich the innovation process. Such a business model encourages organisations to connect with external sources through collaboration, co-creation, and knowledge sharing to maximise the business's productivity. Previous studies on OI have noted that innovation is an interactive process in which organisations interact and collaborate with a variety of other actors such as other firms, universities, and consultants (Chesbrough, 2012; Pittaway, 2004).

Innovation is essential for enhancing competitiveness. Choosing the right innovation and implementation at the right time is even more critical. Asian food SMEs are as open in their innovation processes as other food firms in the market. The managers and directors of these Asian food shops use customer feedback, suppliers and employees' ideas and knowledge in developing products and services. Participant G (Operation's Manager) believes that modern business is an open market, and everybody has the right to express opinions. Interacting with others generates better ideas. The excerpt below is key:

We are working in an open market. Everybody has their right to say or right to express their opinion. So, that gives us the platform to develop ourselves where the problems within our organisation. We do an environmental analysis to find where our strengths are, what our weaknesses are, where the opportunities and the threats. So, if we understand the business environments, then we can improve the business. And this is possible only in the open market. If we follow a closed strategy and don't want to listen to anybody, then you don't know what your strengths and weaknesses are, how would you know your opportunities and threats.

Participant J (a Managing Director) also emphasised the benefits of implementing open innovation in food businesses, stating:

There is a huge benefit in implementing open innovation in our business. We know what customers want and how they want it. We work on that immediately without any delay. Therefore, the sales grow a noticeable amount so does the profit.

Lusch and Vargo (2006) believe that customers play essential roles in the innovation process and value creation activities, particularly in terms of their involvement in product design. This helps firms to improve their offer. Furthermore, Kemp (2013) argues that by understanding what customers value, and by engaging in active interactions, firms can develop superior value propositions relevant to their target customer base. Therefore, engaging customers in

innovating products and processes or services have a more significant impact on the food industry. Similarly, co-operation with suppliers enhances efficiency and productivity. There are countless benefits of co-operation or collaboration with suppliers as Participant L (Operation's Manager) illustrates below:

.... We buy goods from our suppliers on a retro sale. If we buy ten palates of prawns, the supplier will refund us £2 on every case. For example, every 100 cases we get £2000 back from our supplier. By this process, we can at least compete in the market. The suppliers provide us with funding. So, if we made any lose then it would be covered by our suppliers. This is the beauty of collaborating with the supplier. This gives us a competitive advantage in the market.

The findings suggest that some suppliers provide funding facilities to companies to compete in the market. Some suppliers offer retro sale systems whereby wholesalers get commission for sales of some particular products.

Furthermore, Participant K (a Managing Director) outlined the benefits of collaboration with suppliers to enhance competition in markets.

The suppliers advise us on how to improve the products or services. We do take some ideas from them for business improvement. There are some other companies in the same industry, they have got even better ideas than us. We can learn from them.

This finding resonates with the study of Karantininis et al. (2010) which suggests that the food and drink industry in particular shows a strong dependence on specialised suppliers to execute innovation for competitiveness. So, it is clear that Asian food SMEs receive a lot of financial and strategical support from suppliers to innovate and enhance their competitiveness in the market.

4.3.6. Theme Six: Factors Hinder Implementing OI in South Asian Food Wholesale SMEs

Many factors hinder South Asian food wholesale SMEs in implementing open innovation strategy. Economic and financial factors are amongst the main issues that impede SMEs from implementing open innovation. In addition, South Asian food wholesale SMEs often prefer not to seek advice from external sources. Furthermore, managerial incompetence, a lack of skilled workers, and inadequacies in technological usage by South Asian food wholesale SME staff all play a significant role in innovation management. In addition, Asian food SMEs also look at value creation while adapting technology to improve service. Indeed, a number of

calculations must be taken into consideration before embracing technology. The mindsets of SME entrepreneurs play a crucial role in this regard.

...We have a separate department in our head office. It's an internal department. They actually advise us about any innovation strategy to employ.....

(Participant A, Account Manager)

Some of these SMEs implement innovation strategies on their own. They use their own internal departments for this purpose.

There are some downsides to implementing open innovation strategies, as illustrated below:

.....The technology is there. It's just adapting the technology and understanding how technology can adapt to business needs. A lot of companies just use the system that is provided to them. We choose the technology modules that we need for our business to fulfil the need of it.....

(Participant C, Operation's Manager)

In some cases, SMEs and tech firms might not share common goals. In such cases, collaboration with tech firms may become difficult.

In addition, food SME employees might not be familiar with technologies, and this creates some hesitation amongst firms to adopt technology in the process of innovation.

....A lack of knowledge of staff plays a big factor. We train them, as most of the staff are not educated and are from abroad. It's hard to get them to use technology to improve their work. We have all the systems in place whereby they can enter the stock quantities and produce weekly reports and ordering things. However, due to lack of knowledge and training, they are not able to use that kind of technology.....

(Participant E, Managing Director)

Furthermore, food SMEs also face issues in collaborating with suppliers as outlined below:

...Of course, we do face some pitfalls while collaborating with a particular supplier. For example, we were missing one of our popular items on the shelf because of the supply shortage. So, we don't have any other choice but to tell our customers that we are out of stock of that product. Therefore, we are losing customers for that. Sometimes suppliers don't give the right answer to why they are not delivering this specific product item....

(Participant N, General Manager)

.....Sometimes we have to hit a minimum quantity of goods to be delivered to our shop. In addition, the waiting time is a bit longer, sometimes considering the stock availability....

(Participant L, Operation's Manager)

Despite the benefits of open innovation, there are some key challenges when it comes to implementing open innovation in businesses. Various managers and directors take these challenges into consideration while choosing the right innovation strategy.

There are several factors that prevent South Asian food wholesale SMEs from implementing OI strategies. They often prefer not to seek advice from business consultants due to financial constraints and a lack of managerial skills. In addition, the implementation of innovation usually comes from in-house personnel. Participant A (Account Manager) states below:

We have a separate department in our head office. It's an internal department. They actually advise us about any innovation strategy to employ.

It is clear from the findings that these Asian food SMEs take ideas from external sources but innovate on their own due to financial and managerial constraints. The lack of trust with external parties could be another reason why these SMEs implement innovation internally.

Economic and financial factors are the two major issues that prevent SMEs from implementing OI strategies. Furthermore, the directors and managers of Asian food SMEs measure value creation while adopting technology for service improvement. The mindset of entrepreneurs also has a significant impact on technology adoption. Moreover, the compatibility between food SMEs and technological firms must be taken into consideration. As Participant C suggests:

The technology is there. It's just adapting the technology and understanding how technology can adapt to business needs. A lot of companies just use the system that is provided to them. We choose the technology modules that we need for our business to fulfil the need of it.

It is clear from the findings that technology should be easy to use and compatible to fulfil the need of the business. Sometimes food SMEs and tech firms have conflicts of interest. In such cases, a collaboration between the two can become difficult. In addition, employees of food SMEs may not be familiar with some of the modern gadgets which prevent SMEs from adopting technology into their businesses as Participant E (Managing Director) illustrates:

Lack of knowledge of staff plays a big factor. We train them, as most of the staff are not educated and are from abroad. It's hard to get them to use technology to improve their work. We have all the systems in place whereby they can enter the stock quantities and produce weekly reports and ordering things. But due to lack of knowledge and training, they are not able to use that kind of technology.

This aligns with views expressed by Verbano et al. (2015) and Enkel et al. (2009) who highlight that the lack of adequate managerial competence and managerial complexities hinder SMEs in terms of their innovative activities. Apart from the technological competencies evidenced by non-skilled workers, SMEs also face issues in collaborating with suppliers. Supply shortages also affect businesses.

When SMEs rely on one particular supplier, it becomes difficult to obtain supplies of that product because of collaborative agreements. The manager has no choice but to wait until his supplier delivers those goods as interpreted by Participant N. These food wholesale SMEs face some pitfalls. When they get their products from a specific supplier, and if there is a supply shortage, they have no alternative suppliers who can fulfil the customer demands. Therefore, collaborating with more than one supplier always have positive outcomes.

To summarise, the findings suggest that despite the benefits of implementing OI strategies to enhance competitiveness, there are some issues prevent South Asian food wholesale SMEs from implementing them.

4.4. Summary

The first part of the chapter presents the research findings extracted from interview data of this study. Then it discusses the findings of the study by outlining the hostile situation in the marketplace of South Asian food wholesale SMEs. There are a number of reasons why South Asian food wholesale SMEs are in such a situation, for instance, fierce competition, a lack of skilled manpower, and the power of supermarkets. Other business challenges that these food SMEs encounters include supply issues, customs rules, transportation costs, and a lack of marketing knowledge.

The second aspect of the findings examine the motives and triggers for OI strategies, and how open these relate to food SMEs seeking to enhance their competitiveness. In addition, the benefits of implementing open innovation and the factors that hinder innovation have been discussed in this chapter. This chapter also discussed the findings of this research by locating them in the broader context.

5. Conceptual Model

5.1. Introduction

This chapter formulates the conceptual model of the research by considering the findings of the research presented in the previous chapter. Prior to formulating the conceptual model, the conceptual framework presented in chapter two is revisited. This chapter also details how the research data aid in modifying the conceptual framework to match the requirements of the UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs.

5.2. Conceptual Model of Research

The conceptual framework in Section 2.8 was developed based on the existing literature. As previously discussed, the challenges involving OI as well as the outcomes of OI in the context of larger firms were already known in the literature. However, how SMEs use OI and what kind of challenges they face whilst implementing OI were not known, particularly in the context of food wholesaler SMEs. This research, therefore, investigated 19 UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs to explore how they use OI and what kind of challenges they face whilst implementing OI.

This study adopted a qualitative methodology. An inductive approach was used to build theory. Semi-structured interviews were applied for data collection. The results were based on interviews with 22 participants. Amongst those 22 interviewees, there were 19 directors and managers of South Asian food wholesale businesses and 3 industry experts. The findings indicated that the motives to become innovative are firmly market-oriented. The study identified that UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs mainly engage in two types of innovations: product and service. Product and service innovation was used to enhance the competitiveness of businesses in the market. This study also identified that South Asian food wholesale SMEs face particular challenges when importing from international markets. For instance, customs rules and customs taxes are substantial challenges. Customs rules, in particular, vary from country to country. These issues also set new challenges when implementing innovation as a means to overcome barriers.

The conceptual model for this study illustrates that customers, suppliers, competitors and to some extent, technological advancements drive South Asian food firms towards innovation.

The findings suggest that the motives for innovation come from market gaps, and the industry often plays an important role in that regard. Such innovation could be related to the product, the process, or the service. Open innovation strategy has no specific boundary in this sense (Huizingh, 2011). Therefore, numerous forms of innovation are notable (Sarkar and Costa, 2008). Both external and internal bodies help SMEs become innovative in product development, improving services, and thus enhancing their competitiveness in the market. The conceptual model for this study is depicted in figure 5.1.

Figure 5-1: Conceptual Model

Source: The Author

The above conceptual model was developed after carefully considering the findings of this research as well as the existing literature. The model reflects how open innovation implementation in food SMEs can enhance their competitiveness in the market. The conceptual

model highlights that collaboration with external partners helps UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs in their products and service innovation. Through this type of collaborative OI approach, which is achieved through knowledge sharing, the wholesale food SMEs can become more efficient, cost-effective, and, most importantly, create competitive barriers.

The existing literature indicated that open innovation occurs due to networking and collaborations between different internal and external parties, such as directors, employees, customers, and suppliers. This study's findings confirmed that it is also the case in the context of UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. The existing literature indicated that (as noted in Section 2.8) as a result of open innovation and successful coordination between different stakeholders, an organisation can secure numerous benefits, such as market development, product development, and production cost reduction. This research identified that open innovation leads to reduced production costs in the context of UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. This is because SMEs can reduce their R&D expenditure through collaborations with customers and suppliers by using knowledge sharing techniques. Additionally, open innovation also allows SMEs to achieve operational efficiency by collaborating with technological firms such as EPOS, Kukd.com, izettle and many more online ordering systems to be efficient and cost-effective.

Furthermore, collaborative open innovation with external partners, especially suppliers, creates competitive barriers in the marketplace. This study's findings suggest that SMEs make partnership agreements with their trusted suppliers for a specific product range. In this way, South Asian food wholesale SMEs can bring a unique product range to market. Thus, product differentiation creates competitive barriers for South Asian food wholesale SMEs. The section below elaborates on how SMEs coordinate and network with internal and external bodies to innovate.

5.2.1. Collaborating with Internal Bodies for Innovation

Knowledge exchange or knowledge sharing is essential for learning, and thus for innovation (Lundvall et al., 2002; Powell et al., 1996). Knowledge gathering from internal bodies is an important external source. Knowledge exchange can be made via interactions with different bodies within networks. The transfer of knowledge takes place through interactions between partners (Education, 2011; Inkpen and Tsang, 2005). The increasing complexity in the

innovation process has led food SMEs towards a greater dependency on interacting within networks (Edwards et al., 2005; Zeng et al., 2010). Internal bodies play a key role, especially employees, when it comes to developing products and services for Asian food SMEs.

The findings suggest that these food wholesale SMEs have frequent meetings with staff and senior managers to improve the businesses and enhance competitiveness and sustainability. It is very clear from the study findings that although South Asian food SMEs gather customer feedback, and interact with suppliers, they take many of the discussions that arise out of these interactions on board but implement the innovation processes in house. In other words, SMEs are more open to innovation, and all innovative ideas and knowledge are discussed within the company and implemented by internal bodies. The issues of trust are also key. The directors and managers of these South Asian SMEs take ideas from their office staff to delivery drivers in the process of innovation. These staff, in a sense, create value for the company.

Food firms should also look at their innovation capabilities and challenges in implementing collaborations based open innovation strategy. Therefore, the ability to make precise decisions is ultimately very important for directors and managers.

5.2.2. Collaborating with External Bodies for Innovation

The results suggest that the South Asian food wholesale shops engage in collaborative open innovation strategies with external bodies to become effective innovators, thereby enhancing their competitiveness. Knowledge, in this sense, derives from external sources, outside of the organisation's boundaries (Ferrerias-Mendez et al., 2015). External knowledge plays a vital role in minimising the costs associated with R&D and means the business can spread the risks associated with innovation developmental activities (Laursen, 2012; Leiponen, 2012).

5.2.2.1. Customer Involvement

Many studies apply the concept of 'customer involvement' in innovation (Carbonell et al., 2009; Knudsen, 2007; Lynch et al., 2016; Menguc et al., 2014). According to Vanhaverbeke and de Vrande (2008), innovative firms can begin the process of innovation and create ideas within their networks to capitalise on external knowledge while developing strategy internally in collaboration with customers. Customer involvement can be classified as a form of 'inbound open innovation' strategy since customers provide knowledge and information about their needs (Vaisnore and Patraite, 2011).

As the empirical findings of this study suggest, South Asian food wholesale SMEs receive a lot of customer feedback and take action based on this in the process of improving products and services and hence enhancing their competitiveness in the market. Participant M noted that customer interactions are a priority. These interactions allow wholesale food shops to receive feedback on products and services and, in this process, they can fulfil the needs of their customers effectively. The main priority for SMEs is to satisfy customers in every possible way.

Interactions with customers have a significant impact on sales revenue. Participant Q thinks that if customers are not looked after in terms of service excellence, then many stores would lose their position in the marketplace. Therefore, interacting with customers means that businesses have a better chance to understand the needs of their customers and a better chance to act on this information.

Therefore, customer feedback is necessary for SMEs in order to enhance the competitiveness since these food shops have limited internal resources and little means to invest in research and development.

5.2.2.2. Supplier Involvement

Brunswicker and Vanhaverbeke (2015) believe that external sources of knowledge gathering represent an important nonpecuniary mode of inbound open innovation. They discuss how firms can use external knowledge in a nonpecuniary way. Lauren and Salter (2006) argue that openness, measured as the number of outward sources, clearly affects organisations' financial performance. However, Gans and Stern (2003) contend that not all potential sources are of equal value for all innovative organisations. They believe that there are differences in the strength of interactions.

Therefore, interacting with suppliers, research labs, and universities are more effective pursuits in the innovation process. Dahlander and Gann (2010) emphasise that it is essential to concentrate on the particular nature and the distinct mix of interactions with external innovation partners. Interacting with suppliers provides ideas for technological solutions or process innovation (Brunswicker and Vanhaverbeke, 2015).

Interacting with suppliers has many benefits for UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. For example, such interactions reduce the risk associated with product development. The study findings suggest that the majority of South Asian food wholesale SMEs collaborate with their

suppliers to improve their existing products or develop new products. South Asian firms maintain a good relationship with suppliers, and thus they always supply quality products at a negotiable price. The relationship they maintain with suppliers tends to have been built up over the years.

South Asian wholesale firms collaborate with KTC, Natco and many other major food suppliers in a reciprocal way. Both parties get benefitted from these reciprocal relationships. Some South Asian food wholesale SMEs use their suppliers' distribution channels to deliver their own products. In this sense, they cut out costs and roll out products to broader markets. The benefit of collaborating with suppliers is that they keep an eye on the prices in the market. If the price charged by suppliers alters, then the managers talk to them and try to get a better deal. Managers in South Asian food wholesale shops believe that suppliers learn from them through feedback.

Furthermore, collaborating with suppliers allows food wholesalers to generate sales commissions on particular products. Moreover, most of the promotional products in the store are funded by suppliers. Some wholesalers approach the suppliers and make a deal to promote their products in cash and carry stores. The shop then generates some income, and if they make any losses, these are covered by their suppliers. In this sense, the wholesale shops can mitigate many market risks to gain a competitive advantage in the market. In the process of forming partnerships with suppliers, some South Asian wholesale shops create a competitive barrier to competitors. As part of a partnership agreement, suppliers cannot sell particular goods to other shops.

Moreover, through collaborative open innovation with suppliers, these wholesale firms can improve their packaging systems. This resonates with Welsh et al. (2016) study that vertical collaborations (i.e., collaborations with customers and suppliers) increases the commercial rates of innovation. In addition, Nieto and Santamaria (2007) study indicate that diversity in collaboration always brings the positive outcome for both incremental and radical innovation. It is clear that the South Asian food wholesale distribution sector implement vertical collaboration in order to enhance competitiveness in the market.

5.2.2.3. *Technological Firms*

Recent technological advancements have enabled businesses to improve. Technology advancements have given many a chance to improve their customer service. Although the food sectors have a low dependence on technological innovation, this study suggests that South

Asian food shops often improve their services by adopting new technologies. This is especially the case with apps that support online ordering systems.

In addition, South Asian food firms use intermediaries such as kukd.com, purple-i for the ordering systems. Furthermore, the wholesale shops have facilities for customers to use self-service to pay instead of queuing up to use tills. This makes these firms more efficient and cost-effective. Moreover, the electronic tills and payment processes make life easier for both shopkeepers and customers. The role of intermediaries, especially technological firms play a pivotal role in creating innovation systems for food SMEs. South Asian food wholesale SMEs use social media platforms for marketing themselves and their products and services. As Previous studies mentioned that market-oriented actors (i.e., Customer, Suppliers, Other Technological firms) therefore play a distinctive role in innovation in food SMEs (Bigliardi et al., 2011; Zeng et al., 2010; Knudsen, 2007).

5.3. Summary

This chapter presented the conceptual model of the study to show how South Asian food wholesale SMEs can enhance their competitiveness in the market. Business sustainability depends on competitiveness in the market. In the hostile Asian food market, business sustainability can only be assured by enhancing competitiveness in the market. South Asian food SMEs, especially wholesale firms, use both internal as well as external bodies to improve their product, packaging, and services innovation.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1. Introduction

This concluding chapter revisits the existing objectives and elaborates the process in which they were achieved. Besides, this chapter also details the key managerial implications, along with the theoretical and methodological contributions. Furthermore, this chapter also highlights the study limitations and the scope of future studies.

6.2. Revisiting Research Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study was to investigate open innovation strategy implementation in the context of UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. To achieve the research aim, the researcher adopted a qualitative research method. Qualitative research methods are useful for understanding the social and cultural settings within which people live (Saunders et al., 2016). The benefit of qualitative inquiry is that it allows researchers to see and understand the context in which decisions and actions take place (Myers, 2020). In this research, the researcher gathered data using semi-structured in-depth interviews with directors and managers of 19 UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs, and three industry experts.

6.2.1. Objective One: Reviewing the Existing Literature and Developing a Conceptual Framework

The first research objective was developed to critically review the existing literature on Open Innovation to explore various OI strategies, OI models, the importance of OI to SMEs and challenges involving the implementation of OI in SMEs. In order to achieve the first objective, a wide-scale literature review was conducted by reviewing various peer-reviewed journal articles, books and reliable government websites. A review of the literature identified various strategies of Open innovation, such as Inbound OI, Outbound OI and Coupled OI. In addition, challenges faced by SMEs and how open innovation can be used for overcoming those challenges were also reviewed. Although open innovation as a management topic was introduced over a decade ago, it has, recently, increasingly become a matter of contention.

Previous studies on open innovation looked at how open innovation was implemented in large firms as well as in SMEs to improve technological usage. Furthermore, past studies divulged

how open innovation is implemented in various food sector SMEs. However, very few studies specifically explored open innovation strategy implementation in UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. Therefore, this study sought to contribute to the academic literature by looking at how open innovation is implemented in UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs to enhance their competitiveness in the market. Based on the existing literature, a conceptual framework was formulated in Section 2.8. The framework summarised how SMEs collaborate with their external networking partners in the form of open innovation for effective product and service development.

6.2.2. Objective Two: Strategic Challenges Faced by UK-Based South Asian Food Wholesale SMEs

The second research objective was developed to explore the strategic challenges faced by UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. In order to understand the challenges faced by UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 19 managers and directors working in UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. The collected data was analysed using thematic analysis. This study found that UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs operate within a hostile environment. The results revealed that UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs face a greater challenge than ever before. The key challenges they face include intense competition, added legal and customs requirements, and staff shortages.

The findings also outlined that the main competitors of the South Asian food market are local UK supermarkets as they have higher buying power. UK supermarkets have started selling halal meat, which is challenging for South Asian shops as their consumers now have alternative suppliers. Aggressive pricing strategies adopted by supermarkets have become the biggest challenge in this sense. Economies of scale and the greater purchasing power of supermarkets distort the nature of competition in the South Asian food market. In addition, high operating costs sometimes hamper SMEs who adopt low-cost strategies. Furthermore, this study also found that the South Asian food sector, especially the catering sector, is facing staff shortages. Wholesale firms mainly supply South Asian goods to the Asian catering sector. These businesses are, therefore, interlinked. On the other hand, the UK's strict immigration policy is considered one of the reasons why the industry is facing staff shortages. The findings suggest

that restaurateurs are unable to meet the immigration criteria to hire skilled workers from South Asia.

Supply chain management is an essential factor that can facilitate competitiveness in the market. Despite the substantial benefits of supply chain management, the majority of South Asian food wholesale SMEs do not have their own supply chain and logistics; only those who are subsidiary companies of larger firms use their own logistics and supply chains. The study found that only a few medium-sized wholesalers have the opportunity to create their own supply chain to compete in the market. Therefore, the majority of shops import their goods from external suppliers and therefore face supply challenges. Brexit is another main challenge faced by SMEs. Different customs rules and customs duties are new challenges for South Asian food wholesale SMEs following Brexit. The majority of Asian goods are imported from different parts of the world, and import tariffs are not the same for every country. Therefore, high import tariffs are affecting inventory costs and product prices. As this research revealed various strategic challenges faced by UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs, objective two was fully achieved.

6.2.3. Objective Three: Revealing OI Strategies of SMEs and Evaluating Their Effectiveness

The third research objective sought to reveal the OI strategies used by UK-based South Asian wholesale food SMEs and to evaluate their effectiveness in mitigating the competitive barriers. In order to explore key OI strategies used by UK-based South Asian wholesale food SMEs, qualitative data was collected from 19 managers and directors of UK-based South Asian wholesale food SMEs and 3 UK food industry experts. The collated data was analysed using thematic analysis. The analysis revealed that South Asian food firms have begun to adopt innovative strategies to overcome their business challenges. South Asian wholesale SMEs created their own branded products to differentiate. Some used their own supply chain logistics. In addition, many understood the market challenges and have introduced tinned food which had a positive impact on product ranges. Fruits and vegetables in can last longer than traditional packaged goods.

Besides, UK-based South Asian wholesale food SMEs have adopted numerous other strategies for OI; for example, they have collaborated with external bodies, such as customers, suppliers,

competitors and technological intermediaries. Collaborating with external partners helps food wholesale SMEs mitigate market risks. Many South Asian food wholesale SMEs have improved their product packaging systems by collaborating with customers and suppliers. This research also revealed that the managers of South Asian food businesses give priority to customer feedback, and act quickly on it. They are more flexible and able to respond to customer preferences at some pace compared to large firms. SMEs are less bureaucratic than large firms, and their decision making is a lot faster and is responsive to changing market conditions. Since employees are an integral part of any organisation, these wholesale food firms often take on board employees' ideas and knowledge in the process of creating competitive barriers. The results found that all staff members are directly involved in generating new ideas around products, processes and service innovation.

Furthermore, the study findings indicated that technological advancement has helped SMEs improve their services. South Asian food wholesale SMEs have recently introduced EPOS, online line ordering apps and websites, and self-service systems that mitigate challenges of staff shortages. Furthermore, they are now advertising more on social media platforms to reach out to customers. These findings provide substantial insights into SMEs' OI strategies and contribute to the literature; hence, this objective is fully achieved.

6.2.4. Objective Four: Role of Networking in OI in UK-Based South Asian Food Wholesale SMEs

The fourth research objective was developed to understand how effective networking with external partners can facilitate OI in UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. Semi-structured and in-depth interviews with 19 directors and managers of UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs and 3 industry experts in the UK food industry revealed that effective networking provides SMEs with opportunities to thrive in the challenging market. This is because networking enables the exchange of knowledge, which subsequently, in some cases, results in successful new product development. Effective collaboration with networking partners, such as customers, suppliers, competitors and technological firms, always brings value to SMEs because they are able to collect much-needed market insights. In the sample, it was noted that the UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs collaborate with their networking partners, such as customers and suppliers, to gain insights for new product development. The research findings indicated that effective collaboration with external

partners can bring operating costs down by a significant margin. This is because SMEs often use their supplier's transportation systems to deliver goods to the customer's door. These findings of the research make substantial contributions to knowledge by adding new insights to the literature.

6.2.5. Objective Five: Providing Recommendations to the Practitioners in the Industry

The final objective of the research was developed to provide recommendations to the practitioners in UK-based South Asian Food wholesale SMEs for enhancing their organisational competitiveness and performance based on the research findings. Section 6.3.1 provides recommendations to the practitioners in the UK-Based South Asian Food wholesale SMEs based on the findings of this research.

6.3. Contributions of the Research

Contributions of this research are presented in two categories: managerial and theoretical.

6.3.1. Managerial Contributions

The various directors, managers and industry experts outlined the benefits of implementing open innovation strategies for business success. Understanding the importance of the Asian food market in a diversified British culture and the significance of the British economy is key. Companies should follow a robust, innovative framework to be effective and sustainable in the market. Mr X (Industry Expert) and many other participants believed that the sector could be improved if more changes were adopted. These are listed below and are accompanied by explanations.

6.3.1.1. Infrastructural Changes

The findings suggest that the South Asian food wholesale SMEs industry must undergo some infrastructural change. The national chairman of the federation of small businesses emphasised that poor infrastructure is a major frustration for small business owners. Mr X (Industry Expert) thinks that this industry needs to undergo significant change and it requires modern equipment and new technology.

Avermaete and Viaene (2002) also support this argument and suggest that the food industry should undertake innovative processes to improve its product quality, expand consumer confidence and encourage modernisation. Infrastructural deficiency negatively impacts SME business performance (Obokoh and Goldman, 2016). Therefore, the managers and owners of such businesses should adopt modern technology, online platforms, and digital marketing to improve their services.

In addition, the managers of these shops understood the importance of market diversification. Market and product diversification are key elements to enhance competitiveness. Participant A believes that it is essential to diversify the market. Instead of targeting one cuisine, companies should adopt different types of cuisine to attract the mass market. In this way, companies could become more competitive and sustainable.

Therefore, infrastructural change is needed for both medium-sized and small companies. The local council could also play a significant role in supporting such businesses.

6.3.1.2. Selecting the Right Suppliers

Selecting the right suppliers is an important task for companies to effectively establish supply chain management. This is not a straightforward task. Supplier selection involves much more than scanning through a series of price lists. In a competitive market, supplier selection is a critical task for enhancing the performance of the company. Xu J et al. (2017) argue that it is a critical task for firms to choose the right suppliers as potential suppliers help organisations to deliver high-quality products at a reasonable price.

The findings suggest that South Asian food shops often face delivery delays or goods of compromised quality. Participant N said that he occasionally faces delivery issues with suppliers. He also stated that suppliers are sometimes unable to account for delivery delays, and this affects trust between the two.

Therefore, it is proposed that the firm should avoid relying on a single supplier and look for other suppliers in the market. Building a relationship with suppliers must be based on trust, quality, reliability and value for money (Duica et al., 2018). It is always worth having more than one supplier ready to help in difficult circumstances.

6.3.1.3. Better Stock Control

An effective and efficient inventory management control is one of the key variables in businesses. Therefore, food companies from manufacturing to wholesalers and retailers need

effective inventory management to operate successfully. Byoungho (2004) stated that the ideal inventory and proper merchandise turnover would differ from market to market. Billington et al. (2004) illustrated a large inventory may not be justified because the turnover may not warrant the investment. On the contrary, too small an inventory may not fulfil the demand of customers (Byoungho, 2004). As a result, this can minimise profits as customers will go somewhere else to buy items.

Therefore, better stock control is required. The study results have ascertained that stock control is an issue for Asian food SMEs. Stock control systems are poorly managed in these shops. An interview with Participant L (an operations manager) suggests that firms need to follow a rigorous stock control system. Keeping stock records using technology can minimise the unnecessary costs of holding the stock for too long. It is also necessary to stock exclusive, branded products to create competition in the market.

6.3.1.4. Introducing Modern Technology

Technological advancements are a blessing for many businesses. Technological advancements drive retailers and wholesale shops forward rapidly. Technology can be considered a strategic weapon, and research on technology observes how it works best when it fits with business strategies and corporate planning (Ryan, 1996; Zahra and Bogner, 2000).

Technology utilisation is reasonably low in the UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. However, the trend is now changing. Analysis suggests that only a few South Asian wholesale stores use online ordering systems such as apps, websites, and other online platforms. Technology plays a vital role in new product development and improving service. Retailers should adapt to change and increasing technological usage to become more effective and efficient. The participants outlined the importance of technological implementation in their businesses. For example, using social media platforms for the purpose of advertising and marketing which could enhance competitiveness. Asian food wholesalers should collaborate more with technological firms to improve their services.

6.3.1.5. Staff Training

Employee training is necessary for Asian food shops. The study results highlighted that SMEs have an insufficient resource of trained and skilled manpower. Participant E (a Managing Director) outlined the importance of customer service in the food sector SMEs, yet he has too few trained staff. Better trained staff could improve businesses according to this study.

Employees must have the product knowledge to ensure better service for customers. In addition, employees in these sectors lack sufficient technological knowledge. Therefore, management must provide employee training facilities to increase employee efficiency.

6.3.1.6. Implementing Marketing Strategy

South Asian food SMEs should adopt digital marketing through social media. This is an inexpensive and effective way to market products and services. Digital marketing has transformed businesses to be able to communicate with their audiences. The study results found that only a few companies invest in online marketing. Ozuem et al. (2008) study identified that the development of virtual marketplace allows businesses to set up websites that are effective platforms for advertising to the broader community. Therefore, it is recommended that these companies should optimise social media platforms for digital marketing to attract more customers. In addition, these food SMEs could introduce coupons and loyalty discount systems for their customers.

Past research has revealed that using loyalty programmes as a method to retain customers is more profitable to sell to regular customers than acquire new ones (Rust and Zahorik, 1993; Storbacka et al., 1994; Ozuem et al., 2016). Li and Green (2011) study outlined that a stable customer base is a core business asset. Their study also emphasised that a successful customer loyalty strategy can lead to enhanced customer retention rates.

In short, the managers of these firms should be more proactive, ready to adopt change and consciously seeking out any opportunities to be innovative.

6.3.2. Theoretical Contributions

6.3.2.1. Conceptual Model for Open Innovation in Food SMEs

Section 2.8 of this thesis presented the research conceptual framework that was developed based on the existing literature. This research tested the research conceptual framework in the context of UK-based food wholesale SMEs by examining a case of 19 UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs to explore how they use OI and what kind of business outcome a successful OI process can result in. The investigation revealed that UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs mainly engage in two types of innovations: product and service. Product and service innovation were used to enhance the competitiveness of businesses in the market. This research identified that open innovation leads to reduced production cost in the context of UK-

based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. This is because SMEs can reduce their R&D expenditure through collaborations with customers and suppliers by using knowledge sharing techniques. Based on the findings of this research, the conceptual framework of the research was modified, and a conceptual model was formulated in Section 5.2. The proposed conceptual model provides insights to future researchers regarding the process and outcome of OI in the context of UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs and bridges the existing knowledge gap, making substantial contributions to the literature.

6.3.2.1. Adding new insights to the literature

This study sought to bridge the gaps in academic knowledge concerning open innovation. Previous studies have been undertaken on open innovation in food SMEs (Kühne et al., 2013; Baregheh et al., 2014; Lefebvre et al., 2015; Bigliardi and Galati, 2016; Torok et al., 2019; Sadat and Nasrat, 2020). However, no study was conducted on implementing open innovation strategy to enhance competitiveness in food wholesale SMEs. Therefore, this study sought to contribute knowledge to the literature of open innovation in the context of UK-based South Asian food wholesale SMEs. Some points below explain how this study theoretically contributes to knowledge.

Firstly, previous research focussed on the challenges of exploiting open innovation in the food industry without focusing on a specific SME group. This study investigated the competitive challenges faced by South Asian wholesale food SMEs.

Secondly, previous research investigated the barriers that are perceived by Italian SMEs in adopting the OI paradigm. Data were gathered via survey questionnaires carried out on various SMEs including food and beverage, packaging, pharmaceutical, chemical, and other firms. This single case study-based research investigated perceptions of open innovation strategies as perceived by South Asian food wholesale SMEs as a means to overcome barriers and enhance competitiveness. The researcher used a social constructionist approach and analysed interview data to develop knowledge about this social phenomenon.

Moreover, the study explored the motives and drivers that were salient in fostering open innovation in the context of South Asian-food sector wholesale SMEs. The findings suggest that an outside-in (inbound) open innovation strategy is a common form of innovation for South Asian firms seeking to improve their products and services. In addition, this study shows the

importance of networking and collaboration in order to become innovative and competitive in the market. These findings make contributions to the knowledge by adding new insights.

6.4. Limitations and Scope for Future Research

As is the case for all research, this study was subject to certain limitations. A key limitation of the study was that it only focused on one sector of the industry. As a result of carrying out case study-based research, the generalisability of the study findings is challenging.

Getting access to data was very difficult as the managers and directors of the companies were, in some cases, unwilling to participate because of their busy schedules. Only 22 participants were therefore interviewed. However, the researcher used various company websites and company reports to support the study findings.

This study involved interacting with directors and managers. Future studies could investigate the issues from the customer as well as supplier perspectives.

The qualitative inquiry was selected to gain insight into a particular social phenomenon. Future studies could develop upon these findings and conduct quantitative research to test the findings on a larger population. Moreover, future studies should expand to other ethnic minority food sectors to enhance the generalisation of the conclusion.

6.5. Summary

This chapter presented a conclusion to the thesis. It revisited the study objectives and recommended a framework for managers to effectively implement open innovation strategies to enhance their competitiveness in the market. In addition, it outlined the academic contribution, research limitations and the scope of future research.

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8. APPENDICES

Appendix 1

Interview Participants Invitation Letter

Dear Sir,

My name is Md Habibur Rahman, and I am a DBA (Doctor of Business Administration) student at the University of the West of Scotland in London Campus. I am investigating a Project concerning open innovation strategy practice in the South Asian food wholesale sector SMEs in the UK market. Therefore, I am collecting data and information through interviews with managers and owners as part of my doctoral research study. As a successful business owner/manager, you are in an ideal position to share your valuable business strategic information from your perspective.

The interview will take approximately 45 minutes or a little more and is very formal. The principal aim of this interview is to capture your thoughts and perspectives as a business owner/manager. Your responses to questions will strictly be kept confidential, and your identity will be anonymous while analysing the interview data in this research. There is no comparison for participating in this study. However, your participation will be a valuable addition to this study. The interview findings could lead to a greater public understanding of the open innovation practice in SME food sector SMEs in the UK market.

If you are willing to participate or someone better placed in the company to discuss these issues in the interview, please suggest a suitable day and time, and I'll be available. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask. You can contact me by mobile phone or email.

Thank you for reading this and considering whether to participate in this study.

Kind regards,

Md Habibur Rahman

Email:

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 2

Participant Consent Form

Research Project Title: An Exploration of Open Innovation Practices in Food SMEs: A Case of UK Based Asian Food Wholesalers.

Research Investigator: Md Habibur Rahman

The interview will take around 45 minutes. I don't anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to stop the interview or withdraw from the research at any time.

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of the research project. Ethical procedures for academic research undertaken from UK institutions require the interviewees explicitly agree to being interviewed and how the data and information from the interview will be used in this project. This consent form is necessary the researcher to ensure that you are fully understood the purpose of this project and your involvement.

Please read and complete this form carefully by ticking Yes/No. If you are willing to participate in this project, ring the appropriate responses and sign and date the declaration at the end. If you do not understand anything and would like more information, please ask.

- I have had the research satisfactorily explained to me in verbal and / or written form by the researcher. **YES / NO**
- I understand that the research will involve business related information for example: the total turnover, profit or loss, business strategy. The interview will be recorded, and the time involved around 30 minutes **YES / NO**
- I understand that I may withdraw from this study at any time without having to give an explanation. This will not affect my future care or treatment. **YES / NO**

- I understand that all information about me will be treated in strict confidence and that I will not be named in any written work arising from this study. **YES / NO**

- I understand that any audiotape material of me will be used solely for research purposes and will be destroyed on completion of your research. **YES / NO**

- I understand that you will be discussing the progress of your research with your Director of study/supervisor/Assessor. **YES / NO**

I have understood the purpose of this project and therefore, I freely give my consent to participate in this study, also I have been given the copy of this information sheet and consent form.

Signature:

Name in Block Capitals:.....

Position:.....

Date:

Appendix 3

Research Participant Information Sheet

Research Title

An Exploration of Open Innovation Practices in Food SMEs: A Case of UK Based Asian Food Wholesalers.

Invitation

You are being invited to take part of the research project. Before you decide to do so, it is important to know and understand the reason of conducting this study. Please take your time to carefully read the following paragraphs in order to understand the concept of this study and discuss it with others if you wish. It is entirely your decision whether you want to participate or not in this project. Thank you for reading it.

The purpose of this study

The main purpose of this study is to explore the open innovation practices in food SMEs in the context of UK-based South Asian-food wholesalers to enhance the competitiveness in the market.

Reasons the participants are chosen

This study is to investigate open innovation practice to South Asian owned food wholesale SMEs to enhance competitive in the UK market. Your company is one of the food companies in the UK market. As a Manager/Owner, you have the knowledge in this regard.

What will be asked in the interview

The participant will be asked semi-structured questions regarding the investigated topic. The questionnaire will be very straight forward. The interview will only take around 45 minutes. The participation in this study will not cause you any disadvantage or discomfort.

The possible benefits of participating in the project

There is no immediate benefit/s for the participants. It is hoped that this work will make impacts or contribute to the business study.

Participants confidentiality

All the information that I will be collecting while study will be kept strictly confidential. The gathered data will be used anonymously so as the participants names. The result of the research data may be published but the name will be kept anonymous.

Right to Refuse or Withdraw

The decision to participate in this study is entirely up to you. You may stop or refuse to take part in the study at any time without affecting your relationship with the researcher.

Ethically reviewed project

This project has ethically approved by the University Ethics Committee.

For more information

This research has been reviewed and approved by the University of the West of Scotland Research Ethics Committee. If you have any further questions or concerns about this study, please contact:

Name of the researcher: **Md Habibur Rahman**

UWS Business School and Enterprise.

E-mail:

Personal details withheld.

Thank you for reading this information sheet and considering whether to participate in this study.

Appendix 4

Guided questions for Semi-Structured Interview with Directors/Managers

I am conducting a study to investigate open innovation practice in the food sector SMEs in the UK market. Open innovation means a situation where a company not just rely on their own internal knowledge, sources and resources (such as their own employees or R&D for example) for innovation (products, services, processes) but also uses multiple external sources (such as customer feedback, competitors, external agencies, the public to drive innovation. This interview will take 45 minutes or little more and it will have a semi-structured interview format. This means you can elaborate/intricate your answers and new questions may arise during the interview. The interview will be voice recorded for data analysis.

Section A. General view of company and its industry:

1. Would you like to tell me about your company? Concerning company size, how big your firm/company is? Is it Micro (0-9 employees), small (10-49 employees) or medium (50-249 employees) in size?

-Company established

-Your position in the company

2. In your viewpoint, what is the current situation of South Asian-food wholesale sector especially, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the UK market?

Section B. Innovation in general and its application to food business

Innovation generally refers to changing processes or creating more effective processes, products or services. For businesses this could mean implementing new ideas, creating dynamic products or improving existing products or services

3. Could you please tell me the type of innovative approaches that your company recently used to satisfy the customers?

4. How does the main source of innovation usually come from in your firm? For example: from employees (Senior managers), from customers, or from the area?

5. Could you now please tell me how you develop innovation strategy within your firm? Do you prepare by yourself or do you consult any other firms or institutions?

6. Does your firm face any challenges in the market from the competitors? If yes, then what types of barriers do you encounter from your competitors?

Section C. Open innovation practice in South Asian food SMEs

The term open innovation means a situation where an organisation doesn't just rely on their own internal knowledge, sources and resources (such as their own staff or R&D for example) for innovation (of product or services) but also uses multiple external sources such as customer feedback, competitors, suppliers, external agencies to drive innovation.

7. Based on the definition that I have mentioned, could you please tell me which open innovation strategy your firm has practised and why? It's complete story.

8. From your viewpoint as an owner or manager, could you please tell me what are the benefits you think of practising open innovation strategy in your company?

9. What are the downsides/pitfalls you faced when trying to implement open innovation? (factors such as financial, lack of skilled workers, the inability of using technological tools, knowledge sharing with others).

10. How to overcome such challenges to implement open innovation successfully within the food industry to be more competitive and sustainable in the market?

11. Do you have any other suggestions to improve and manage the integration during the open innovation process either with internal or external actors?

Appendix 5

Guided interview questions for Industry Experts on Asian food in the UK market.

Please tell me about yourself.

1. As an industry expert, could you please tell me what the current situation of South Asian-food SMEs is in the UK market? (Factors such as Economic contribution, Employability).
2. In your point of view, could you please tell me, what are the barriers of South Asian-food SMEs in the UK market which hinders their competitiveness in the market?
3. How can your stated barriers be overcome by these firms for their competitiveness in the market?
4. Are food firms open to innovation? If Yes, what open innovation methods and concepts are most commonly applied in the Asian-food industry?
5. From your viewpoint, could you please mention what challenges do food SMEs face when trying to implement open innovation methods within firms?
6. What are the potential opportunities for food firms to practice open innovation? And how should they go about it to successfully implement open innovation?
7. How does collaboration work for food sectors SMEs?
8. What kind of supports are available from business agencies for food SMEs to be more open to innovation for their competitiveness?
9. As an industry expert, by considering the importance of food SMEs in UK economy and open innovation practising opportunities, what would be your recommendations to food firms to successfully implement open innovation practice for the competitiveness?

.....**End**.....